

Air quality maps of EEA member and cooperating countries for 2022

PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, NO₂, NO_x and BaP spatial estimates and their uncertainties

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Summary

Air quality concentrations maps of the member and cooperating countries of the European Environmental Agency (EEA)⁽¹⁾ have been prepared for the year 2022. The maps are primarily based on air quality data as reported under the Ambient Air Quality Directives (EC, 2004, 2008). The mapping method ('Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping') follows a methodology developed earlier (Horálek et al., 2024, and references cited therein); it combines the monitoring data with outputs from a chemical transport model and other supplementary data such as land cover and satellite data.

Population exposure

Regarding population exposure to air pollutants, concentrations of PM₁₀ (i.e. particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm or less) remained above the European Union (EU) and World Health Organisation (WHO) standards in large parts of Europe in 2022. Approximately 8 % of the considered European population was exposed to concentrations above the EU PM₁₀ limit value of 40 µg/m³ and 77 % of population was exposed to concentrations exceeding the WHO Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level of 15 µg/m³ in 2022 (WHO, 2021a). Furthermore, 19 % of the population was estimated to live in areas where the 90.4 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily means was above the EU limit value of 50 µg/m³. Approximately 1 % and 5 % of the considered European population (excluding Türkiye in this case of PM_{2.5}) was exposed to concentrations above the EU PM_{2.5} limit value of 25 µg/m³ and above the EU PM_{2.5} indicative limit value of 20 µg/m³, respectively. Moreover, 97 % of the population was exposed to concentrations above the 2021 WHO AQG level of 5 µg/m³. Figure S.1 (top) illustrates that the countries with the highest values of annual averages PM_{2.5} are located in south-eastern Europe.

For ozone, it was estimated that 17 % of the considered European population lived in areas where concentrations exceeded the ozone target value threshold. Figure S.1 (middle) shows that countries with the highest values of the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means are situated in southern and central Europe. Additionally, 98 % of the considered European population lived in areas where the ozone concentration was above the 2021 WHO AQG level of 60 µg/m³ (the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means).

Approximately 3 % of the considered European population was exposed to NO₂ concentrations above the EU annual limit value of 40 µg/m³ in 2022. Figure S.1 (bottom) illustrates that, except for Türkiye, the majority of population lived well below the limit value in 2022. However, about 75 % of the considered European population was exposed to annual average concentrations above the 2021 WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³.

Based on the experimental map of benzo(a)pyrene (BaP), it is estimated that 14 % of the considered European population live in areas where BaP concentrations are above the EU target value. The highest BaP concentrations are shown in Poland, north-eastern Czechia and some populated locations in central and south-eastern Europe, in the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy, and in Finland.

⁽¹⁾ The EEA member countries are the 27 Member States of the European Union (EU-27), plus Iceland, Lichtenstein, Norway, Switzerland, and Türkiye. The EEA cooperating countries are Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo under the UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia. In addition, three microstates (Andorra, a country which voluntary reports air quality data, Monaco and San Marino) are also presented in this report.

Figure S.1 Concentrations of PM_{2.5} annual average (top), O₃ indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means (middle) and NO₂ annual average (bottom) to which the population per country was exposed in 2022. The EU limit value (for PM_{2.5} and NO₂) or target value threshold (for O₃) is marked by the red line, the EU PM_{2.5} indicative limit value by the orange line, the 2005 WHO AQG level by the yellow line and the 2021 WHO AQG by the green line. In the case of NO₂, both the 2005 WHO AQG level and the EU limit value are 40 µg/m³ and marked by the red line.

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50 % in the case of the black marker, 25 % and 75 % in the cases of the box's edges, 2 % and 98 % in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

Accumulated risks

Out of the total population of 559 million in the mapped area, almost 7 % (38.3 million) people live in areas where two or three of these air quality standards are exceeded; 0.09 % (0.5 million) people live in areas where all three standards are exceeded. The worst situation in 2022 was observed in Greece, Türkiye and Italy (in particular the Po valley), where 0.6 %, 0.4 % and 0.3 % lived in areas where all three standards are exceeded, respectively.

Vegetation exposure

In a limited number of cases, concentrations of NO_x are above the EU critical level. However, since most of these cases happen in urban areas, this is only relevant if there is vegetation in those areas. Ozone concentrations (AOT40 for vegetation) are above the EU target value threshold for the protection of vegetation in about 33 % of the agricultural areas and above the EU long-term objective in 88 % of the agricultural areas. Ozone concentrations (AOT40 for forests) are above the critical level for the protection of forests in about 63 % of the forested areas.

In 2022, POD₆ values for wheat above the highest critical level (CL) (i.e. for protein yield) are found mainly in central, western and southern Europe. POD₆ values for potatoes exceeded the CL for tuber yield across a large continuous area of central Europe, with the exception of several regions. Regions with POD₆ values for potatoes higher than the CL for tuber yield were also found in western Europe and parts of southern Europe. On the other hand, POD₆ values above the critical level for tomatoes were recorded only in a few coastal areas, similar to previous years.

The CL of POD₁ for beech was exceeded in almost the entire European mapped area, with the exception of large areas in Spain and Türkiye and many smaller areas throughout the mapped area. The CL of POD₁ for spruce was exceeded almost throughout the entire mapped European area, with the exception of large areas in northern Europe and the larger area in Romania extending into Bulgaria.

Changes over time

Since 2005, maps for most of the pollutants have been prepared in an overall consistent way (although the mapping methodology has been subject to continuous improvement). This enables an analysis of changes in exposure over time. Apart from minor methodological changes, a major change was introduced for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} since 2017 maps, taking into account air quality in urban traffic areas. For some pollutants, maps of several years are not available.

The evolution of the population-weighted concentrations, as a measure of population exposure, is shown in Figure S.2, while the evolution of the agricultural-weighted concentration is presented in Figure S.3. For comparability reasons, the results based on both the old and the new PM mapping methodology have been included in Figure S.2. As the regular NO₂ maps are not available for all years, an alternative mapping results prepared based on a subset of stations for the purpose of trend analysis 2005-2019 (Horálek et al., 2022a) are also presented, in addition.

The PM population-weighted concentrations show a steady decrease of about 0.6 µg/m³ per year for PM₁₀ annual average and 0.5 µg/m³ per year for PM_{2.5} annual average. It is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to a PM₁₀ annual mean concentration of 18 µg/m³ and to a PM_{2.5} annual mean concentration of 11 µg/m³ in 2022, being both the lowest values in the eighteen-year time series (together with the years 2020 and 2021).

For the ozone population-weighted concentration (expressed as SOMO35) no trend is observed for the period 2005-2022, due to the year-to-year variability. Also, no trend is observed for the agricultural-weighted concentration, in terms of AOT40 for vegetation.

The NO₂ population-weighted concentration (in terms of annual average) shows a decrease of about 0.6 µg/m³ per year over the period 2005-2022.

Figure S.2 Population-weighted concentration of PM₁₀ (annual mean), PM_{2.5} (annual mean), ozone (SOMO35), and NO₂ (annual mean) in 2005-2022. For PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, results based on both the old (blue dots) and the updated (red dots) mapping methodology are presented, where available. For NO₂, results based on both the regular (red) and the trend analysis (blue) maps are presented, where available.

Figure S.3 Agricultural-weighted concentration of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation in 2005-2022

1 Introduction

This report provides air quality concentration maps, population exposure and vegetation exposure estimates for 2022 for the area of the EEA member and cooperating countries. It builds on previous similar reports (Horálek et al., 2024, and references cited therein). The analysis is based on interpolation of annual statistics of validated monitoring data from 2022, reported by the EEA member and cooperating countries (and the voluntary reporting microstate of Andorra) in 2022. Two other microstates (Monaco and San Marino) are also included in the assessment. Türkiye (including both European and Asian areas) is included in the mapping area for all pollutants except PM_{2.5}, due to the lack of enough PM_{2.5} reported data in 2022 to the AQ e-reporting database from rural stations in Türkiye (EEA, 2024).

In this report 2022 results for particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5})⁽²⁾ ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) are presented, being the most relevant pollutants for annual updating due to their potential impacts on health and ecosystems. The analysis method applied is similar to that of previous years. BaP is presented for the third time in this regular report, based on the method shown in Horálek et al. (2022b).

The mapping is primarily based on air quality measurements. It combines monitoring data, chemical transport model results and other supplementary data (such as altitude and meteorology). The method is a linear regression model followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that model ("residual kriging"). It should be noted that this methodology does not allow for formal compliance checking with the legal standards as set by the Ambient air quality directives (EC, 2004, 2008).

The maps of health-related indicators of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and NO₂ are constructed by the improved mapping methodology developed in Horálek et al. (2017b, 2018, 2019): together with the rural and urban background map layers, the urban traffic map layer is constructed and incorporated into the final merged map using the road data. All individual map layers are created at 1 km resolution and land cover and road data are included in the mapping process as supplementary data. The maps of health-related indicators of O₃ are created for the rural and urban (including suburban) background areas separately on a grid of 10 km resolution. In this report, map for ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour is presented for the first time. Subsequently, the rural and urban background maps are merged into one final combined air quality indicator map using a 1 km population density grid, following a weighting criterion applied per grid cell. This fine resolution takes into account the smaller settlements in Europe that are not resolved at the 10 km grid resolution. The map of BaP is constructed using the rural and urban map layers that are created at the 1 km resolution and subsequently merged. The map of BaP is labelled as experimental (as recommended in Horálek et al., 2022b) to indicate that it does not yet meet the same accuracy standards as the regularly produced maps of other pollutants.

The maps of O₃ and NO_x vegetation-related indicators are constructed at a grid resolution of 2 km and applicable for rural areas only. They are based on rural background measurements; in the case of O₃, they serve as input to the EEA's indicator AIR004 (EEA, 2024b). Among the ozone vegetation-related indicators, maps of Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₆) indicators are also presented, following the conclusions of Colette et al. (2018). POD is the O₃ flux through the stomata of leaves above a specific threshold accumulated during a specified time; it is calculated based on methodology described in CLRTAP (2017a) according to Emberson et al. (2000) and Jarvis (1976).

⁽²⁾ PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm and 2.5 µm or less, respectively.

Maps of the POD for representative species of crops in Europe i.e. wheat, potato and tomato have been presented in the regular mapping reports since maps for 2018. Maps of the POD for representative selected trees i.e. beech and spruce are presented in this report for the second time, in agreement with conclusions of Vlasáková et al. (2023). The POD annual maps are calculated based on hourly ozone rural maps (created similarly to the annual ozone maps), hourly meteorological data and the soil hydraulic properties data.

Next to the annual indicator maps, tables showing the population exposure to PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃ and NO₂, and the exposure of vegetation to ozone in terms of AOT40 indicators are presented. The tables of population exposure are prepared using the concentration and population density maps in 1 km² grid resolution. For PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂, the population exposure in each grid cell is calculated separately for urban areas directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas, in order to better reflect the population exposed to traffic emissions. The tables of the vegetation exposure are prepared using the concentration maps in 2 km grid resolution and the Corine Land Cover 2018 dataset in 100 m resolution (EU, 2020).

All tables present exposure results for individual countries, for the EU-27, for the whole mapped area and for five large European regions. For the country grouping into the regions, see Annex 1 Map A1.1 and below: Northern Europe (N): Denmark (including Faroes), Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden; 2) Western Europe (W): Belgium, France (metropolitan) north of 45°, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands; Central Europe (C): Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Liechtenstein, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland; Southern Europe (S): Andorra, Cyprus, France (metropolitan) south of 45°, Greece, Italy, Malta, Monaco, Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira), San Marino, Spain (without Canarias); South-eastern Europe (SE): Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Kosovo under the UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia (considered both including and excluding Kosovo)⁽³⁾, Türkiye.

Chapters 2, 3, 4 and 5 present the concentration maps and exposure estimates for particulate matter, O₃, NO₂ and NO_x, and BaP, respectively. Chapter 4 presents only the concentration map for NO_x; concentrations above the critical level for the protection of vegetation occur in very limited areas and, as such, it is considered not to provide relevant information from the European scale perspective. Chapter 6 provides information of accumulated risks, showing in which areas population is exposed to concentrations above the legal standards for more than one pollutant. Finally, Chapter 7 summarizes the trends in exposure estimates in the period 2005-2022.

Annex 1 describes briefly the different methodological aspects. Annex 2 documents the input data applied in the 2022 mapping and exposure analysis. Annex 3 presents the technical details of the maps and their uncertainty analysis including the cross-validation results. Annex 4 presents the concentration maps including concentration values measured at the stations, in order to provide more complete information of the air quality in 2022 across Europe.

⁽³⁾ In the report, the status-neutral point of view on Kosovo under the UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99 is held.

2 Particulate matter

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets limit values for long-term and for short-term PM₁₀ concentrations and for long-term PM_{2.5} concentrations. The EU long-term annual PM₁₀ limit value is set at 40 µg/m³. The Air Quality Guideline level recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2005 (WHO, 2005) for the PM₁₀ annual average was 20 µg/m³. In September 2021, WHO introduced its new Air Quality Guidelines (WHO, 2021a). The current Air Quality Guideline level for the PM₁₀ annual average is set to 15 µg/m³. The EU short-term limit value indicates that the daily average PM₁₀ concentration should not exceed 50 µg/m³ during more than 35 days per year. It corresponds to the 90.4 percentile of daily PM₁₀ concentrations in one year. This daily limit value is the most frequently exceeded air quality PM limit value in Europe. The Air Quality Guideline levels recommended by the World Health Organization in 2005 (WHO, 2005) and in 2021 (WHO, 2021a) for short-term PM₁₀ concentrations indicates that the 99 percentile of the daily average PM₁₀ concentrations should not exceed 50 µg/m³ and 45 µg/m³, respectively (99 percentile means 3-4 exceedance days per year).

The EU annual limit value for the annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations (ALV) is set at 25 µg/m³. In EC (2008), there is also an indicative limit value (ILV) of 20 µg/m³ defined as Stage 2, in place since 2020. The Air Quality Guideline level recommended by the World Health Organization in 2005 (WHO, 2005) for the PM_{2.5} annual average was 10 µg/m³. The current Air Quality Guideline level as introduced by the WHO in September 2021 (WHO, 2021a) for the PM_{2.5} annual average is set to 5 µg/m³.

This chapter presents the 2022 situation in relation to both EU PM₁₀ limit values, i.e. the annual average and the 90.4 percentile of the daily averages, and the PM_{2.5} annual average. The 90.4 percentile of the daily averages is a more relevant PM₁₀ indicator in the context of the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) than the 36th highest daily mean, which was used up to 2013 maps (Horálek et al., 2017a).

The maps of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} are based on the improved mapping methodology developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2019). The map layers are created for the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas separately on a grid at 1 km resolution. Subsequently, the urban background and urban traffic map layers are merged together using the gridded GRIP road data (Meijer et al., 2018) into one urban map layer. This urban map layer is further combined with the rural map layer into the final PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5} map using a population density grid at 1 km resolution. For details, see Annex 1, Section A1.1. The supplementary data used are chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude, wind speed and land cover for rural areas, CTM output for urban background areas and CTM output and wind speed for urban traffic areas (Annex 3, Sections A3.1 and A3.2). For all PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} indicators, the final combined map is presented in the 1 km grid resolution. Be it noted that this final map is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas (which are smoothed in this 1 km spatial resolution).

The current number of PM_{2.5} measurement stations is still somewhat limited and its spatial distribution is irregular over Europe. Therefore, in this paper the mapping of the health-related indicator PM_{2.5} annual average is based on a mapping methodology developed in Denby et al. (2011). This methodology derives additional pseudo PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations from PM₁₀ annual mean measurement concentrations. As such, it increases the number and spatial coverage of PM_{2.5} 'data points' and these data are used to derive a European wide map of annual mean PM_{2.5}. Pseudo PM_{2.5} stations data are estimated using PM₁₀ measurement data, surface solar radiation, latitude and longitude.

The population exposure tables are calculated based on the concentration maps, according to the methodology described in Horálek et al. (2019), i.e. they are calculated separately for urban areas directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas, in order to better reflect the population exposed to traffic. For details, see Annex 1, Equation A1.6.

Annex 3, Sections A3.1 and A3.2 provide details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} maps, as well as the uncertainty analysis of these maps.

2.1 PM₁₀ annual average

Concentration map

Map 2.1 presents the final combined concentration map for the 2022 PM₁₀ annual average. Red and purple areas indicate concentrations above the limit value (LV) of 40 µg/m³.

The stations are not presented in the map, in order to better visualise the urban areas. However, concentration values from the station measurements used in the kriging interpolation methodology (Annex 3, Section A3.1) are considered to provide relevant information to the concentration map. In Map A4.1 of Annex 4 these point values are presented on top of Map 2.1. This illustrates the smoothing effect that the interpolation method can have on the gridded concentration fields.

Map 2.1 shows annual mean concentrations above the LV in urban areas of south-eastern Europe states (Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia and Serbia), similarly to previous years. A larger, more continuous area with concentrations above LV occurs in the south-eastern and eastern parts of Türkiye. In general, the south-eastern, the south and the central parts of Europe appear with higher concentrations and population-weighted concentrations than the western and the northern parts.

Map 2.1 Concentration map of PM₁₀ annual average, 2022

Map 2.2 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for annual average for PM₁₀. Orange to red areas show an increase of PM₁₀ concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

At the annual average PM₁₀ difference map the highest increases are observed in Türkiye, parts of southern and south-eastern Europe with the highest increases in Cyprus, Portugal, Spain, south of France and parts of Italy (Sardinia and south of Italy), part of central Europe on the border between Switzerland and Italy and part of western Europe (Luxembourg, Ireland). On the other hand, there are decreases in the most of remaining countries, mainly central Europe and parts of some countries in south-eastern Europe.

Map 2.2 Difference in concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for PM₁₀ annual average

Be it noted that besides the actual changes in the concentrations, the variability of the linear regression model and variogram parameters, changes in the measurement network and changes in the dispersion model may cause minor differences in the concentration levels estimated.

The uncertainty of the concentration map can be expressed in relative terms of the absolute Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) uncertainty related to the mean air pollution indicator value for all stations (see Annex 1, Section A1.4). This relative mean uncertainty (RRMSE) of the final combined map of PM₁₀ annual average is 26 % for rural areas and 27 % for urban background areas including Turkish stations (i.e. quite similar to the last years), and respectively 20 % for rural areas and 19 % for urban background areas without Turkish stations (Annex 3, Section A3.1). This means quite good mapping uncertainty, compared to the data quality objective for models of PM₁₀ annual average (i.e. 50 %) as set in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008). The main reason for presenting the results also without Turkish stations is to enable the comparison with previous years.

Population exposure

Figure 2.1 gives the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to PM₁₀ concentrations. More detailed Table 2.1 also presents the 2022 population-weighted concentration and the difference in the population-weighted concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for individual countries, for five European regions, for EU-27, and for the total mapped area according to Equation A1.7.

Table 2.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, PM₁₀ annual average, 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	PM ₁₀ – annual average, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 15	15-20	20-30	30-40	40-50	> 50	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 794	6.3	13.3	73.5	6.9			23.8	29.0	-5.2
Andorra	AD	79	27.0	73.0					15.6	19.9	-4.3
Austria	AT	8 979	42.9	53.5	3.6				15.0	16.4	-1.4
Belgium	BE	11 618	7.1	63.8	29.1				18.6	18.8	-0.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271	4.8	9.6	33.2	34.6	17.5	0.2	30.6	32.1	-1.5
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	3.3	20.0	61.2	15.6			24.0	28.0	-4.0
Croatia	HR	3 862	12.2	34.0	52.6	1.2			20.5	22.7	-2.2
Cyprus	CY	1 288		0.1	13.8	29.5	56.5		38.0	32.0	6.0
Czechia	CZ	10 517	13.7	67.1	19.2				18.2	20.6	-2.4
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926	93.4	6.6					13.8	15.1	-1.4
Estonia	EE	1 332	97.1	2.9					10.9	11.3	-0.4
Finland	FI	5 548	99.8	0.2					8.4	9.2	-0.8
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647	29.4	62.4	8.2				16.6	16.2	0.4
Germany	DE	83 237	62.3	37.3	0.5				14.7	15.7	-1.0
Greece	GR	10 460	2.6	12.4	62.2	21.7	1.1		26.7	28.1	-1.4
Hungary	HU	9 689	1.2	31.9	67.0				21.0	23.4	-2.4
Iceland	IS	376	100.0						8.5	9.7	-1.2
Ireland	IE	5 060	93.1	6.9					12.0	11.8	0.2
Italy	IT	59 030	2.2	16.7	62.9	18.2			24.3	24.2	0.1
Latvia	LV	1 876	46.5	39.2	14.3				15.4	17.3	-1.8
Liechtenstein	LI	39	99.4	0.6					12.0	12.4	-0.3
Lithuania	LT	2 806	29.6	47.2	23.2				17.5	18.7	-1.2
Luxembourg	LU	645	27.9	72.1					15.7	15.5	0.2
Malta	MT	521		0.0	97.6	2.3			26.3	27.5	-1.2
Monaco	MC	37		80.5	19.5				20.3	20.2	0.1
Montenegro	ME	618	5.7	26.2	55.5	12.6			24.7	26.2	-1.6
Netherlands	NL	17 591	8.5	91.1	0.4				17.1	17.7	-0.6
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	2.1	4.8	36.2	41.5	15.4		31.8	37.2	-5.5
Norway	NO	5 425	94.6	5.4					9.9	10.0	-0.1
Poland	PL	37 654	2.1	23.5	68.7	5.6			23.0	26.4	-3.4
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864	4.7	43.5	51.8				20.2	17.8	2.4
Romania	RO	19 042	5.6	37.9	56.3	0.2			21.0	23.3	-2.2
San Marino	SM	34	0.6	22.4	77.0				20.7	21.1	-0.4
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571	1.4	7.9	57.1	33.3	0.2		27.3	32.7	-5.4
Slovakia	SK	5 435	4.0	57.4	38.6				19.4	22.3	-2.9
Slovenia	SI	2 107	17.1	56.7	26.1				18.2	19.9	-1.7
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	5.2	31.6	61.5	1.7			21.6	19.7	1.8
Sweden	SE	10 452	95.1	4.7	0.2				10.1	10.8	-0.7
Switzerland	CH	8 739	70.4	28.2	1.4				14.2	13.7	0.5
Türkiye	TR	84 680	0.2	2.8	8.7	33.0	30.9	24.5	43.4	34.2	9.2
Total		558 706	22.7	31.1	28.8	9.0	4.8	3.6	22.7	22.5	0.1
			53.8				8.4				
EU-27		442 153	25.7	37.6	32.5	4.0	0.2		19.0	19.7	-0.7
			63.3				0.2				
Northern Europe		33 742	87.2	9.9	2.9				11.3	12.3	-1.0
Western Europe		85 476	27.0	65.6	7.4				16.6	16.6	-0.1
Central Europe		166 396	38.7	37.0	23.1	1.3			17.4	19.2	-1.8
Southern Europe		141 577	5.4	27.4	56.5	10.2	0.5		22.7	21.8	0.9
South-Eastern Europe		10 452	1.9	10.9	26.0	25.6	20.1	15.4	36.1	34.4	1.8
Kosovo	KS	1 774	1.4	10.7	87.6	0.4			23.3	30.8	-7.5
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797	1.4	7.2	49.3	41.8	0.3		28.3	33.1	-4.8

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and five-year mean 2017-2021.

It is estimated that 77 % and 46 % of population of the considered mapped area has been exposed to annual average concentrations above the current (2021) and the 2005 WHO Air Quality Guideline levels of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (WHO, 2021a) and 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (WHO, 2005), respectively. The same is true for 74 % and 37 % of the EU-27 population.

Approximately 8 % of population of the considered mapped area has been exposed to concentrations above the EU annual limit value (ALV) of 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$; the same is the case for around 0.2 % of the EU-27 population.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in 35 out of 41 mapped countries. A limited fraction of the population (up to 18 %) has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in Serbia, Greece, North Macedonia, and Bosnia and Herzegovina (in ascending order). More than 50 % of the population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in Türkiye and Cyprus. However, as the current mapping methodology tends to underestimate high values (see Annex 3, Section A3.1), the percentage of population exposed to concentrations above the ALV will most likely be underestimated. Additional population exposure above the ALV could therefore be expected in countries like Italy, Greece, Cyprus, Türkiye, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia where a relatively large fraction (ca. 20-40 %) of the population lives in areas with concentration levels 30-40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

The population-weighted concentration of the annual average for 2022 for the considered European population (including Türkiye) is estimated to be about 23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and about 19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the EU-27 only. The value for considered European population and EU-27 increased by about 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and decreased about 0.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively, compared to the previous five-year mean 2017-2021,. When assessing the absolute change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Kosovo (7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), the highest increase was estimated in Türkiye (9.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Figure 2.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different PM₁₀ annual averages ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at country level, 2022

Figure 2.2 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest population frequency can be seen for classes between 13 and 23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. One can see a quite continuous strong decline of population frequency for classes between 23 and 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and a mild decline for classes beyond 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 2.2 Population exposure frequency distribution, PM₁₀ annual average, 2022. The 2021 WHO AQG level (15 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2005 WHO AQG level (20 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.23 % of population lived in areas with PM₁₀ annual average concentrations between 75 and 309 µg/m³.

Figure 2.3 shows for individual countries the PM₁₀ annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2022. It can be seen that the countries with the highest values of PM₁₀ annual average are located in the central and south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 2.3 PM₁₀ annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2022. The 2021 WHO AQG level (15 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2005 WHO AQG level (20 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50 % in the case of the black marker, 25 % and 75 % in the cases of the box's edges, 2 % and 98 % in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

2.2 PM₁₀ – 90.4 percentile of daily means

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) describes the PM₁₀ daily limit value (DLV) as “a daily average of 50 µg/m³ not to be exceeded more than 35 times a calendar year”. This requirement can be evaluated by the indicator 36th highest daily mean, which is in principle equivalent to the indicator 90.4 percentile of daily mean. However, for measurement data these two indicators are equivalent

only if no data is missing, which is in general not the case. As shown in de Leeuw (2012), the additional uncertainty related to incomplete time series is substantially smaller when using percentile values instead of the x-th highest value. Furthermore, the Air Quality Directive requires the use of the 90.4 percentile when random measurements are used to assess the requirements of the PM₁₀ DLV. As in the previous reports since the maps for 2014 (Horálek et al., 2017a), the PM₁₀ daily means are expressed as the 90.4 percentile instead of the formerly used 36th highest daily mean.

Concentration map

Map 2.3 presents the final combined map, where red and purple marked areas indicate values of the 90.4 percentile of daily means above 50 µg/m³ (i.e. concentrations above the DLV of 50 µg/m³ on more than 35 measurement days). The similar mapping procedure as in the case of the annual average is used. The mapping details and the uncertainty analysis are presented in Annex 3. Large areas with concentrations above the DLV are observed in northern Italy (i.e. the Po Valley), in the industrial region Krakow – Katowice (Poland) – Ostrava (Czechia) and in southern, south-eastern and eastern parts of Türkiye. Urban and surrounding areas with concentrations above the DLV are observed in Balkan countries, Cyprus, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Spain and Türkiye, as in previous years.

In general, the south-eastern, the south and the central parts of Europe appear with higher concentrations and population-weighted concentrations than the western and the northern parts.

The relative mean uncertainty (relative RMSE) of the final combined map of the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily means is 30 % for both rural and urban background areas including Turkish stations. The mean uncertainty for the map without Türkiye is 20 % for both rural areas and 22 % for urban background areas (Annex 3, Section A3.1). Thus, the mapping uncertainty of this is at the similar level as in the case of the PM₁₀ annual average.

Map 2.3 Concentration map of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2022

Map 2.4 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for the 90.4 percentile of daily means for PM₁₀. Orange to red areas show an increase of PM₁₀ concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

Map 2.4 Difference in concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for **PM₁₀ 90.4 percentile**

The situation is similar to that of the annual average value of PM₁₀. The highest increases are observed in large parts of Türkiye and in parts of southern Europe (Italy, France, Spain, and Portugal). On the other hand, there are decreases in the remaining countries, mainly central Europe (Poland, Czechia, Slovakia, and Hungary), parts of some countries in south-eastern and southern Europe (Serbia, Romania and Bulgaria) and parts of Spain and France.

Population exposure

Figure 2.4 gives the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means. More detailed Table 2.2 also presents the 2022 population-weighted concentration and the difference in the population-weighted concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for individual countries, for five European regions, for EU-27, and for the total mapped area according to Equation A1.7.

In 2022 about 19 % of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and 6 % of the EU-27 population are estimated to live in areas with PM₁₀ concentrations above the EU limit value of 50 µg/m³.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the DLV in 23 out of 41 mapped countries. A limited fraction of the population (up to 19 %) has been exposed to concentrations above the DLV in Slovakia, Czechia, Romania, Spain, Hungary, Croatia, Albania, Poland, Greece, Kosovo and Bulgaria (in ascending order). More than 20 % but less than 50 % of the population has been exposed to concentrations above the DLV in Italy, Montenegro and Serbia. More than half of the population has been estimated to be exposed to concentrations above the DLV in Bosnia and Herzegovina (64 %), North Macedonia (72 %), Cyprus (77 %), and Türkiye (86 %).

Table 2.2 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	PM ₁₀ - perc90.4, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 20	20-30	30-40	40-50	50-75	> 75	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 794	0.0	17.1	28.2	44.2	10.4		42.3	52.1	-9.8
Andorra	AD	79	9.6	18.6	71.8				29.2	35.5	-6.2
Austria	AT	8 979	19.8	72.8	7.4				25.6	28.8	-3.1
Belgium	BE	11 618	2.4	25.6	72.0	0.1			31.8	32.8	-1.0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271	0.0	6.2	13.0	16.5	45.3	18.9	59.4	64.2	-4.9
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	0.2	17.6	40.1	23.2	18.9		40.4	49.5	-9.1
Croatia	HR	3 862	1.6	26.5	34.0	34.7	3.2		37.6	42.8	-5.3
Cyprus	CY	1 288		0.0	6.1	17.2	76.7		61.2	51.7	9.6
Czechia	CZ	10 517	2.6	36.1	54.5	6.7	0.0		31.9	37.2	-5.3
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926	14.0	86.0					22.4	25.7	-3.3
Estonia	EE	1 332	50.9	49.1					20.1	20.1	0.0
Finland	FI	5 548	94.1	5.9					15.8	16.9	-1.1
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647	4.8	69.9	25.3				28.0	27.1	0.9
Germany	DE	83 237	9.6	90.1	0.3				24.5	26.6	-2.1
Greece	GR	10 460	0.0	9.8	27.9	44.3	17.4	0.6	44.3	47.3	-3.0
Hungary	HU	9 689	0.3	11.1	69.3	16.8	2.6		36.9	42.1	-5.2
Iceland	IS	376	99.0	1.0					15.4	17.6	-2.2
Ireland	IE	5 060	53.9	45.2	1.0				20.7	20.5	0.2
Italy	IT	59 030	0.6	10.9	44.4	20.2	23.9		42.3	43.1	-0.8
Latvia	LV	1 876	19.2	42.5	38.3				27.4	30.1	-2.7
Liechtenstein	LI	39	42.4	57.6					21.5	22.2	-0.6
Lithuania	LT	2 806	4.4	49.1	46.4				29.6	32.4	-2.8
Luxembourg	LU	645	15.8	84.2					25.7	25.8	-0.1
Malta	MT	521		7.9	5.3	86.8			41.9	42.4	-0.5
Monaco	MC	37		19.5	80.5				32.3	31.0	1.3
Montenegro	ME	618	0.0	10.5	29.7	12.2	44.1	3.5	48.7	50.9	-2.1
Netherlands	NL	17 591	5.7	81.1	13.2				27.9	29.2	-1.2
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	0.0	4.4	7.7	15.8	53.6	18.4	60.3	74.0	-13.7
Norway	NO	5 425	65.6	33.6	0.7				18.6	18.4	0.2
Poland	PL	37 654	0.2	11.8	41.4	33.4	13.2		40.3	47.9	-7.5
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864	1.1	45.3	43.6	10.0			32.1	29.8	2.3
Romania	RO	19 042	1.2	28.3	47.0	22.8	0.7		35.1	39.9	-4.9
San Marino	SM	34		12.5	87.5				36.4	37.9	-1.5
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571	0.0	3.7	19.6	33.3	39.2	4.1	50.1	61.7	-11.6
Slovakia	SK	5 435	0.6	20.3	70.3	8.8	0.0		33.7	40.6	-6.9
Slovenia	SI	2 107	2.1	40.3	46.2	11.3			32.5	35.8	-3.2
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	2.4	27.2	55.1	14.1	1.3		34.6	32.3	2.3
Sweden	SE	10 452	75.3	24.7					17.8	19.4	-1.7
Switzerland	CH	8 739	14.2	77.1	8.1	0.6			26.2	24.2	2.0
Türkiye	TR	84 680	0.0	1.2	5.0	7.8	53.0	33.0	74.6	69.3	5.3
Total		558 706	7.0	37.9	25.8	10.8	13.4	5.1	38.7	39.4	-0.6
			44.8				18.6				
EU-27		442 153	7.6	45.2	30.6	10.9	5.6	0.0	32.1	34.0	-1.9
			52.8				5.6				
Northern Europe		33 742	97.1	2.9					20.0	21.9	-1.9
Western Europe		85 476	92.6	7.4					27.9	28.1	-0.2
Central Europe		166 396	75.6	23.1	1.3				29.9	33.8	-3.9
Southern Europe		141 577	32.8	56.5	10.2	0.5			38.1	37.3	0.7
South-Eastern Europe		10 452	12.8	26.0	25.6	20.1	14.1	1.3	62.6	61.2	1.3
Kosovo	KS	1 774	0.0	2.1	21.5	57.8	18.5		44.2	61.1	-16.8
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797	0.0	4.1	19.1	27.1	44.6	5.2	51.6	61.9	-10.3

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and five-year mean 2017-2021.

The European-wide population-weighted concentration of the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily means is estimated for 2022 at about 39 µg/m³ for the total mapped area and 32 µg/m³ for the EU-27. The population-weighted concentration of this PM₁₀ indicator decreased by about 0.6 µg/m³ for the considered European population and by about 2 µg/m³ for EU-27 compared to the previous five-year mean 2017-2021. When assessing the absolute change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Kosovo (17 µg/m³), the highest increase was estimated in Cyprus (10 µg/m³).

Figure 2.4 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2022

Figure 2.5 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 2 µg/m³. One can see the highest population frequency for classes between 22 and 40 µg/m³, then a quite strong decline of population frequency for classes between 40 and 46 µg/m³ and continuous mild decline of population frequency for classes between 50 and 120 µg/m³.

Figure 2.5 Population exposure frequency distribution, PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means, 2022. The EU daily limit value (50 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.19 % of population lived in areas with values of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means between 135 and 490 µg/m³.

Figure 2.6 shows for individual countries the P90.4 of the PM₁₀ daily concentrations to which the population was exposed in 2022. It can be seen that the countries with the highest values of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means are located mainly in south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 2.6 PM₁₀ expressed as indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means to which the population was exposed in 2022, per country. The EU daily limit value (50 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50 % in the case of the black marker, 25 % and 75 % in the cases of the box's edges, 2 % and 98 % in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

As in previous years, the daily limit value was more widely exceeded than the annual limit value in 2022.

2.3 PM_{2.5} annual average

Concentration map

Map 2.5 presents the final combined map for the 2022 PM_{2.5} annual average. The dark red areas show concentrations above the ALV of 25 µg/m³. Red areas show concentrations above the indicative LV of 20 µg/m³ defined as Stage 2 (ILV).

Due to the lack of enough rural PM_{2.5} stations in Türkiye, no proper interpolation results could be estimated for this country in a rural map. Therefore, the estimated PM_{2.5} values for Türkiye are not presented in the final map.

According to Map 2.5, the areas with the highest PM_{2.5} concentrations appear to be the Po Valley in northern Italy, in the Krakow – Katowice (Poland) – Ostrava (Czechia) industrial region and areas of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia and North Macedonia. Concentrations above the ALV appear also around the city of Warsaw. Different other cities and areas in south-eastern and central Europe also show elevated PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations. Like in the case of PM₁₀, the central and the south and south-eastern parts of Europe show higher concentrations than the western and the northern parts.

Similarly to the PM₁₀, the final map in 1 km resolution is representative for the rural and the urban background areas, but not for the urban traffic areas (which are smoothed in the 1 km resolution).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.3 of Annex 4.

Map 2.5 Concentration map of PM_{2.5} annual average, 2022

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 map of PM_{2.5} annual average is 28 % for rural and 25 % for urban background areas and it is determined exclusively on the actual PM_{2.5} measurement data points, i.e. not on the pseudo stations (Annex 3, Section A3.2). Similarly as in the case of PM₁₀, this uncertainty is satisfactory, compared to the data quality objective for models of PM_{2.5} annual average (i.e. 50 %) as set in the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

Map 2.6 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for annual average for PM_{2.5}. Orange to red areas show an increase of PM_{2.5} concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

At the annual average PM_{2.5} difference map the highest increases are in parts of southern Europe with the highest increases in Spain, Portugal, France and in the north of Italy and parts of northern Europe (Norway and Sweden). On the other hand, there are decreases in most of the remaining countries, mainly central Europe (especially in Poland, Hungary, Slovakia), parts of some countries in south-eastern and southern Europe (Serbia, Romania, Bulgaria, Greece and Italy).

Map 2.6 **Difference in concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for PM_{2.5} annual average**

Population exposure

Table 2.3 and Figure 2.7 give the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to PM_{2.5} concentrations calculated on a grid of 1 km resolution. Table 2.3 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapping area.

About 97 % and 56 % of the considered European population (excluding Türkiye), has been exposed to annual average concentrations above the current 2021 and the 2005 WHO Air Quality Guideline levels of 5 µg/m³ (WHO, 2021a) and 10 µg/m³ (WHO, 2005), respectively. The same is true for 98 % and 56 % of the EU-27 population.

The total considered and EU-27 population exposed to concentrations above the EU annual limit value (ALV) of 25 µg/m³ has been 0.7 % and 0.2 %, respectively.

Table 2.3 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, PM_{2.5} annual average 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	PM _{2.5} – annual average, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 5	5-10	10-15	15-20	20-25	> 25	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 794	0.0	6.5	32.1	50.6	10.9		15.9	18.8	-3.0
Andorra	AD	79	17.3	82.7					7.2	9.8	-2.5
Austria	AT	8 979	0.9	39.5	57.4	2.2			10.1	11.4	-1.3
Belgium	BE	11 618	0.0	39.1	60.9				10.1	11.2	-1.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271	0.0	3.5	12.9	22.1	26.6	34.9	22.1	23.7	-1.5
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	0.0	3.6	49.3	44.7	2.4		15.1	18.7	-3.6
Croatia	HR	3 862	0.0	12.1	36.8	48.3	2.7		14.6	16.0	-1.4
Cyprus	CY	1 288		1.6	69.0	21.4	8.1		14.7	14.6	0.1
Czechia	CZ	10 517		11.0	74.8	12.7	1.6		13.1	15.1	-2.0
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926	1.2	98.8					7.7	8.8	-1.1
Estonia	EE	1 332	29.0	71.0					5.6	5.8	-0.3
Finland	FI	5 548	71.8	28.2					4.4	4.9	-0.5
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647	0.4	62.1	37.5				9.5	9.7	-0.2
Germany	DE	83 237	0.0	80.2	19.7				9.2	10.5	-1.3
Greece	GR	10 460	0.0	7.5	30.2	60.9	1.3		15.7	18.9	-3.2
Hungary	HU	9 689		0.3	77.2	22.5			13.8	16.1	-2.3
Iceland	IS	376	100.0						3.6	4.5	-0.9
Ireland	IE	5 060	4.0	92.7	3.3				7.1	7.1	0.0
Italy	IT	59 030	0.1	11.8	46.6	21.5	19.8	0.3	15.0	15.1	-0.1
Latvia	LV	1 876	0.9	63.6	35.5				8.8	10.3	-1.5
Liechtenstein	LI	39	0.6	99.4					8.4	8.5	-0.1
Lithuania	LT	2 806		49.6	50.4				9.9	11.3	-1.4
Luxembourg	LU	645		100.0					7.4	8.6	-1.2
Malta	MT	521		11.4	88.6				10.6	11.6	-1.0
Monaco	MC	37			100.0				10.2	11.7	-1.5
Montenegro	ME	618	0.0	5.3	39.2	45.0	10.4		15.9	18.4	-2.5
Netherlands	NL	17 591		87.2	12.8				9.3	10.6	-1.2
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	0.0	2.4	8.5	30.6	24.3	34.3	22.2	26.1	-3.9
Norway	NO	5 425	44.0	56.0					5.4	5.5	-0.1
Poland	PL	37 654		1.8	38.4	47.5	10.8	1.5	16.1	19.0	-2.8
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864	0.4	64.9	34.7				9.3	8.3	1.0
Romania	RO	19 042	0.0	3.6	57.1	39.2	0.2		14.4	16.0	-1.7
San Marino	SM	34		5.2	94.8				13.9	13.0	0.9
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571		1.0	20.2	41.1	28.9	8.9	18.7	23.4	-4.7
Slovakia	SK	5 435	0.0	1.3	73.1	25.6			13.9	16.3	-2.4
Slovenia	SI	2 107	0.0	10.8	61.4	27.0	0.9		13.5	14.0	-0.4
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	0.2	34.5	61.6	3.7			10.9	10.4	0.5
Sweden	SE	10 452	53.8	46.2					5.3	5.4	-0.1
Switzerland	CH	8 739	2.4	91.5	5.4	0.6			8.6	9.0	-0.4
Total (without Türkiye)		474 026	2.9	41.0	37.2	13.7	4.5	0.7	11.7	12.8	-1.1
			43.9				5.2				
EU-27		442 153	2.4	41.5	39.0	13.2	3.8	0.2	11.5	12.5	-1.0
			43.8				4.0				
Northern Europe		33 742	38.1	55.5	6.4				6.1	6.8	-0.7
Western Europe		85 476	0.4	65.7	33.9				9.4	10.1	-0.7
Central Europe		166 396	0.2	48.0	34.4	14.4	2.6	0.3	11.6	13.4	-1.8
Southern Europe		141 577	0.2	27.7	48.3	15.1	8.6	0.1	12.8	12.8	0.0
South-Eastern Europe without Türkiye		46 834	0.0	4.0	40.6	40.2	9.6	5.6	16.3	18.9	-2.6
Kosovo	KS	1 774		1.1	21.1	76.6	1.1	0.2	16.6	22.6	-6.0
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797		0.9	20.0	32.0	36.0	11.1	19.2	23.7	-4.4

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and five-year mean 2017-2021.

No population in 34 out of 40 countries has been exposed to concentrations above the limit value. In Kosovo, Italy and Poland (in ascending order) less than 2 % of population has been exposed to concentrations above the limit value. In Serbia, North Macedonia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, between cc. 10 % and 35 % of the population have been exposed above this limit value.

Concentrations above the indicative limit value (ILV) of 20 µg/m³ were found in areas with 5 % of the considered European population and with 4 % of the EU-27 population. No population has been exposed to concentrations above the ILV in 25 countries. In Romania, Slovenia, Kosovo, Greece, Czechia, Bulgaria, Croatia, and Cyprus (in ascending order) between 0.2 and 8 % of the population is exposed to concentrations above the ILV. In Montenegro, Albania, Poland, Italy, and Serbia, 10-47 % of the population suffers from exposures above this ILV; in North Macedonia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, more than 58 % of the population have been exposed above this ILV.

Since PM_{2.5} is one of the most relevant pollutants linked to health problems and premature mortality (EEA, 2019) it should be mentioned that at least some part of the population, with the exception of Iceland, was exposed to PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations above the 2021 WHO AQG level in each country (a minimum of 28 % in Finland). More than 90 % of the population has been exposed to concentrations above the 2021 WHO AQG level in 34 countries.

As the current mapping methodology tends to underestimate high values (Annex 3, Section A3.2), the percentages and/or the number of countries with population exposed to concentrations above both the current ALV and the indicative ILV will most likely be higher.

The population-weighted concentration of the PM_{2.5} annual means has been estimated for 2022 at about 12 µg/m³ for both European population (excluding Türkiye) and for the EU-27, which means a decrease about 1 µg/m³ compared to five-year mean for both characteristics. When assessing the absolute change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Kosovo (6 µg/m³), the highest increase was estimated in Portugal (1 µg/m³).

Figure 2.7 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of PM_{2.5} annual average (µg/m³), 2022

Figure 2.8 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 0.5 µg/m³. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 7 and 12 µg/m³.

Figure 2.8 Population exposure frequency distribution, PM_{2.5} annual average, 2022. The 2021 WHO AQG level (5 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the 2005 WHO AQG level (10 µg/m³) is marked by the yellow line, the EU annual indicative limit value (20 µg/m³) is marked by the orange line and the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³) is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.17 % of population lived in areas with PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations between 30 and 36 µg/m³.

The boxplot showing for individual countries the PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2022 is presented in Summary, Figure S.1.

3 Ozone

For ozone, four health-related indicators, i.e. 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means (see below), peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and SOMO10, and seven vegetation-related indicators, i.e. AOT40 for vegetation, AOT40 for forests, POD₆ for crops (wheat, potato and tomato) and POD₁ for trees (beech and spruce) are considered. For the definition of the SOMO35, SOMO10 and AOT40 and POD indicators, see following sections and Annexes 1 and 2.

The separate rural and urban background health-related indicator map layers are calculated at a resolution of 10 km. Subsequently, the final health-related indicator maps are created by combining rural and urban areas based on the 1 km resolution population density map, following the procedure as described in Annex 1, Section A1.1. The supplementary data used are chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude and surface solar radiation for rural areas and CTM output, wind speed and surface solar radiation for urban areas (Annex 3). The final concentration maps are presented on the 1 km grid resolution. The population exposure tables are calculated on the basis of these health-related indicator maps.

The vegetation-related indicator maps are created for rural areas only, as urban areas are considered not to represent areas covered by vegetation (although the vegetation located in the outskirts of agglomerations might be omitted by this approach). These maps are calculated from observations at rural background stations and are representative for rural areas only. The supplementary data used are CTM output, altitude and surface solar radiation. These supplementary data sources are the same as those used for the human health related ozone indicators in the rural areas. The maps have a resolution of 2 km. This resolution serves the needs of the EEA's AIR004 indicator on ecosystem exposure to ozone (EEA, 2024b).

Annex 3, Section A3.3 provides details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the maps of the ozone indicators, as well as the uncertainty analysis of the maps.

3.1 Ozone – 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) describes the O₃ target value (TV) for the protection of human health as “a maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 25 times a calendar year, averaged over three years”. On an annual basis, what we call the target value threshold ⁽⁴⁾, can be evaluated by the indicator 26th highest maximum daily 8-hour mean, which is in principle equivalent to the indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means. However, for measurement data these two indicators are equivalent only if no data is missing, which is in general not the case. As shown in de Leeuw (2012), the additional uncertainty related to incomplete time series is substantially smaller when using percentile values instead of the x-th highest value. As in the previous reports since 2014 maps, this ozone indicator is expressed as the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means instead of the formerly used 26th highest maximum daily 8-hour mean.

Concentration map

Map 3.1 presents the final combined map for 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means. In the map, the red and dark red areas show values of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means above 120 µg/m³ in 2022, i.e. above the TV threshold of 120 µg/m³ on more than 25 days in 2022. Note that in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) the TV is actually defined as 120 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 25 days per calendar year averaged over three years. Here only 2022 data are presented, and no three-year average has been calculated.

⁽⁴⁾ A maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 25 times a calendar year.

The map shows that percentile values above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ occur in several areas of Europe in 2022. Those values are particularly evident in large areas of Türkiye and northern Italy. To a lesser extent, values above 120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ occurred in Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Germany, Switzerland, Austria, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland, Hungary and all the Balkan countries. In general, the southern, the south-eastern and central parts of Europe show higher ozone concentrations than the northern parts, which is caused mainly by higher solar radiation and temperature in these areas. Nevertheless, concentrations above the TV threshold can occur even in northern Europe during warm year as it was presented for 2018 (Horálek et al., 2021).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.4 of Annex 4.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 map of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-h ozone means is about 8 % for rural and 10 % for urban areas (Annex 3, Section A3.2). The low uncertainty values are influenced by the character of this ozone indicator. Note that the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets no modelling uncertainty for ozone annual indicators.

Map 3.1 Concentration map of ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022

Map 3.2 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maxima for O_3 . Orange to red areas show an increase of O_3 concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

In 2022, increases in the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maxima for O_3 were observed in nearly the entire mapped area; although a slight increase was only noted in parts of northern Europe. The highest increase (even more than 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was observed in parts of southern and south-eastern European countries, namely Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Romania, Greece, and Türkiye. Decreases in the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maxima for O_3 were observed in an area extending into Poland and the Baltic states, as well as in several discontinuous regions of southern and south-eastern Europe.

Map 3.2 Difference in concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maxima

Population exposure

Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1 give, for the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes. Table 3.1 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area.

In 2022, it has been estimated that 17 % of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and around 17 % of the EU-27 population lived in areas where the ozone concentration was above the health-related target value threshold of 120 µg/m³.

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV threshold in 10 countries. In Romania, Luxembourg, Montenegro, Belgium, North Macedonia, Albania, Bulgaria, Kosovo, Malta, Poland, San Marino, Liechtenstein, Andorra, Spain and Portugal (in ascending order) up to 10 % of population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV threshold. In Slovakia, Cyprus, Austria, Türkiye, Czechia, Greece, Germany, France, Croatia, Hungary, Serbia, Italy, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, this was the case for between 11 % and 50 % of the population. More than half of population has been exposed to concentrations above the TV threshold in Slovenia, Switzerland and Monaco.

As the current mapping methodology tends to underestimate high values due to interpolation smoothing (Annex 3, Section A3.3), the percentage of population exposed to values above the TV threshold is most likely somewhat underestimated; additional population exposure above the TV threshold might be expected in some other countries: Albania, France, Hungary, Croatia, Germany, Belgium, Czechia, Austria, Liechtenstein and San Marino. The reason is that in these countries the estimated percentage population exposed to the concentrations between 110 µg/m³ and 120 µg/m³ is considerable (more than 50 %).

**Table 3.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator
93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022**

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	Ozone — perc93.2, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 90	90-100	100-110	110-120	120-140	> 140	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 794		8.0	35.0	56.9	0.2		108.6	111.5	-2.9
Andorra	AD	79	67.0	7.7	10.3	11.9	3.0		94.3	105.6	-11.3
Austria	AT	8 979		0.1	7.3	80.6	12.0	0.0	116.6	116.8	-0.2
Belgium	BE	11 618		1.4	19.6	78.9	0.1		111.8	108.8	3.0
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271			11.4	38.9	48.7	1.0	119.7	113.8	5.9
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	35.1	39.5	18.3	6.7	0.4	0.0	93.9	98.1	-4.2
Croatia	HR	3 862			4.2	67.7	28.1	0.0	117.4	114.9	2.5
Cyprus	CY	1 288	0.1	35.8	27.4	25.6	11.2		105.8	109.6	-3.7
Czechia	CZ	10 517			4.0	79.6	16.4		116.8	115.2	1.7
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926	19.5	72.6	7.8	0.0			94.1	96.8	-2.7
Estonia	EE	1 332	64.0	36.0					89.4	92.4	-3.0
Finland	FI	5 548	79.8	20.2					88.5	90.2	-1.8
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647	0.1	2.6	19.5	57.7	20.1	0.0	114.2	110.3	3.9
Germany	DE	83 237		1.6	10.8	68.2	19.4		115.6	113.0	2.6
Greece	GR	10 460	3.0	8.6	25.4	46.7	16.3	0.0	111.8	112.1	-0.3
Hungary	HU	9 689			8.8	58.8	32.4		117.4	111.6	5.7
Iceland	IS	376	76.0	24.0	0.0				88.9	87.0	1.9
Ireland	IE	5 060	35.6	64.4	0.0				91.0	90.7	0.2
Italy	IT	59 030	0.4	2.9	23.8	24.0	24.9	24.1	124.0	122.8	1.2
Latvia	LV	1 876	7.4	89.1	3.6				92.3	93.0	-0.7
Liechtenstein	LI	39				97.1	2.9		119.0	120.3	-1.3
Lithuania	LT	2 806	3.2	96.8	0.0				93.2	96.5	-3.3
Luxembourg	LU	645			66.3	33.7	0.0		110.3	110.0	0.2
Malta	MT	521			72.1	26.5	1.4		109.0	105.6	3.4
Monaco	MC	37					100.0		126.1	121.1	5.1
Montenegro	ME	618		11.9	77.7	10.4	0.0		105.4	110.1	-4.7
Netherlands	NL	17 591		12.8	62.5	24.6			106.0	104.2	1.8
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	2.9	22.1	68.4	6.7	0.1		104.0	102.0	2.1
Norway	NO	5 425	40.1	59.2	0.6	0.0			90.7	93.3	-2.6
Poland	PL	37 654		11.1	47.0	40.4	1.4		108.6	108.3	0.4
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864	9.1	18.4	44.9	19.5	8.2		104.2	102.2	2.0
Romania	RO	19 042	4.0	33.8	51.3	11.0	0.0		101.8	99.8	2.0
San Marino	SM	34				98.0	2.0		116.0	120.0	-4.1
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571	0.1	4.3	28.4	36.5	30.8		114.0	103.8	10.2
Slovakia	SK	5 435		2.4	41.7	45.0	10.9		112.4	111.0	1.4
Slovenia	SI	2 107				43.9	56.1		120.7	117.2	3.6
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	1.8	14.8	34.3	43.9	5.3		109.2	109.8	-0.6
Sweden	SE	10 452	28.6	68.8	2.5				92.2	95.0	-2.8
Switzerland	CH	8 739				21.6	76.0	2.3	122.6	120.6	2.0
Türkiye	TR	84 680	37.9	14.6	15.9	19.3	11.2	1.1	97.5	104.3	-6.8
Total		558 706	9.0	12.1	22.6	39.3	14.2	2.8	109.7	109.4	0.3
			21.1				17.0				
EU-27		442 153	3.8	11.5	24.2	44.0	13.3	3.3	111.9	110.3	1.5
			15.2				16.6				
Northern Europe		33 742	35.9	61.6	2.4	0.0			91.6	94.1	-2.5
Western Europe		85 476	2.1	8.3	28.5	52.8	8.4	0.0	110.1	107.1	3.0
Central Europe		166 396		3.4	18.7	59.2	18.6	0.1	114.6	112.5	2.1
Southern Europe		141 577	1.6	8.2	27.8	33.7	18.4	10.3	116.3	115.4	1.0
South-Eastern Europe		131 514	26.3	17.2	23.3	21.1	11.3	0.7	100.7	104.0	-3.3
Kosovo	KS	1 774		6.5	72.9	19.7	0.9		107.2	104.0	3.2
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797	0.1	3.7	17.0	40.8	38.4		115.8	103.8	12.0

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and five-year mean 2017-2021.

The overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in 2022 in terms of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means has been estimated to be $110 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $112 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the considered European area and for the EU-27, respectively, i.e. of about $0.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $1.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ higher than the five-year 2017-2021 mean concentration, respectively. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Andorra ($11 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and Türkiye ($7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), the highest increase was estimated in Serbia (both incl. and excl. Kosovo) (10 and $12 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively).

Figure 3.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), 2022

Figure 3.2 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of $2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 100 and $126 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For classes above $126 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a sharp decline of population frequency can be seen.

Figure 3.2 Population exposure frequency distribution, O_3 indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022. The EU target value threshold ($120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is marked by the red line

The boxplot showing for individual countries the ozone concentrations expressed as the indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means to which the population per country was exposed in 2022 is presented in Summary, Figure S.1.

3.2 Ozone – peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means

In September 2021, the WHO introduced new AQG for O₃. The new long-term Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level ⁽⁵⁾ for O₃ is set to 60 µg/m³ and it is related to the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration of the so-called peak season. The peak season is defined as the six consecutive months of the year with the highest six-month running-average ozone concentration. In regions away from the equator, this period will typically occur during the warm season within a single calendar year in the northern hemisphere or spanning two calendar years in the southern hemisphere (WHO, 2021). For details of the calculations of this indicator, see Annex 2 Section A2.1.

The new long-term WHO AQG level for O₃ (i.e. 60 µg/ m³, not to be exceeded by the average of the daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration during the peak season) was determined based on average concentrations observed in studies that examined the health effects of long-term O₃ exposure. By setting this guideline, WHO aims to minimize the health risks associated with long-term ozone exposure and non-accidental mortality (WHO, 2021a). This peak season indicator is not regulated in any of the EU air quality directives, and there are no associated limit or target values defined.

Concentration map

Map 3.3 presents the final combined map for ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means. In the map, all coloured area except the dark green ones show values of peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means above 60 µg/m³ in 2022.

The map shows that in 2022, areas with peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means exceeding 60 µg/m³ cover the entire mapped region with the exception of a small area in Türkiye (specifically in Ankara). Similar to other O₃ characteristics, lower values (< 80 µg/m³) are observed in northern Europe (Sweden, Finland, the Baltic states), while higher values (> 100 µg/m³) are observed in central Europe (Switzerland, Slovenia, parts of Austria and Hungary), southern and south-eastern Europe (parts of Italy, parts of Spain and Portugal, southern France, parts of various Balkan countries, and large areas of Türkiye).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.5 of Annex 4.

Since the concentration map for ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means is presented in this report for the first time for 2022, it was not possible to calculate a five-year mean (2017-2021) and subsequently create a differences map, as done for other pollutants and indicators.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 map of the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means is about 7 % for rural and 10 % for urban areas (Annex 3, Section A3.2). The low uncertainty values are influenced by the character of this ozone indicator. Note that the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets no modelling uncertainty for ozone annual indicators.

⁽⁵⁾ Besides the short-term AQG of 100 µg/m³ defined as 99th percentile of the annual distribution of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration (WHO, 2021a).

Map 3.3 Ozone indicator peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022

Population exposure

Table 3.2 and Figure 3.3 give, for the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes. Table 3.2 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area.

In 2022, it has been estimated that 98 % of the considered European population (including Türkiye) and 100 % of the EU-27 population lived in areas where the ozone concentration was above the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means of 60 µg/m³.

Figure 3.3 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022

Table 3.2 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs·1000)	Ozone — peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means (%)						Population-weighted concentration 2022
			< 60	60 - 80	80 - 90	90 - 100	100 - 120	> 120	
Albania	AL	2 794			11.7	83.2	5.1	95.0	
Andorra	AD	79			75.5	17.2	7.3	85.2	
Austria	AT	8 979			2.9	86.2	10.9	96.6	
Belgium	BE	11 618		0.4	77.6	22.0		88.4	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271			0.9	64.9	34.2	98.0	
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	1.0	75.0	12.9	10.0	1.1	0.0	76.5
Croatia	HR	3 862				46.1	53.9	101.1	
Cyprus	CY	1 288		0.1	51.0	35.5	13.4	91.0	
Czechia	CZ	10 517			0.1	99.1	0.8	95.4	
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926		42.1	57.9	0.1		80.0	
Estonia	EE	1 332		91.1	8.9			77.1	
Finland	FI	5 548		99.6	0.4			75.5	
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647		0.6	39.6	47.6	12.2	92.8	
Germany	DE	83 237		0.3	18.6	75.5	5.6	93.5	
Greece	GR	10 460		15.7	7.8	27.6	48.9	0.0	95.4
Hungary	HU	9 689			3.7	89.4	6.9	96.6	
Iceland	IS	376		82.7	17.3			78.3	
Ireland	IE	5 060		86.6	13.4			76.7	
Italy	IT	59 030		1.1	12.6	33.7	46.9	5.7	102.6
Latvia	LV	1 876		96.8	3.2			77.3	
Liechtenstein	LI	39				98.0	2.0	98.5	
Lithuania	LT	2 806		86.9	13.1			77.7	
Luxembourg	LU	645			46.9	53.1		90.9	
Malta	MT	521				95.8	4.2	96.1	
Monaco	MC	37					100.0	106.5	
Montenegro	ME	618			24.5	75.1	0.4	91.8	
Netherlands	NL	17 591		3.6	86.5	10.0		85.7	
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	0.5	66.9	22.6	8.1	1.8	78.1	
Norway	NO	5 425		69.3	30.7	0.0		79.1	
Poland	PL	37 654		1.2	59.9	38.9	0.0	88.2	
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864		3.0	62.3	31.3	3.4	88.2	
Romania	RO	19 042		13.8	70.1	16.0	0.1	85.1	
San Marino	SM	34				99.9	0.1	97.3	
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571		9.4	24.1	60.2	6.3	92.1	
Slovakia	SK	5 435			17.3	80.1	2.7	93.9	
Slovenia	SI	2 107				54.4	45.6	100.0	
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181		7.9	16.8	72.6	2.7	92.6	
Sweden	SE	10 452		72.1	27.9			78.4	
Switzerland	CH	8 739				53.5	46.4	0.1	100.2
Türkiye	TR	84 680	13.6	42.0	12.5	17.2	14.5	0.2	78.6
Total		558 706	2.0	14.6	26.8	43.2	12.7	0.6	90.1
			16.6				13.4		
EU-27		442 153	0.0	9.2	30.3	47.7	12.0	0.8	92.1
			9.2				12.8		
Northern Europe		33 742		74.8	25.2	0.0			78.1
Western Europe		85 476		6.2	58.7	33.6	1.6		88.8
Central Europe		166 396		0.4	24.0	68.7	6.8	0.0	93.2
Southern Europe		141 577		4.3	16.8	47.0	29.5	2.4	97.4
South-Eastern Europe		131 514	8.6	34.2	21.5	23.3	12.4	0.1	82.0
Kosovo	KS	1 774		26.8	51.5	15.7	5.9		85.3
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797		4.9	17.1	71.6	6.4		93.9

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure.

The overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in terms of peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means has been estimated to be 90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2022 for the considered European area (including Türkiye) and 92 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the EU-27. When considering individual countries, the highest overall population-weighted ozone concentrations in terms of peak season average has been estimated to be 107 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Monaco and 103 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Italy, respectively, while the lowest was estimated to be 76 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Finland.

Figure 3.4 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 80 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. For classes above 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, a sharp decline of population frequency can be seen.

Figure 3.4 Population exposure frequency distribution, ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022. The 2021 WHO AQG (60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is marked by the green line.

The boxplot in Figure 3.5 shows for individual countries the ozone concentrations expressed as peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means to which the population per country was exposed in 2022. It can be seen that the countries with the highest ozone concentrations are located in the southern, south-eastern and central parts of Europe.

Figure 3.5 Population frequency distribution, O₃ peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022. The 2021 WHO AQG (60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is marked by the green line.

3.3 Ozone – SOMO35 and SOMO10

SOMO35 is the annually accumulated ozone maximum daily 8-hourly means in excess of 35 ppb (i.e. $70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). It is not regulated in the EU air quality directives and there are no associated limit or target values defined. Nevertheless, it is considered by the WHO as a good indicator of human exposure to ozone (WHO, 2013). Comparing the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means versus the SOMO35 for all background stations shows no simple relationship between the two indicators. However, it seems that the TV threshold of the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means (being $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is related approximately with a SOMO35 value in the range of $6\,000$ - $8\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. This comparison motivates a somewhat arbitrarily chosen threshold of $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, in order to facilitate the discussion of the observed distributions of SOMO35 levels in their spatial and temporal context. This threshold is used in this and previous papers (Horálek et al., 2023, and the references cited therein) when dealing with the population exposure estimates.

SOMO10 is the annually accumulated ozone maximum daily 8-hourly means in excess of 10 ppb (i.e. $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). This indicator was introduced due to its link to the health impact assessment, since the WHO recommended using the SOMO10 as an alternative to the SOMO35 when estimating the health impact of ozone (WHO, 2013).

Concentration maps

Maps 3.4 and 3.5 presents the final combined map for SOMO35 and SOMO10. In the final combined map of SOMO35, the red and dark red areas show values above $8\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, while the orange areas show values above $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. In the case of SOMO10, the boundaries of concentration classes have been chosen quite arbitrary, in order to reflect the concentration distribution of this indicator. In the final combined map of SOMO10, the red and dark red areas show values above $24\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$.

Map 3.4 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO35, 2022

Map 3.5 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO10, 2022

Like in the case of the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means, generally the southern and south-eastern parts of Europe show higher ozone SOMO35 and SOMO10 concentrations than the northern parts. Higher levels of ozone also occur more frequently in mountainous areas south of 50 degrees latitude than in lowlands. In 2022, SOMO35 levels above 6 000 µg/m³·d were estimated in almost all of Türkiye, Italy, Spain and Portugal, in much of the Balkan countries and in a large area of France.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 maps of the SOMO35 and SOMO10 is about 25 % and 11 %, respectively, for rural areas and 33 % and 14 %, respectively, for urban areas (see Annex 3).

Map 3.6 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for the O₃ indicators SOMO35 and SOMO10. Orange to red areas show an increase of those O₃ indicators in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

The largest increases in SOMO35 and SOMO10 levels were recorded in a few areas of several Balkan countries, Türkiye, in a relatively continuous area of northern Italy and southern France, and in Portugal. Areas with notable increases were estimated in northern France, Germany, Spain, and to a limited extent in Norway (only in a case of SOMO35). Areas with the highest decreases were found in Türkiye, some Balkan states, Italy, and the Iberian Peninsula.

Map 3.6 Difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for SOMO35 and SOMO10

Population exposure

SOMO35

Table 3.3 and Figure 3.6 give for SOMO35 the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes. Table 3.3 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area.

It has been estimated that in 2022 about 18 % of the considered European population (including Türkiye), and about 17 % of the EU-27 population, lived in areas with SOMO35 values above 6 000 µg/m³·d (see above on the motivation of this criterion).

In 2022, like in the previous several years, the northern and western European countries (with the exception of France in 2022) have had almost no inhabitants exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d. No population has been exposed to concentrations SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d in 11 countries. In Norway, Poland, Romania, Czechia, North Macedonia, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Hungary, Liechtenstein, Montenegro, San Marino, Germany, Portugal and Serbia (in ascending order) between > 0 and 9 % of the population has been exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d. In Albania, Kosovo, France, Austria, Andorra, Spain, Türkiye, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia, between 14 and 38 % of population has been exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d. The largest proportion of the population (more than 50 % up to 100 %) was exposed to SOMO35 concentrations above 6 000 µg/m³·d in Switzerland, Slovenia, Cyprus, Italy, Greece, Monaco and Malta.

Table 3.3 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator SOMO35, 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inths·1000)	Ozone — SOMO10, exposed population, 2022 (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 2 000	2 000- 4 000	4 000- 6 000	6 000- 8 000	8 000- 10 000	> 10 000	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 794		8.6	77.3	14.0	0.2		5 177	6 108	-931
Andorra	AD	79		72.4	9.7	14.1	3.8		3 656	4 924	-1 268
Austria	AT	8 979		2.0	81.7	15.2	1.1	0.1	5 482	5 405	77
Belgium	BE	11 618		41.4	58.6				4 052	3 243	810
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271			62.3	32.1	5.5	0.0	6 085	5 689	396
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	26.1	57.7	11.1	4.8	0.3		2 934	3 371	-437
Croatia	HR	3 862			62.1	25.0	12.8	0.0	6 104	5 934	169
Cyprus	CY	1 288			40.5	42.8	7.0	9.7	6 664	6 603	61
Czechia	CZ	10 517			99.3	0.7			5 045	4 911	134
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926	21.4	78.3	0.3				2 535	2 688	-153
Estonia	EE	1 332	71.8	28.2					1 840	2 063	-223
Finland	FI	5 548	79.5	20.5					1 754	1 751	2
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647	0.1	20.7	64.4	10.6	4.3	0.0	4 916	4 291	625
Germany	DE	83 237	0.1	14.4	78.2	7.3	0.0		4 808	4 122	686
Greece	GR	10 460	0.0	8.3	27.0	56.9	6.2	1.6	6 313	6 592	-279
Hungary	HU	9 689		1.1	92.8	6.0			5 314	4 817	497
Iceland	IS	376	38.7	61.1	0.2				1 981	1 590	392
Ireland	IE	5 060	38.9	61.0	0.2				2 148	1 976	172
Italy	IT	59 030		4.2	35.8	26.7	25.6	7.7	6 910	6 551	359
Latvia	LV	1 876	10.7	89.3					2 150	2 079	71
Liechtenstein	LI	39			93.3	6.6		0.1	5 779	5 426	352
Lithuania	LT	2 806	21.6	78.4					2 225	2 437	-211
Luxembourg	LU	645			100.0				4 406	3 613	793
Malta	MT	521				97.4	1.7	1.0	6 599	6 156	443
Monaco	MC	37					100.0		8 042	7 240	802
Montenegro	ME	618		8.1	85.1	6.7	0.1		5 027	5 694	-667
Netherlands	NL	17 591		83.0	17.0				3 486	2 994	492
North Macedonia	MK	1 837		56.0	40.2	3.7	0.1		3 936	4 083	-146
Norway	NO	5 425	28.7	70.6	0.7	0.0			2 242	2 202	40
Poland	PL	37 654		55.5	44.5	0.0			3 851	3 824	27
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864		54.2	36.8	8.6	0.4	0.0	4 155	3 795	360
Romania	RO	19 042	2.0	66.6	31.0	0.3			3 639	3 349	290
San Marino	SM	34			93.2	6.8			5 578	6 108	-530
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571	0.1	16.3	73.2	10.3	0.2		4 989	4 028	961
Slovakia	SK	5 435		11.5	84.5	4.0			4 905	4 721	184
Slovenia	SI	2 107			46.9	45.6	7.5	0.0	6 296	5 950	345
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	0.5	18.0	62.0	19.3	0.2	0.0	5 082	5 294	-212
Sweden	SE	10 452	31.3	68.7	0.0				2 289	2 483	-193
Switzerland	CH	8 739			48.1	48.0	3.5	0.4	6 139	5 577	562
Türkiye	TR	84 680	28.8	22.5	29.2	12.5	5.5	1.5	4 008	5 102	-1 094
Total		558 706	7.2	26.1		12.1	4.5	1.1	4 683	4 565	118
EU-27		442 153	3.4	27.2		11.4	4.5	1.1			
Northern Europe		33 742	36.9	63.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	2 199	2 297	-98
Western Europe		85 476	2.3	41.7	53.8	2.3	0.0	0.0	4 099	3 530	568
Central Europe		166 396	0.0	20.5	71.1	8.0	0.3	0.0	4 758	4 324	434
Southern Europe		141 577	0.1	12.1	44.4	26.5	13.5	3.5	6 033	5 854	180
South-Eastern Europe		131 514	19.8	29.4	34.9	10.9	4.0	0.9	4 111	4 686	-575
Kosovo	KS	1 774	0.0	34.5	51.0	14.0	0.6		4 572	4 412	160
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797	0.1	11.6	78.9	9.3	0.1		5 097	3 934	1 162

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021.

In 2022, the population-weighted ozone concentration in terms of SOMO35 for the total mapped area was estimated to be 4 683 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, i.e. 118 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ higher than the five-year 2017-2021 mean SOMO35 concentration. For the EU-27, it was 4 793 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, i.e. 315 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ higher than the five-year 2017-2021 mean SOMO35 concentration. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Andorra (1 268 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$) and Türkiye (1 094 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$), while the highest increase was estimated in Serbia (1162 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$).

Figure 3.6 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator SOMO35 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$), 2022

Figure 3.7 shows, for the whole mapped area, the frequency distribution of SOMO35 for population exposure classes of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. The highest frequencies are found for classes between 4 000 and 6 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. One can see a steep decline of population frequency for exposure classes between 6 500 and 8 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ and a continuous mild decline of population frequency for classes above 8 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$.

Figure 3.7 Population exposure frequency distribution, ozone indicator SOMO35, 2022

Figure 3.8 shows for individual countries the ozone indicator SOMO35 to which the population was exposed in 2022. It can be seen that the countries with the highest ozone concentrations are located in the southern and south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 3.8 Ozone concentrations expressed as indicator SOMO35 to which the population per country was exposed in 2022

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50 % in the case of the black marker, 25 % and 75 % in the cases of the box's edges, 2 % and 98 % in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

SOMO10

Figure 3.9 and Table 3.4 give for SOMO10 the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes. Table 3.4 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapped area.

Figure 3.9 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of the ozone indicator SOMO10 (µg/m³·d), 2022

Table 3.4 Population exposure and population-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator SOMO10, 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inths·1000)	Ozone — SOMO10, exposed population, 2022 (%)					Population-weighted concentration			
			< 15 000	15 000- 18 000	18 000- 21 000	21 000- 24 000	24 000- 27 000	> 27 000	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
			Albania	AL	2 794		8.5	67.9	20.9	2.7	
Andorra	AD	79		72.4	5.8	10.3	11.5		17 447	19 845	-2 398
Austria	AT	8 979		9.7	70.7	16.6	2.9	0.1	19 989	20 020	-31
Belgium	BE	11 618		20.0	79.9	0.1			18 452	16 985	1 467
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271		7.0	59.7	25.8	6.4	1.1	20 228	20 387	-159
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	40.5	42.8	9.4	6.3	1.0	0.0	15 781	16 666	-885
Croatia	HR	3 862		14.7	49.2	18.6	16.1	1.4	20 735	20 985	-250
Cyprus	CY	1 288		22.9	39.4	23.8	12.6	1.4	20 648	21 325	-677
Czechia	CZ	10 517		0.9	92.8	6.3			19 526	19 700	-174
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926		29.5	70.5	0.1			18 501	18 169	332
Estonia	EE	1 332		96.3	3.7				16 708	16 737	-29
Finland	FI	5 548		99.6	0.4				16 152	16 144	8
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647		9.6	65.2	18.5	6.6	0.1	20 286	19 526	761
Germany	DE	83 237		7.4	86.7	5.9	0.1		19 252	18 246	1 006
Greece	GR	10 460	4.5	19.4	15.2	35.5	24.5	0.8	21 153	21 778	-625
Hungary	HU	9 689		4.8	92.9	2.3			19 440	18 975	464
Iceland	IS	376		92.9	7.1				16 805	16 591	214
Ireland	IE	5 060		64.5	35.3	0.2			17 637	17 297	340
Italy	IT	59 030		1.6	38.5	47.2	12.4	0.3	21 706	21 439	267
Latvia	LV	1 876		93.9	6.1				16 899	16 341	558
Liechtenstein	LI	39			94.2	4.3	1.4	0.1	19 594	19 557	38
Lithuania	LT	2 806		98.6	1.4				16 758	16 696	62
Luxembourg	LU	645		46.2	51.6	2.2			18 434	17 849	585
Malta	MT	521					98.3	1.7	24 824	24 049	774
Monaco	MC	37					100.0		24 383	23 504	879
Montenegro	ME	618		3.9	82.4	12.3	1.4		19 826	20 937	-1 111
Netherlands	NL	17 591		36.0	64.0				18 070	17 070	1 000
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	3.1	68.6	19.5	8.0	0.8	0.0	17 312	17 727	-415
Norway	NO	5 425	6.8	68.4	24.7	0.1			17 172	17 035	137
Poland	PL	37 654		47.0	52.5	0.4	0.0		17 995	17 970	25
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864	8.1	15.8	48.4	23.8	3.9	0.0	19 543	19 237	307
Romania	RO	19 042	2.6	60.5	33.7	3.2	0.0		17 676	17 071	605
San Marino	SM	34			86.3	13.7			20 123	21 059	-936
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571	0.1	31.8	57.3	9.7	1.0		18 830	17 593	1 237
Slovakia	SK	5 435		14.3	80.0	5.7	0.0		19 275	19 275	0
Slovenia	SI	2 107		1.3	54.7	35.5	8.5	0.0	20 966	20 867	99
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	0.9	7.5	32.5	51.3	7.8	0.0	21 211	21 329	-118
Sweden	SE	10 452		71.2	28.8				17 381	17 581	-200
Switzerland	CH	8 739			77.2	19.9	2.5	0.4	20 830	20 041	789
Türkiye	TR	84 680	45.6	25.1	16.8	6.4	5.5	0.6	15 436	17 963	-2 527
Total		558 706	7.7	21.1	50.3	16.2	4.5	0.2	18 971	19 006	-35
EU-27		442 153	1.1	20.0	56.1	18.1	4.5	0.1	19 603	19 185	419
Northern Europe		33 742	1.1	73.4	25.5	0.0			17 217	17 153	64
Western Europe		85 476		21.5	72.4	6.0	0.2	0.0	19 022	18 163	859
Central Europe		166 396		15.9	77.6	6.1	0.4	0.0	19 133	18 564	569
Southern Europe		141 577	1.2	5.8	34.0	45.6	13.2	0.3	21 444	21 305	139
South-Eastern Europe		131 514	31.2	31.3	25.3	7.4	4.3	0.4	16 468	17 992	-1 524
Kosovo	KS		72.7	12.3	12.4	2.6		18 001	18 498	-497	1 221
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	0.1	21.3	68.9	9.1	0.6		19 043	17 372	1 671	2 073

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and five-year mean 2017-2021.

The population-weighted ozone concentrations, in terms of SOMO10, were estimated to be 18 971 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ for the total mapped area. i.e. 35 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ less than the five-year 2017-2021 mean SOMO10 concentration. For the EU-27, it was 19 603 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$, i.e. 419 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$ higher than the five-year 2017-2021 mean SOMO10 concentration. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found in Türkiye (2 527 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$), while the highest absolute increase was estimated in Serbia (2 073 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$).

Figure 3.10 shows the population frequency distribution of SOMO10 for population exposure classes of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$. The graph shows the highest frequencies for classes between 16 000 and 23 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}$.

Figure 3.10 Population exposure frequency distribution, ozone indicator SOMO10, 2022

Figure 3.11 shows for individual countries the ozone indicator SOMO10 to which the population was exposed in 2022. It can be seen that the countries with the highest ozone concentrations are located in the southern and south-eastern parts of Europe.

Figure 3.11 Ozone concentrations expressed as indicator SOMO10 to which the population per country was exposed in 2022

Note: For each country, the box plot shows the concentration to which a percentage of the population was exposed: 50 % in the case of the black marker, 25 % and 75 % in the cases of the box's edges, 2 % and 98 % in the cases of the whiskers' edges.

3.4 Ozone – AOT40 vegetation and AOT40 forests

In the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) a target value (TV) and a long-term objective (LTO) for the protection of vegetation from high ozone concentrations accumulated during the growing season have been defined. TV and LTO are specified using “accumulated ozone exposure over a threshold of 40 parts per billion” (AOT40). This is calculated as a sum of the difference between hourly concentrations greater than 40 ppb (i.e. $80 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and 40 ppb, using only observations between 08:00 and 20:00 Central European Time (CET) each day, calculated over three months from 1 May to 31 July. The TV is $18\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ (averaged over five years) and the LTO is $6\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$.

Note that the term “vegetation” as used in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) is not further defined. Nevertheless, the TV used in the directive is quite similar as the critical level used in the Mapping Manual (CLRTAP, 2017a) for “agricultural crops” (although the definitions of AOT40 by the EU and the CLRTAP are slightly different), so the term vegetation in the Air Quality Directive has been interpreted as primarily agricultural crops. Therefore, the exposure of agricultural crops has been evaluated here based on the AOT40 for vegetation as defined in the Air Quality Directive and the agricultural areas, defined as the CORINE Land Cover level-1 class 2 Agricultural areas (encompassing the level-2 classes 2.1 Arable land, 2.2 Permanent crops, 2.3 Pastures and 2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas), see Section 3.3.2. Note that in addition to these agricultural areas there are several other CLC classes that could be considered “vegetation”, namely level-2 classes 1.4 Artificial, non-agricultural vegetated areas (encompassing the level-3 classes 1.4.1 Green urban areas and 1.4.2 Sport and leisure facilities), 3.1 Forests (see below) and 3.2 Scrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations. These other CLC classes have not been considered (apart from forests, see below).

Next to the AOT40 for vegetation protection, the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) defines also the AOT40 for forest protection, which is calculated similarly as the AOT40 for vegetation, but is summed over six months from 1 April to 30 September. For AOT40 for forests there is no TV defined in the Air Quality Directive. However, there is a critical level (CL) established by the CLRTAP, see CLRTAP (2017a). This critical level is set at $10\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$. Although CLRTAP (2017a) calculates the AOT40 indicators somewhat differently (e.g. it uses the ozone concentration corrected at canopy height), we further use this CL level for the AOT40 for forests calculated according to the EC (2008).

For the exposure of forests evaluation, the CLC level-2 class 3.1 Forests has been used.

The ecosystem based accumulative ozone indicators described in this section are specifically prepared for calculation of the EEA indicator on ecosystem exposure to ozone (EEA, 2024b). For the estimation of the vegetation and forested area exposure to accumulated ozone, the maps in this section are created on a grid of 2 km resolution. The exposure frequency distribution outcomes are based on the overlay with the 100 m grid resolution of the CLC2018 land cover classes.

Concentration maps

The interpolated maps of AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests are applicable for rural areas only. Map 3.7 presents the final map of AOT40 for vegetation in 2022. Note that in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) the TV is actually defined as $18\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ averaged over five years. Here only 2022 data are presented, and no five-year average has been calculated. Therefore, we evaluate the concentrations against what we call the target value threshold, an AOT40 of $18\,000 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ in 2022.

Map 3.7 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation, rural map, 2022

The areas in the map with concentrations above the TV threshold of 18 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ are marked in red and dark red. The areas below the long-term objective (LTO) are marked in green. AOT40 levels above the TV threshold for vegetation occur specifically in southern and south-eastern of Europe (Italy, parts of Spain, Portugal and France and parts of the Balkan countries and Türkiye) and partly also in central Europe (all of Switzerland, parts of Germany, Austria, Slovenia, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland and Hungary). The highest levels (dark red) were estimated in the north of Italy, in south-west of Türkiye and in Cyprus. The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 map of the AOT40 for vegetation is about 31 % (Annex 3, Section A3.3).

Map 3.8 presents the final map of AOT40 for forests in 2022. The areas in the map with concentrations above the critical level (CL) defined by CLRTAP (2017a) are marked in yellow, orange, red and dark red. One can see large forested areas exceeding this level in most of Europe, with the exception of parts of some northern countries and Ireland. The highest values of the AOT40 for forests in 2022 were found mainly in southern Europe (south of France, the Po Valley and Cyprus) and Türkiye. The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 map of the AOT40 for forests is about 30 % (Annex 3, Section A3.3).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the AOT40 maps including the AOT40 values based on the actual rural background measurement data at stations are presented in Maps A4.8 and A4.9 of Annex 4.

Map 3.9 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for AOT40 for vegetation and for AOT40 for forests. Orange to red areas show an increase of AOT40 in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

The most notable increases in AOT40 for vegetation were recorded in large areas of southern Europe, primarily in Portugal, eastern Spain, southern France, and northern Italy. Additionally, substantial increases in AOT40 were observed in south-eastern European countries, specifically Romania, Serbia, Bulgaria, and Türkiye. Higher increases were also noted in central Europe, particularly in southern Poland and Hungary and Slovenia. Elsewhere, a decrease in AOT40 has been observed across various parts throughout the mapped area, with the most notable decrease in some parts of Türkiye.

Regarding AOT40 levels for forests, the situation mirrors that of AOT40 for vegetation. However, for AOT40 in forests, we observe a noticeable decline in Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, and North Macedonia, along with smaller and less widespread increases in Romania, Bulgaria, and Serbia.

Map 3.8 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for forests, rural map, 2022

Map 3.9 Difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for ozone indicators, AOT40 for vegetation (left) and AOT40 for forests (right)

Vegetation exposure

Agricultural crops

The rural map with the ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation has been combined with the land cover CLC2018 map. Following a similar procedure as described in Horálek et al. (2007), the exposure of agricultural areas (as defined above) has been calculated at the country-level.

Table 3.5 gives the absolute and relative agricultural area for each country and for five European regions where ozone concentrations are above the target value (TV) threshold and the long-term objective (LTO) for protection of vegetation as defined in the Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008). The frequency distribution of the agricultural area over some exposure classes per country is presented as well.

Table 3.5 Agricultural area exposure and agricultural-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation, 2022

Country	Agricultural area, 2022					Percentage of agricultural area (%)				Agricultural-weighted conc.			
	Total area (km ²)	> LTO (6 000 µg/m ³ ·h)		> TV (18 000 µg/m ³ ·h)		< 6 000	6 000- 12 000	12 000- 18 000	18 000- 27 000	> 27 000	(µg/m ³ ·h)		
		(km ²)	(%)	(km ²)	(%)						2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	8 017	8 017	100.0	3 878	48.4		12.2	39.4	48.4	0.0	16 834	18 260	-1 425
Andorra	13	13	100.0	9	66.7			33.3	66.7		20 083		
Austria	26 827	26 827	100.0	13 319	49.6		4.7	45.7	49.6	0.0	17 658	17 949	-290
Belgium	17 473	17 473	100.0				64.5	35.5			11 187	11 621	-434
Bosnia and Herzegovina	17 023	15 649	91.9	10	0.1	8.1	67.2	24.6	0.1		10 215	13 120	-2 904
Bulgaria	57 390	57 387	100.0	12 794	22.3	0.0	31.6	46.1	21.6	0.7	14 587	10 740	3 847
Croatia	22 168	22 059	99.5	3 819	17.2	0.5	34.3	48.0	13.3	3.9	14 287	15 011	-724
Cyprus	4 291	4 291	100.0	4 291	100.0					47.9	27 383	22 279	5 104
Czechia	44 784	44 784	100.0	19 383	43.3		0.1	56.6	43.3		17 709	16 661	1 048
Denmark (incl. Faroes)	31 235	17 110	54.8			45.2	54.8				6 053	6 220	-167
Estonia	14 252	13	0.1			99.9	0.1				3 745	3 549	195
Finland	27 504					100.0					1 549	2 810	-1 260
France	323 377	320 050	99.0	29 326	9.1	1.0	60.5	29.4	7.3	1.7	12 244	11 072	1 172
Germany	204 463	204 369	100.0	54 277	26.5	0.0	27.3	46.1	26.5		14 723	13 252	1 471
Greece	50 052	50 052	100.0	39 048	78.0		1.6	20.3	64.0	14.0	21 617	20 058	1 559
Hungary	60 390	60 390	100.0	41 565	68.8		0.6	30.6	65.7	3.1	20 087	15 054	5 033
Iceland	2 518					100.0					208	1 061	-853
Ireland	46 756					100.0					856	2 936	-2 080
Italy	155 718	155 718	100.0	118 289	76.0		2.5	21.5	43.1	32.8	25 139	21 578	3 562
Latvia	25 532	1	0.0			100.0	0.0				1 843	4 015	-2 171
Liechtenstein	37	37	100.0	2	5.6			94.4	5.6		15 606	18 566	-2 960
Lithuania	38 155					100.0					2 703	5 259	-2 556
Luxembourg	1 351	1 351	100.0					100.0			14 220	13 415	805
Malta	125	125	100.0	125	100.0					86.2	23 025	19 808	3 217
Monaco													
Montenegro	2 242	2 242	100.0	583	26.0		3.4	70.7	26.0		16 556	14 811	1 745
Netherlands	23 644	23 169	98.0			2.0	88.5	9.5			8 535	8 906	-371
North Macedonia	9 146	9 146	100.0	1 670	18.3		22.7	59.0	18.3		14 673	16 884	-2 211
Norway	15 637	814	5.2			94.8	5.2	0.0			2 764	3 229	-465
Poland	183 268	172 825	94.3	10 076	5.5	5.7	52.7	36.1	5.5		11 466	11 275	191
Portugal	42 566	42 132	99.0	10 979	25.8	1.0	35.4	37.8	25.8	0.0	14 742	10 090	4 652
Romania	135 279	135 033	99.8	13 404	9.9	0.2	30.3	59.6	9.9		13 568	9 183	4 386
San Marino	42	42	100.0	42	100.0				100.0		22 368	20 423	1 945
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	46 768	46 768	100.0	30 926	66.1		1.3	32.5	65.8	0.3	19 191	13 828	5 362
Slovakia	23 100	23 100	100.0	10 701	46.3		2.4	51.3	46.3		17 221	14 263	2 958
Slovenia	6 986	6 986	100.0	6 669	95.5			4.5	87.3	8.1	21 780	17 259	4 521
Spain	241 014	234 460	97.3	96 720	40.1	2.7	11.9	45.2	38.4	1.8	16 566	15 739	827
Sweden	39 035	6 089	15.6			84.4	15.6				4 335	5 231	-895
Switzerland	11 359	11 359	100.0	10 471	92.2			7.8	90.4	1.8	21 297	18 130	3 167
Türkiye	339 984	330 533	97.2	224 183	65.9	2.8	7.5	23.8	43.2	22.7	20 920	20 720	200
Total	2 299 525	2 050 414	89.2	756 559	32.9	10.8	24.5	31.8	26.3	6.6	15 075	13 793	1 283
EU-27	1 846 681	1 625 794	88.0	484 786	26.3	12.0	28.2	33.6	22.2	4.0	14 019	12 567	1 452
Northern Europe	193 869	24 027	12.4			87.6	12.4	0.0			3 344	4 552	-1 208
Western Europe	346 009	295 450	85.4	14 805	4.3	14.6	61.6	19.6	4.2	0.0	9 700	9 648	52
Central Europe	561 215	550 677	98.1	166 464	29.7	1.9	27.5	40.9	29.2	0.5	14 939	13 487	1 452
Southern Europe	560 414	553 426	98.8	284 023	50.7	1.2	11.3	36.8	38.2	12.5	19 268	16 950	2 318
South-Eastern Europe	638 018	626 834	98.2	291 267	45.7	1.8	16.8	35.8	33.3	12.3	17 993	16 363	1 630
Kosovo	42 601	42 601	100.0	27 309	64.1		1.5	34.4	63.8	0.3	20 851	15 518	5 333
Serbia (without Kosovo)	4 167	4 167	100.0	3 616	86.8			13.2	86.6	0.2	19 028	13 663	5 365

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed agricultural area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no agricultural area in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021.

Table 3.5 illustrates that in 2022, 33 % of all European agricultural land including Türkiye has been exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV threshold of 18 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$. For the area for the EU-27, it has been about 26 %. None of the agricultural area presents ozone levels in excess of the TV in thirteen countries. Agricultural areas with ozone concentrations above TV threshold covered less than 25 % in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Poland, Liechtenstein, France, Romania, Croatia, North Macedonia and Bulgaria (in ascending order). In Portugal, Montenegro, Germany, Spain, Czechia, Slovakia, Albania and Austria, between 26 % and 50 % of agricultural area has been exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV threshold. The largest proportion of the agricultural area exposed to ozone concentrations above the TV threshold is Kosovo, Türkiye, Andorra, Hungary, Italy, Greece, Serbia, Switzerland, Slovenia, San Marino, Malta and Cyprus (from 65 % up to 100 %).

Considering the LTO of 6 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, the total European area (including Türkiye) in excess has been 89 %. For the area for the EU-27, it has been 88 %. In 2022, values of the AOT40 for vegetation above the LTO have occurred in all countries with the exception of Iceland, Finland, Ireland and Lithuania. Fewer than 15 % of the areas with values above the LTO have occurred in Latvia, Estonia, Norway and Sweden. In the remaining countries, the agricultural area exposed above the LTO in 2022 has been between 55 % and 100 %. In Switzerland, Slovenia, Slovakia, San Marino, Serbia, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Malta, Luxembourg, Liechtenstein, Kosovo, Italy, Hungary, Greece, Czechia, Cyprus, Belgium, Austria, Andorra and Albania, the entire agriculture area was exposed to AOT40 levels above the LTO for protection of vegetation.

In 2022, the agricultural-weighted ozone concentration of vegetation-related AOT40 for the total mapped area was estimated to be 15 075 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 1 283 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ higher than the five-year 2017-2021 mean. For the EU-27 area, it was estimated to be 14 019 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 1 452 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ higher than the five-year 2017-2021 mean. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest decrease was found in Bosnia and Herzegovina (2 904 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$), while the highest increase was estimated in Serbia (both incl. and excl. Kosovo) (5 362 and 5365 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, respectively).

Forests

The rural map with ozone indicator AOT40 for forests was combined with the land cover CLC2018 map. Following a similar procedure as described in Horálek et al. (2007), the exposure of forest areas (as defined above) has been calculated for each country, for the same five European regions as for crops and for Europe as a whole. Table 3.6 gives the absolute and relative forest area where the critical level (CL) set at 10 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, the same level as defined in CLRTAP (2017a), and the value 20 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ (which is equal to the earlier used reporting value, RV, as was defined in the repealed ozone directive 2002/3/EC) are exceeded. Next to the forest area in exceedance, the table presents the frequency distribution of the forest area over some exposure classes.

The CL was exceeded in 2022 at 64 % of all European forested area including Türkiye. For the area of the EU-27 it was exceeded at about 61 %. As in previous years, most countries continue to have in 2022 the whole or considerable forest areas in excess of the CL. In 2022, there were only three countries without CL exceedance (Iceland, Estonia and Lithuania). Up to 10 % of the areas with values above the CL have occurred in Finland, Latvia, Ireland, and Sweden. In Norway and Denmark, the areas with the values above CL has been 28 % and 79 %, respectively. In the remaining countries, the CL for AOT40 was exceeded in more than 90 % of the area of the respective country. In 24 countries, the entire forested area was exposed to AOT40 levels above the CL for forests.

In 2022, the forest-weighted ozone concentration of forest-related AOT40 for the total mapped area was estimated to be 19 543 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 446 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ less than the five-year 2017-2021 mean. For the EU-27 area, it was estimated to be 18 715 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. 345 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ less than the five-year 2017-2021 mean. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease was found

in North Macedonia (9 804 µg/m³-h), while the highest increase was estimated (apart from the microstate Monaco) in Slovenia (4 427 µg/m³-h).

Table 3.6 Forested area exposure and forest-weighted concentrations, ozone indicator AOT40 for forests, 2022

Country	Forested area					Percentage of forested area [%]				Forest-weighted conc. (µg/m ³ -h)			
	Total area (km ²)	> CL (10 000 µg/m ³ -h) (km ²)	(%)	> RV (20 000 µg/m ³ -h) (km ²)	(%)	< 10 000 (%)	10 000-20 000 (µg/m ³ -h)	20 000-30 000 (µg/m ³ -h)	30 000-50 000 (µg/m ³ -h)	> 50 000 (µg/m ³ -h)	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	7 104	7 104	100.0	6 910	97.3		2.7	47.3	50.0	0.0	30 026	38 566	-8 540
Andorra	128	128	100.0	128	100.0			32.6	67.4		31 346		
Austria	36 667	36 667	100.0	34 492	94.1		5.9	65.8	28.3		27 360	31 530	-4 171
Belgium	6 089	6 089	100.0	5 715	93.9		6.1	93.9			22 421	21 517	903
Bosnia-Herzegovina	23 911	23 193	97.0	8 797	36.8	3.0	60.2	35.8	1.0		18 555	27 067	-8 512
Bulgaria	34 675	34 675	100.0	31 392	90.5		9.5	53.0	36.8	0.7	28 638	27 527	1 111
Croatia	19 734	19 671	99.7	13 929	70.6	0.3	29.1	41.8	28.6	0.2	25 668	29 911	-4 243
Cyprus	1 458	1 458	100.0	1 458	100.0				20.9	79.1	53 369	45 697	7 672
Czechia	25 867	25 867	100.0	25 830	99.9		0.1	80.5	19.4		27 554	29 971	-2 417
Denmark (incl. Faroes)	3 747	2 950	78.7			21.3	78.7				11 611	11 628	-16
Estonia	21 080					100.0					6 852	7 016	-163
Finland	211 668	0	0.0			100.0	0.0				3 138	5 262	-2 124
France	143 376	143 375	100.0	113 325	79.0	0.0	21.0	50.0	25.2	3.8	27 413	24 540	2 873
Germany	108 031	108 030	100.0	98 167	90.9	0.0	9.1	54.3	36.6		27 528	25 921	1 607
Greece	26 122	26 122	100.0	26 047	99.7		0.3	22.2	72.6	4.9	35 898	39 384	-3 487
Hungary	17 407	17 407	100.0	17 160	98.6		1.4	51.7	46.9		30 276	29 157	1 119
Iceland	537					100.0					2 116	4 364	-2 247
Ireland	4 510	5	0.1			99.9	0.1				4 088	6 263	-2 175
Italy	79 052	79 052	100.0	78 529	99.3		0.7	19.6	59.6	20.1	40 504	39 608	896
Latvia	24 261	8	0.0			100.0	0.0				5 062	8 121	-3 060
Liechtenstein	79	79	100.0	79	100.0			28.2	71.8		35 040	35 757	-717
Lithuania	19 455					100.0					6 297	10 707	-4 410
Luxembourg	937	937	100.0	937	100.0			100.0			26 446	23 571	2 875
Malta	2	2	100.0	2	100.0				13.6		49 903	43 008	6 895
Monaco	1	1	100.0	1	100.0					100.0	65 798	37 630	28 169
Montenegro	5 777	5 777	100.0	5 741	99.4		0.6	45.2	54.2		30 653	32 564	-1 911
Netherlands	3 118	3 114	99.9	909	29.2	0.1	70.7	29.2			17 986	16 340	1 646
North Macedonia	8 144	8 144	100.0	7 879	96.8		3.2	65.8	30.9		27 857	37 661	-9 804
Norway	103 494	28 806	27.8	41	0.0	72.2	27.8	0.0			7 988	8 289	-301
Poland	96 966	88 816	91.6	34 948	36.0	8.4	55.6	36.0	0.1		18 154	20 943	-2 789
Portugal	16 512	16 426	99.5	11 600	70.3	0.5	29.2	33.3	36.9		25 653	21 351	4 302
Romania	71 273	71 209	99.9	50 580	71.0	0.1	28.9	66.5	4.5		22 423	20 559	1 864
San Marino	6	6	100.0	6	100.0				100.0		34 452	37 598	-3 146
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	27 211	27 211	100.0	27 078	99.5		0.5	36.2	63.4		31 589	29 281	2 308
Slovakia	20 484	20 484	100.0	18 792	91.7		8.3	74.1	17.7		25 709	26 469	-760
Slovenia	11 441	11 441	100.0	11 441	100.0			3.5	94.7	1.8	37 655	33 228	4 427
Spain	107 927	103 946	96.3	87 518	81.1	3.7	15.2	41.8	38.6	0.6	27 394	26 385	1 010
Sweden	261 757	25 626	9.8			90.2	9.8				6 930	7 868	-938
Switzerland	11 850	11 850	100.0	11 850	100.0			4.9	88.5	6.6	38 784	34 414	4 370
Türkiye	114 886	111 013	96.6	97 487	84.9	3.4	11.8	27.0	44.5	13.3	33 473	33 445	28
Total	1 676 742	1 066 577	63.6	828 653	49.4	36.4	14.2	26.8	20.2	2.4	19 543	19 989	-446
EU-27	1 373 615	843 380	61.4	662 773	48.3	38.6	13.1	28.3	18.2	1.8	18 715	19 060	-345
Northern	645 997	57 391	8.9	41	0.0	91.1	8.9	0.0			5 788	7 169	-1 380
Western	104 660	100 151	95.7	73 247	70.0	4.3	25.7	54.8	14.9	0.3	23 308	21 872	1 436
Central	328 793	320 642	97.5	252 759	76.9	2.5	20.6	49.8	26.8	0.3	25 539	26 173	-635
Southern	284 577	280 510	98.6	252 930	88.9	1.4	9.7	33.0	47.4	8.5	32 781	31 204	1 577
South-Eastern	312 715	307 997	98.5	249 792	79.9	1.5	18.6	43.1	31.8	5.0	28 345	28 990	-645
Kosovo	4 316	4 316	100.0	4 316	100.0			9.9	90.1		35 107	34 288	819
Serbia (without Kosovo)	22 894	22 894	100.0	22 762	99.4		0.6	41.1	58.3		30 926	28 336	2 589

Note: The percentage value “0.0” indicates that an exposed forested area exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no forested area in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2021 and the five-year mean 2017-2021.

In this context, it should be mentioned that the AOT40 indicator is not the best proxy for vegetation damage assessment. AOT40 does not take into account plant physiological control of ozone absorbed doses, which is taken into account in the POD (i.e. Phytotoxic Ozone Dose) indicators, as discussed in Section 3.5. POD indicators are known to be more related with ozone effects on plant growth than ambient air ozone concentrations alone. The AOT40 does not take into account the influence of meteorological conditions on growing season timing. Growing season’s start and end dates can change across Europe, and between years for a given site, depending on factors such as air temperature, solar radiation, photoperiod or rainfall. High temperature and dry weather favouring ozone pollution cause a reduction of ozone absorbed doses by plants due to plant physiological response to drought (i.e. the vegetation closes its stomata protecting itself from the exposure to ozone). However, plants may still

be sensitive to ozone in such weather conditions, as illustrated by foliar injury records in Aleppo pine stands growing in southern France (CLRTAP, 2016) or controlled experimental results (e.g. Alonso et al., 2014).

3.5 Ozone – Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_Y) for crops and trees

Ozone is generally recognized to be the most relevant pollutant for plants. Visible injury, reduction in growth, changes in biomass partitioning, or a higher susceptibility to pathogen attack can be the effect of ozone influence (Krupa et al., 2000). As mentioned above, scientific evidence suggests that observed effects of ozone on vegetation are more strongly related to the uptake of ozone through the stomatal leaf pores into the leaf interior (stomatal flux) than to the concentration in the atmosphere around the plants (Reich, 1987; Ashmore et al., 2004; Mills et al., 2011).

The cumulative stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) through the stomata of leaves found at the top of the canopy are calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient ozone concentration and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to ozone. The stomatal conductance has been calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model (Emberson et al., 2000) based on Jarvis (1976) as a function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a single leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density, PPFD), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture.

POD_Y (Phytotoxic Ozone Dose) is the accumulated plant uptake (flux) of ozone above a threshold of Y during a specified time or growth period. The flux-based POD_Y metrics are preferred in risk assessment over the concentration-based AOT40 exposure index. AOT40 accounts for the atmospheric ozone concentration above the leaf surface and is therefore biologically less relevant for ozone impact assessment than POD_Y as it does not take into account how ozone uptake is affected by climate, soil and plant factors.

Several POD_Y indicators are described in CLRTAP (2017a). POD_YSPEC is a species or group of species-specific POD_Y that requires comprehensive input data and is suitable for detailed risk assessment. POD_YIAM is a vegetation-type specific POD_Y that requires less input data and is suitable for large-scale modelling, including integrated assessment modelling. POD_YSPEC is further used in this report.

For crops (wheat, potato and tomato), the Y value is taken equal to 6 nmol/m² PLA s⁻¹ (i.e. per unit projected leaf area) as recommended in CLRTAP (2017a). For the details of POD_Y (and specifically POD₆SPEC as used in this report) calculation, see Annex 1, Section A1.3.

The species-specific flux models and associated response functions and critical levels for ozone-sensitive crops and cultivars can be used to quantify the potential negative impacts of O₃ on the security of food supplies at the local and regional scale. They can be used to estimate yield losses, including economic losses. A flux-threshold Y of 6 (POD₆SPEC) provides the strongest flux-effect relationships for crops (Pleijel et al., 2007). O₃ effects proved to be significant at a 5 % reduction of the effect parameter (Mills et al., 2011), hence critical levels (CL) were determined for this 5 % reduction of the effect parameter (i.e. yield, weight or quality of grain, tuber or fruit), based on the slope of the function. The POD₆SPEC CLs for crops were determined based on this reduction of relevant yield or weight, as shown in Table 3.7.

Wheat, potato and tomato are considered as representative species of crops in Europe (tomato can be regarded as representative horticultural crop for the Mediterranean and Black Sea regions, which is the case of potato for other regions). Therefore, POD₆SPEC for these crops (labelled further simply as POD₆ for wheat, potato and tomato, respectively) are recommended for regular map construction.

This report presents maps of POD₆ for wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) and tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*).

Table 3.7 POD₆SPEC critical levels for crops as determined by CLRTAP

Crop	Effect parameter	POD ₆ SPEC critical level
Wheat	grain yield	1.3 mmol/m ² PLA
Wheat	1000-grain weight	1.5 mmol/m ² PLA
Wheat	protein yield	2.0 mmol/m ² PLA
Potato	tuber yield	3.8 mmol/m ² PLA
Tomato	fruit yield	2 mmol/m ² PLA
Tomato	fruit quality	3.8 mmol/m ² PLA

Source: CLRTAP, 2017a

Regarding trees, beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) and Norway spruce (*Picea abise*) were selected as the tree species for which the most comprehensive parameterization for POD is available. For them, the Y value is taken equal to 1 nmol/m² PLA s⁻¹ (i.e. per unit projected leaf area). For the details of POD_Y (and specifically POD₁SPEC as used in this report) calculation, see Vlasáková et al. (2023).

A uniform O₃ flux threshold of Y = 1 nmol/m²/s PLA (projected leaf area) was adopted for use in species-specific phytotoxic O₃ doses (POD_YSPEC) for all tree species at the O₃ Critical Levels workshop in Madrid, November 2016 (CLRTAP, 2017a), based on data and analyses presented in Büker et al. (2015). Anav et al. (2022) illustrated that POD₁ is the most reliable simple estimate of O₃ risk and recommended the use of this metric by policy makers as an air quality standard to protect vulnerable forest ecosystems in the future. The POD₁SPEC critical levels for forest trees were set to values for an acceptable biomass loss, as shown in Table 3.8.

Table 3.8 POD₁SPEC critical levels for trees as determined by CLRTAP

Tree	Effect parameter	POD ₁ SPEC critical level
Beech	4 % annual reduction of the whole tree biomass	5.2 mmol/m ² PLA
Spruce	2 % annual reduction of the whole tree biomass	9.2 mmol/m ² PLA

Source: CLRTAP, 2017a

The POD maps have been calculated based on the hourly ozone concentration maps, together with the meteorological and soil hydraulic properties data, based on the methodology described in Annex 1, Section A1.3. The ozone maps for each hour of the year 2022 have been constructed using the same methodology as the annual maps, i.e. the multiple linear regression followed by the kriging of its residuals (see Annex 1, Section A1.1) based on the measurement data, chemical transport model (CAM5-Ensemble forecast) output, altitude and the surface solar radiation. For details, see Annex 3, Section A3.3. The ozone maps have been calculated at the 2 km resolution, while the complete POD calculation has been executed in 0.1° x 0.1° resolution. The hourly ozone maps are created for rural areas only, based on rural background stations. The POD maps are therefore applicable to rural areas only. Next to this, it should be noted that in the POD calculations for wheat and potato, all growing areas are considered rain-fed (i.e. without irrigation), see Colette et al. (2018). Thus, the maps are directly applicable only for areas without irrigation. If applied for irrigated areas, the POD values for wheat and potato might be somewhat underestimated. On the other hand, no limitation of stomatal

conductance due to soil moisture can be assumed for tomato, since it is an irrigated horticultural crop (see Annex 1, Section A1.3).

Phytotoxic Ozone Dose maps

Maps 3.10 to 3.12 present the maps of Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_6) for wheat, potato and tomato and maps 3.13 and 3.14 present the maps of POD_1 for beech and spruce in 2022. Generally, high values of the POD can be found in different parts of Europe since the POD is dependent not only on ozone levels but also on the environmental conditions and plant phenology. The lowest levels of the POD usually occur in areas with lower ozone concentrations (e.g. northern European regions) and/or in areas where environmental conditions limit the ozone stomatal conductance (dry and warm areas, including parts of the southern, south-western and south-eastern Europe). On the other hand, higher POD values can occur in areas with lower ozone concentrations, but favourable conditions for the stomatal conductance.

Crops

The areas in the Map 3.10 with POD_6 values below the lowest CL for wheat (i.e. $1.3 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$ for grain yield) are marked in dark green and green.

Map 3.10 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_6) for wheat, rural map, 2022

The areas with POD_6 values in between CLs for grain yield and 1 000-grain weight (i.e. between $1.3 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$ and $1.5 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$) and in between CLs for 1 000-grain weight and protein yield (i.e. between $1.5 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$ and $2 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$) are marked in yellow and dark yellow, respectively. The areas with POD_6 values above the CL for protein yield of wheat (i.e. $2 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$) are marked in orange, red and dark red.

In 2022, POD_6 values for wheat above the highest CL (i.e. for protein yield) are found in northern Europe (parts of Denmark and a small area in the south of Sweden), central Europe (parts of Poland, Czechia, Austria, Switzerland, Hungary, Slovenia and large area of Germany), western Europe (parts of France and almost the entire area of Benelux countries) and in southern and south-eastern Europe (almost the entire area of Portugal, large area of Spain, parts of Italy, Greece and Türkiye). In addition,

the lower CLs for grain yield and 1 000-grain weight were exceeded in parts of central Europe (Germany, Czechia, Poland, Austria, Hungary, Slovenia), western Europe (France) and in parts of southern Europe (Portugal, Spain, Italy, smaller areas of the different Balkan countries and Türkiye).

Map 3.11 presents the map of POD₆ for potato in 2022. The areas with POD₆ values above the CL for tuber yield of potato (i.e. 3.8 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in yellow, dark yellow, orange, red and dark red. Areas below this CL are marked in green and dark green.

In 2022, POD₆ values for potatoes exceeded the CL for tuber yield across a large continuous area of central Europe, with the exception of several regions in northern Poland, Slovakia, Hungary, and relatively large areas of Austria and Switzerland. Regions with POD₆ values for potatoes higher than the CL for tuber yield were also found in western Europe (a large part of France and the Benelux countries), parts of southern Europe (some parts in north Portugal, smaller parts of the southern and western coast of Spain, parts of Italy excluding the north and south and parts of some Balkan states). The lowest POD₆ values for potatoes in 2022 were observed in northern Europe, as well as in parts of central, western, and southern Europe, and most of Türkiye. This heterogeneity in POD₆ values highlights their dependence on both ozone concentrations and meteorological conditions that determine stomatal conductance.

Map 3.11 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD₆) for potato, rural map, 2022

Map 3.12 presents the map of POD₆ for tomato in 2022. The areas with POD₆ values above the CL for fruit yield (i.e. 2 mmol/m² PLA) are marked in red and dark red, the areas with POD₆ values above the CL for fruit quality (i.e. 3.8 mmol/m² PLA) in dark red. The Modelling and Mapping Manual (CLRTAP, 2017a) defines the parameterization for tomato for the Mediterranean area. EU-27 agriculture statistics show that 64 % of tomato in 2022 was produced in Italy, Spain, Portugal, and Greece (EC, 2024). In the colder regions of Europe, tomato would be mostly grown in greenhouses where the methodology used to compute ozone concentrations and uptake is not applicable. For the purpose of completeness, the POD₆ has been modelled even for non-Mediterranean areas using the same parameterization (lighter colours in the Map 3.12).

Most of the Mediterranean areas showed the values of POD_6 for tomato below the CLs for tomato in 2022. POD_6 values above CL occurred mainly in small coastal areas of Portugal, southern France, Italy, Croatia, Albania, Greece, and Türkiye.

Map 3.12 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_6) for tomato, rural map, 2022

Trees

Map 3.13 shows the map of POD_1 for beech in 2022.

Map 3.13 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_1) for beech, rural map, 2022

The areas with POD_1 values below the CL for beech (i.e. $5.2 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$) are marked in dark green and green. The areas with POD_1 values above the CL for beech are marked in yellow, dark yellow, orange, red and dark red. Since no parametrization for beech in the Boreal, Arctic and Alpine $> 50^\circ$ biogeographical regions is available, these areas are marked in lighter colours.

The CL for beech was exceeded in almost the entire European mapped area, with the exception of large areas in Spain and Türkiye and many smaller areas throughout the mapped area (e.g. in southern France, parts of Sardinia and Sicily, Slovakia, Hungary, Serbia, Romania, Bulgaria, Northern Macedonia, Greece and Cyprus).

The highest levels of POD_1 for beech in 2022 are found in a large area of central Europe, partly in western Europe, in northern Europe (Denmark), parts of southern and south-eastern Europe (the north of Spain, parts of Italy, areas of the Balkan countries and north of Türkiye).

Map 3.14 presents the map of POD_1 for spruce in 2022. The areas with POD_1 values below the CL for spruce (i.e. $9.2 \text{ mmol/m}^2 \text{ PLA}$) are marked in dark green and green. The areas with POD_1 values above the CL for spruce are marked in yellow, dark yellow, orange, red and dark red. Since no parametrization for spruce in the Mediterranean, Anatolian and Black Sea biogeographical regions is available, this area is marked in lighter colours.

The CL for spruce has been exceeded almost throughout the entire mapped European area, with the exception of large areas in northern Europe and a large area in Romania extending into Bulgaria. However, many smaller areas with POD_1 values below CL can be found in almost every country in Europe. Nevertheless, according to CLRTAP (2020), the start of the growing season in northern Europe is earlier than the start of the growing season calculated by the current recommended latitude model (boreal region). As a result of this earlier start of the growing season, POD_1 values in northern Europe (boreal region) could be higher than those presented. Unfortunately, a better approach for determining the start of the growing season for spruce is not currently available in this region.

Map 3.14 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD_1) for spruce, rural map, 2022

4 NO₂ and NO_x

The methodology for creating the concentration maps follows the same principle as for the rest of pollutants: a linear regression model on the basis of European wide station measurement data, followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that regression model (residual kriging).

The map on NO₂ is based on an improved mapping methodology developed in Horálek et al. (2017b, 2018). The map layers are created for the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas separately on a grid at 1 km resolution. Subsequently, the urban background and urban traffic map layers are merged using the gridded road data into one urban map layer. This urban map layer is further combined with the rural map layer into the final NO₂ map using a population density grid at 1 km resolution. For details, see Annex 1, Section A1.1. Supplementary data used consist of chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude, Sentinel-5P satellite data, wind speed, population density and land cover indicators for rural areas; for urban background areas these are CTM output and temperature, altitude, Sentinel-5P satellite data, wind speed, population density and land cover indicators; for traffic areas the CTM output, altitude, and Sentinel-5P satellite data are used (Annex 3, Section A3.4). The final concentration map is presented at the 1 km grid resolution. Be it noted that this final map is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas (which are smoothed at this 1 km spatial resolution).

The map of the vegetation-related indicator NO_x annual average is created on a grid at 2 km resolution, based on rural background measurements only, as vegetation is considered not to be extensively present at urban and suburban areas. Hence, this map is applicable to rural areas only. The resolution is chosen equally to the one of the vegetation indicator for ozone.

The population exposure to NO₂ has been calculated based on the methodology described in Horálek et al. (2017b), i.e. according to Equation A1.6 of Annex 1. It has been calculated separately for urban areas directly influenced by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas, in order to better reflect the population exposed to traffic. Based on this, the different concentration levels in urban background and traffic areas inside the 1 km x 1 km grid cells are taken into account. Thus – like for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} – the population exposure refers not only to the rural and urban background areas, but to the urban traffic locations as well. However, it should be mentioned that only population density data at 1 km resolution has been used. This means that contrary to the concentration levels, the population density is constant within each 1 km grid cell. This shortcoming can increase the uncertainty of the population exposure results.

Annex 3 provides details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the maps, as well as the uncertainty analysis of the maps.

4.1 NO₂ – Annual mean

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets two limit values (LV) for NO₂ for the human health protection. The first one is an annual LV (ALV) at the level of 40 µg/m³. This is the same concentration level as recommended by the World Health Organization for the NO₂ annual average as the 2005 Air Quality Guideline level (WHO, 2005). Nevertheless, the current WHO Air Quality Guideline level for the NO₂ annual average is set to 10 µg/m³, as introduced in 2021 (WHO, 2021a). The second one is an hourly LV (HLV, 200 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 18 hours per year). Concentrations above the HLV were observed in 0.8 % (24 stations) of all reporting stations in 2022, mostly at urban traffic stations, see Targa et al. (2024). In view of this low number of exceedances, the short-term LV has not been included in the mapping procedures.

Concentration map

Map 4.1 presents the final combined concentration 1 km resolution map for the 2022 NO₂ annual average. According to Map 4.1, the areas where NO₂ concentrations were above the ALV of 40 µg/m³ include urbanized parts of some large cities, particularly Milan, Ankara and Istanbul, and some other smaller cities in Türkiye. Some other cities show NO₂ levels above 30 µg/m³, e.g. in France, Greece, Italy, Romania, Spain, and Türkiye. Most of the European area shows NO₂ levels below 10 µg/m³; a larger area with NO₂ concentrations between 10 and 20 µg/m³ is located in Türkiye. Some areas above 20 µg/m³ or 30 µg/m³ can be found in the Po Valley, the Benelux, the German Ruhr region, the Île de France region, around the national capitals or large cities in southern and south-eastern Europe, and in the Krakow – Katowice (PL) – Ostrava (CZ) industrial region.

It should be noted that the interpolated map is created at 1 km resolution only. Although the urban traffic map layer is used in the map creation, the traffic locations are smoothed in the 1 km resolution. Thus, the map as such refers to the rural and urban background situations only, while the concentrations above the NO₂ limit values occur mostly at local hotspots such as dense traffic locations and densely urbanised and industrialised areas. Such concentrations are mostly not visible in the 1 km resolution map.

The relative mean uncertainty of the NO₂ annual average map is 34 % for rural and 25 % for urban background areas (Annex 3, Section A3.4). This means slightly worse mapping uncertainty in rural areas compared to the quality objective for models of NO₂ annual average (i.e. 30 %) as set in the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

In order to provide more complete information of the air quality across Europe, the final combined map including the measurement data at stations is presented in Map A4.10 of Annex 4.

Map 4.1 Concentration map of NO₂ annual average, 2022

Map 4.2 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for NO₂ annual average. Orange to red areas show an increase of NO₂ concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease.

At the annual average NO₂ difference map the highest increases are observed in Türkiye. There are increases also in parts of southern and south-eastern Europe with the highest increases in Romania, parts of Italy (central and northern), Austria and Switzerland. A smaller increase is also observed in western and northern Europe, specifically in Ireland and in disconnected areas of the Baltic states. On the other hand, there are decreases in several countries, including the Benelux region, Germany, northern Italy, the Île-de-France region, some Balkan countries and around some of the biggest cities in Spain.

Map 4.2 Difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for NO₂ annual average

Population exposure

Table 4.1 and Figure 4.1 give the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes calculated on a grid of 1x1 km² resolution. Table 4.1 also presents the population-weighted concentration for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the whole mapping area.

It has been estimated that in 2022 almost 3 % of the considered European population including Türkiye and 0.2 % of the EU-27 population lived in areas with NO₂ annual average concentrations above the EU limit value of 40 µg/m³ (i.e. equivalent to the previous 2005 WHO AQG).

About 75 % of the considered European population including Türkiye and 71 % of the EU-27 population has been exposed to annual average concentrations above the current 2021 WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³ (WHO, 2021a).

No population has been exposed to concentrations above the ALV in 34 countries. In Poland, Romania, Italy, France, Cyprus and Greece up to 3 % of population has been exposed to concentrations above the limit value. In Türkiye, this is the case for 16 % of the population.

Table 4.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, NO₂ annual average, 2022

Country	ISO	Population (inhbs-1000)	NO ₂ — annual average, exposed population (%)						Population-weighted concentration		
			< 10	10-20	20-30	30-40	40-45	> 45	2022	5-year mean	Diff.
Albania	AL	2 794	34.3	55.2	10.6				12.4	14.4	-2.0
Andorra	AD	79	27.5	72.4	0.1				12.4	18.6	-6.3
Austria	AT	8 979	28.9	54.1	16.6	0.5			14.0	16.3	-2.3
Belgium	BE	11 618	8.0	75.2	15.7	1.1			15.7	18.0	-2.3
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA	3 271	25.4	61.6	13.1				13.9	14.2	-0.3
Bulgaria	BG	6 839	18.3	58.9	22.0	0.7			15.8	18.2	-2.4
Croatia	HR	3 862	33.0	51.2	14.5	1.3			13.3	13.9	-0.6
Cyprus	CY	1 288	10.2	9.1	72.2	5.8	2.6	0.0	24.0	21.5	2.4
Czechia	CZ	10 517	27.8	67.5	4.7				12.7	14.1	-1.4
Denmark (incl. Faroe Islands)	DK	5 926	82.6	17.2	0.3				7.3	8.5	-1.1
Estonia	EE	1 332	71.2	28.8					7.2	6.7	0.4
Finland	FI	5 548	73.8	26.2					7.5	7.6	-0.1
France (metropolitan)	FR	65 647	42.6	43.1	9.5	4.3	0.5	0.0	12.7	14.6	-1.9
Germany	DE	83 237	20.4	65.5	13.0	1.2			14.4	17.2	-2.8
Greece	GR	10 460	29.0	35.3	25.9	6.6	0.7	2.6	17.2	19.6	-2.4
Hungary	HU	9 689	19.8	62.5	15.0	2.7			14.6	16.3	-1.8
Iceland	IS	376	77.3	18.2	4.5				8.1	9.1	-0.9
Ireland	IE	5 060	57.6	39.2	3.2				9.2	9.3	-0.1
Italy	IT	59 030	13.6	49.8	28.9	7.2	0.5	0.0	18.2	19.5	-1.3
Latvia	LV	1 876	54.5	44.1	1.5				10.0	10.6	-0.6
Liechtenstein	LI	39	3.9	94.9	1.2				13.6	16.3	-2.7
Lithuania	LT	2 806	48.0	48.2	3.8				11.0	11.0	0.0
Luxembourg	LU	645	19.1	73.3	7.6				13.5	17.6	-4.0
Malta	MT	521	45.6	44.2	10.2				11.5	11.8	-0.3
Monaco	MC	37		98.0	2.0				17.2	22.4	-5.2
Montenegro	ME	618	21.8	78.0	0.2				12.2	13.6	-1.4
Netherlands	NL	17 591	6.6	77.0	16.4				16.1	18.2	-2.1
North Macedonia	MK	1 837	15.1	71.3	13.5				14.7	17.2	-2.5
Norway	NO	5 425	70.7	27.2	2.0				7.6	9.2	-1.5
Poland	PL	37 654	34.4	54.7	10.3	0.6	0.0		12.9	14.3	-1.3
Portugal (excl. Azores, Madeira)	PT	9 864	44.8	46.1	7.5	1.7			11.7	14.0	-2.2
Romania	RO	19 042	15.7	56.9	20.3	6.9	0.2		17.0	18.3	-1.3
San Marino	SM	34	17.2	78.1	4.7				12.9	14.3	-1.4
Serbia (incl. Kosovo)	RS	8 571	16.2	64.2	18.7	0.9			15.8	17.0	-1.3
Slovakia	SK	5 435	31.0	66.8	2.2				11.7	13.3	-1.6
Slovenia	SI	2 107	35.2	57.0	7.8				12.6	14.1	-1.5
Spain (excl. Canarias)	ES	45 181	26.3	46.5	19.8	7.4			15.9	17.8	-1.9
Sweden	SE	10 452	83.4	16.6	0.1				6.9	7.5	-0.6
Switzerland	CH	8 739	14.1	76.0	9.6	0.4			14.1	16.3	-2.2
Türkiye	TR	84 680	5.5	16.1	35.8	26.2	5.1	11.3	29.4	25.6	3.8
Total		558 706	25.1	47.9	17.9	6.5	0.9	1.7	16.5	17.4	-0.9
			73.1				2.6				
EU-27		442 153	28.6	52.9	15.0	3.3	0.2	0.1	14.4	16.2	-1.8
			81.4				0.2				
Northern Europe		33 742	74.3	24.8	0.9				7.7	8.5	-0.8
Western Europe		85 476	31.2	53.5	11.6	3.2	0.4	0.0	13.8	15.8	-2.1
Central Europe		166 396	24.7	62.8	11.5	0.9	0.0		13.8	16.0	-2.2
Southern Europe		141 577	23.9	46.9	22.5	6.2	0.3	0.2	16.3	18.0	-1.6
South-Eastern Europe		131 514	10.7	32.1	29.3	17.6	3.2	7.1	24.3	22.4	1.9
Kosovo	KS	1 774	19.6	73.9	6.6				13.9	15.8	-1.9
Serbia (excl. Kosovo)	RS-	6 797	15.4	61.7	21.9	1.1			16.2	17.3	-1.1

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure. 5-year mean, i.e. five-year mean 2017-2021. Diff., i.e. difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021.

The population-weighted concentration of the NO₂ annual mean has been estimated for 2022 at about 17 µg/m³ for total mapped area and 14 µg/m³ for the EU-27, which means a decrease of about 1 µg/m³ and 2 µg/m³ compared to the previous five-year mean, respectively. When assessing the change in individual countries, the steepest absolute decrease (apart from the microstate Andorra) was found in Luxembourg (4 µg/m³), and the highest increase was estimated in Türkiye (4 µg/m³).

Figure 4.1 Percentage of the population (%) exposed to different values of NO₂ annual average (µg/m³), 2022

Figure 4.2 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 1 µg/m³. One can see the highest population frequency for classes between 7 and 19 µg/m³, a continuous decline of population frequency for classes between 20 and 30 µg/m³ and continuous mild decline of population frequency for classes between 31 and 60 µg/m³.

Figure 4.2 Population exposure frequency distribution, NO₂ annual average, 2022. The 2021 WHO AQG level (10 µg/m³) is marked by the green line, the EU annual limit value and 2005 WHO AQG level (40 µg/m³ in both cases) are marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.23 % of population lived in areas with PM_{2.5} annual average concentrations between 65 and 103 µg/m³.

The boxplot showing for individual countries the NO₂ annual average concentrations to which the population per country was exposed in 2022 is presented in Summary, Figure S.1.

4.2 NO_x – Annual mean

Concentration map

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008) sets a critical level (CL) for the protection of vegetation for the NO_x annual mean at 30 µg/m³. According to this directive, the sampling points targeted at the protection of vegetation and natural ecosystems shall be in general sited more than 20 km away from agglomerations or more than 5 km away from other built-up areas. Thus, only the observations at rural background stations are used for the NO_x mapping and the resulting map is representative for rural areas only.

The number of NO_x measurement stations is limited. The mapping of the NO_x annual average has been therefore performed on the basis of an approach presented in Horálek et al. (2007). This approach derives additional pseudo NO_x annual mean concentrations from NO₂ annual mean measurement concentrations and increases as such the number and spatial coverage of NO_x ‘data points’, and applies these data to the NO_x mapping. Section A1.1 of Annex 1 provides some details.

Map 4.3 presents the concentration map of NO_x annual average. It concerns rural areas only, representing an indicator for vegetation exposure to NO_x.

Most of the European area shows NO_x levels below 20 µg/m³. However, in the Po Valley, part of the Netherlands and Belgium, the German Ruhr region and around some larger European cities (typically being the national capitals or large cities) NO_x concentrations above the CL are observed. Furthermore, around many other larger European cities concentrations above the CL are observed. These concentrations are expected to be the result of large emissions from transport in and around the cities, as well as energy production and industrial facilities taking place at these areas. These values above the CL would be relevant only for the so-called peri-urban vegetation where patches of agricultural land and of natural or planted vegetation can be found. On the contrary, low concentrations (below 10 µg/m³) are observed in large areas of most of mapped countries with the exception of Greece, Bulgaria and Türkiye.

Map 4.3 Concentration map of NO_x annual average, rural map, 2022

The relative mean uncertainty of this rural map is 50 %. This means worse mapping uncertainty compared to the quality objective for models of NO_x annual average (i.e. 30 %) as set in the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008). This higher relative uncertainty is highly influenced by the low concentration values of NO_x in most of the areas. The NO_x annual average rural map including the data measured at rural background stations is presented in Map A4.11 of Annex 4. The map illustrates the lack of the NO_x rural stations in the Balkan area.

Map 4.4 presents the difference between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for annual average for NO_x. Orange to red areas show an increase of NO_x concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease. The highest increases are observed in Türkiye, with increases also in the eastern regions of Bulgaria and Romania, and the islands of Sardinia, Corsica and Crete. Notable decreases are primarily observed in the Île-de-France region and Benelux, the Po Valley, parts of Germany, and southern Scandinavia. Other areas where NO_x concentrations decreased were identified in south-eastern European countries.

Map 4.4 Difference concentrations between 2022 and the five-year mean 2017-2021 for NO_x annual average

Vegetation exposure has not been calculated for NO_x, since values above the CL for protection of the vegetation would occur in limited vegetation areas only and, as such, is considered not to provide essential information from the European scale perspective. Furthermore, contrary to vegetation exposure to high ozone concentrations in Europe that leads to considerable damage, vegetation exposure to NO_x pollution is of minor importance in terms of actual impacts. On the other hand, NO_x concentrations contribute in part to the total N-deposition, which leads to acidifying and eutrophying effects on vegetation. These effects, especially eutrophication, are still very important in Europe (e.g. EMEP, 2020). However, these effects on vegetation cannot be expressed by an exposure to NO_x as many oxidized and reduced nitrogen compounds contribute to total atmospheric nitrogen deposition.

Concerning the potential exposure estimate of vegetation and natural ecosystems to NO_x there is an additional dilemma: which receptor types should be selected to estimate the exposure and CL exceedance of vegetation and natural ecosystems? An option would be the use of CLC classes (e.g. like

in Horálek et al., 2008); nevertheless, this classification is too general. Another option would be the NATURA 2000 database. However, that data source contains a wide series of receptor types, species and classes. Serious additional efforts would be needed to conclude on the most relevant set of receptors from the NATURA 2000 geographical database.

5 Benzo(a)pyrene

An annual average map for benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) has been produced and is presented in the regular mapping report for the third time. In agreement with the conclusions of Horálek et al. (2022b), it is labelled as an experimental map to indicate that it does not yet meet the same accuracy standards as the regularly produced maps of other pollutants.

The map of BaP is based on the mapping methodology developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2022b). The methodology for creating the concentration maps follows the same principle as for the rest of pollutants: a linear regression model based on European wide station measurement data, followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that regression model (residual kriging). The map layers are created for the rural and urban background areas separately on a grid at 1 km resolution. For details, see Annex 1, Section A1.1. Supplementary data used in the linear regression for rural areas consist of chemical transport model (CTM) output, altitude, temperature, wind speed and land cover; for urban background areas they are CTM output and temperature (Annex 3, Section A3.5). The final concentration map is presented at a 1 km grid resolution.

Due to the poor spatial coverage of the BaP measurement stations, so-called pseudo-BaP stations have also been used in addition. Pseudo-BaP data in locations with PM_{2.5} measurements (or with pseudo-PM_{2.5} data based on PM₁₀ measurements) and with no BaP measurements have been estimated based on the exponential regression of the observed BaP concentrations with the PM_{2.5} data, geographical coordinates and the land cover. Due to quite high uncertainty of the pseudo data, they are only used in areas with a lack of BaP measurements. Due to the serious lack of Turkish data, Türkiye is not included in the mapping area. Annex 3, Section A3.5 provides details on the regression and kriging parameters applied for deriving the BaP map, as well as the uncertainty analysis of this map.

The 2004 Ambient Air Quality Directive (EC, 2004) sets a target value for ambient air concentration of BaP, as a marker for the carcinogenic risk of PAHs in ambient air. The target value (TV) for BaP (measured in PM₁₀) is set to 1 ng/m³ as an annual mean.

Both the EU target value (1 ng/m³) and the estimated WHO reference level (RL, 0.12 ng/m³) are based on the WHO lung cancer unit risk for PAH mixtures and correspond to an additional lifetime cancer risk of approximately 9 cases and 1 case in 100 000 exposed individuals, respectively (WHO, 2021b).

5.1 Benzo(a)pyrene – Annual mean

Concentration map

Map 5.1 presents the final combined concentration 1 km resolution map for the 2022 BaP annual average. Red and purple areas indicate concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³.

The highest BaP concentrations are shown in Poland, the north-eastern part of Czechia and some populated locations in central and south-eastern Europe, northern Europe (mainly Lithuania, Latvia and towns and cities in Finland) and the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy. By contrast, western and southern Europe (except Italy) have low BaP values. Generally, lower levels of BaP concentrations in natural areas can be seen, compared with the other land cover types.

The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 map of BaP annual average is 146 % for rural and 80 % for urban areas and determined exclusively on the actual BaP measurement data points, i.e. not the pseudo stations (Annex 3, Section A3.5). This uncertainty is considerably high (especially in the rural areas) with respect to the quality objective for models for BaP annual average (i.e. 60 %) as set in the European directive (EC, 2004). The high uncertainty in the rural areas is probably highly affected (besides the low density of the rural stations) by the fact that stations classified as “rural background”

comprise both regional stations with low BaP values and stations located in villages, which are often highly influenced by local heating leading to high BaP concentrations.

Map 5.1 Concentration map of benzo(a)pyrene annual average, 2022, experimental map

Map 5.2 Difference concentrations between 2022 and the four-year mean 2018-2021 benzo(a)pyrene annual average

Map 5.2 presents the difference between 2022 and the four-year mean 2018-2021 for BaP annual average. Orange to red areas show an increase of NO₂ concentration in 2022, while blue areas show a decrease. Areas with the lowest decreases were found in Poland.

Population exposure

Table 5.1 gives the population frequency distribution for a limited number of exposure classes to BaP concentrations, as well as the population-weighted concentration. Due to the experimental character of the benzo(a)pyrene map and its high uncertainty, the population exposure is presented only for EU-27, for five European regions and for the total mapping area, not for individual countries.

Table 5.1 Population exposure and population-weighted concentration, benzo(a)pyrene annual average, 2022, based on the experimental map

Area	Population [inhbs·1000]	BaP – annual average, exposed population, 2022 [%]						Population-weighted concentration		
		< 0.12	0.12-0.4	0.4-0.6	0.6-1.0	1.0-1.5	> 1.5	2022	4-year mean	Diff.
Northern Europe	33 742	6.0	47.1	22.2	13.4	6.7	4.6	0.57	0.52	0.05
Western Europe	85 476	35.3	64.5	0.2	0.1			0.15	0.15	0.00
Central Europe	166 396	4.4	52.3	8.4	9.4	9.7	15.9	0.75	1.02	-0.27
Southern Europe	141 577	35.1	52.4	7.0	3.7	1.7	0.1	0.25	0.27	-0.03
South-Eastern Europe without Türkiye	46 834	1.5	11.5	16.0	39.2	13.9	18.0	1.12	1.34	-0.22
Total	474 026	18.9	49.9	8.3	9.4	5.8	7.8	0.52	0.64	-0.13
EU-27	442 153	19.6	51.5	8.3	8.8	5.2	6.7	0.48		

Note: The percentage value "0.0" indicates that an exposed population exists, but it is small and estimated to be less than 0.05 %. Empty cells mean no population in exposure.

Based on the experimental map, it is estimated that 14 % of the population living in the considered European area was exposed to concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³ in 2022. Further, it is estimated that about 81 % of the population living in the considered European area was exposed to concentrations above the WHO RL of 0.12 ng/m³. The population-weighted concentration of the BaP annual average for 2022 for the considered European countries is estimated to be about 0.5 ng/m³.

Figure 5.1 shows, for the whole mapped area, the population frequency distribution for exposure classes of 0.05 ng/m³. The highest population frequency is found for classes between 0.05 and 0.20 ng/m³. A quite continuous decline of population frequency is visible for classes above 0.20 ng/m³.

Figure 5.1 Population frequency distribution, benzo(a)pyrene annual average, 2022. The value 1.0 ng/m³ is marked by the red line

Note: Apart from the population distribution shown in the graph, it was estimated that 0.6 % of population lived in areas with BaP annual average concentrations between 3.5 and 11.7 ng/m³.

6 Accumulated risks

Although the spatial distributions of PM, NO₂ and ozone concentrations differ widely, the possibility of an accumulation of risk resulting from high exposures to all three pollutants cannot be excluded. The maps for the three most frequently exceeded EU standards (PM₁₀ daily limit value, O₃ target value and NO₂ annual limit value) have been combined, see Map 6.1.

Map 6.1 Exceedance of Health-Related Air Quality Standards, 2022

The combined population exposure shows the following results: out of the total population of 559 million in the mapped area, almost 7 % (38.3 million) people live in areas where two or three of these air quality standards are exceeded; 0.09 % (0.5 million) people live in areas where all three standards are exceeded. The worst situation in 2022 was observed in Greece, Türkiye and Italy (in particular the Po valley), where 0.6 %, 0.4 % and 0.3 % lived in areas where all three standards are exceeded, respectively.

7 Exposure trend estimates

This report has presented the 2022 interpolated maps for the PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, ozone and NO₂ human health related air pollution indicators (annual average and the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily means, annual average for PM_{2.5}, the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and SOMO10 for ozone, and the annual average for NO₂), as well as the BaP annual average experimental map, together with tables showing the frequency distribution of the estimated population exposures and the population-weighted concentration per country (apart from BaP), large European region, EU-27 and the total mapping area.

Furthermore, interpolated maps of ozone and NO_x vegetation related air pollution indicators have been produced. More specifically, these include maps of the ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests, and tables with the frequency distribution of estimated land area exposures and agricultural- and forest- weighted concentration per country, large region, EU-27 and the total mapping area. In addition, the maps of the Phytotoxic Ozone Dose (POD) for crops (wheat, potato and tomato) and trees (spruce and beech), and the NO_x annual average map have been produced, but without exposure estimates.

A mapping approach similar to previous years (Horálek et al., 2024 and references therein) based primarily on observational data has been used. With the interpolated air pollution maps and exposure estimates for the year 2022 completed, an eighteen-year overview of comparable exposure estimates has been obtained (with full time series coverage for PM₁₀ and four ozone indicators, with one year missing for PM_{2.5} and with four years missing for NO₂). In this chapter these multi-annual overviews of exposure estimates are provided for each of the indicators of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and ozone (except peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO10 and POD_y), including a brief trend analysis.

For the previous years, mapping results as presented in Horálek et al. (2024) and previous mapping reports have been used. Since 2017 results, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} maps have been prepared based on the updated method (Horálek et al., 2019). For comparability reasons, results for 2015-2019 (and partly also for 2005 and 2009) are presented in two variants for these pollutants, i.e. based on the old and the updated methodologies. Ozone maps based on the 1 km merging resolution as tested in Horálek et al. (2010) and routinely applied since 2008 results are used for the whole period, due to consistency. For the human health indicators, the exposure estimates are expressed, on one hand, as population-weighted concentration and, on the other hand, as percentage of population exposed to concentrations above the limit/target value. For the vegetation related indicators, the exposure estimates are expressed as the agricultural- and forest-weighted concentrations, as well as the agricultural or forest areas exposed to concentrations above defined thresholds.

It should be noted that the percentage of population, agricultural area, or forest area exposed is a less robust indicator compared to the population-weighted, agricultural-weighted, or forest-weighted concentration, as a small concentration increase (or decrease) may lead to a major increase (or decrease) of population, agricultural or forest area exposed. This is not the case when taking the population-weighted or agricultural/forest-weighted concentration as indicator. Therefore, the trend analysis is done based on the population-weighted, agricultural-weighted and forest-weighted concentrations only.

When thinking about a trend, the following should be taken into account: (i) the meteorologically induced variations, (ii) the uncertainties involved in the interpolation (Annex 3), and (iii) the year-to-year variation of the station density and their spatial distribution, which influence the interpolated maps. In addition, one should be aware of the fact that different trends in various parts of Europe may occur. However, bearing in mind these limitations here a trend analysis is provided for the period 2005-2022 on the population-, agricultural- and forest-weighted concentrations for the total mapping area.

For comparability reasons, in this chapter the results for the total mapped area do not include Türkiye, because 2016 was the first year for which the area of Türkiye was mapped. Next to this, the results for the total mapped area include United Kingdom in this chapter. For the 16-year time series 2005-2020, the overall exposure included the United Kingdom (see Horálek et al., 2023, and the references therein). Therefore, the overall exposure for the total area including the United Kingdom has been calculated also for 2021 and 2022. The relevant values were easily available, as the mapping domain includes the United Kingdom (see Section A1.1).

7.1 Human health PM₁₀ indicators

Table 7.1 summarises the average concentration to which the considered European population has been exposed to over the eighteen-year period 2005-2022 for both human health PM₁₀ indicators, expressed as the population-weighted concentration, and the percentage of population exposed to PM₁₀ concentrations above limit values (LV), i.e. the annual (ALV) and daily (DLV) limit value, respectively.

For the years 2012 and 2013 both the 36th highest value and the 90.4 percentile of daily mean(s) have been calculated. Their results demonstrate an underestimation of almost 1 µg/m³ at the 36th highest daily mean. One may conclude that this underestimation is caused by the fact that when calculating the 36th highest daily mean value there is no correction for the missing values at incomplete time series. Whereas the 90.4 percentile of daily means adjusts for such missing data.

As the PM₁₀ maps for 2022 (as presented in Chapter 2) have been constructed using the updated methodology as developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2019), the table presents the results for 2015-2019 (and 2005 and 2009, for annual average) both based on the updated and the old methodologies, for comparability reasons.

Table 7.1 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the PM₁₀ limit values (LV) for the protection of health for 2005 to 2022

PM ₁₀	meth.	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Annual Average																			
Pop.-weighted concentration [µg/m ³]	old	28.0	28.9	26.6	25.1	24.6	24.5	25.3	22.9	22.2	21.1	21.2	20.2	20.2	20.1	18.3			
	new	28.6				25.3						21.6	20.5	20.8	20.8	18.7	18.0	18.1	18.4
Pop. exposed > ALV (40 µg/m ³) [%]	old	13.3	10.9	7.1	5.9	6.0	5.2	7.2	3.4	2.6	2.0	0.6	1.7	2.9	2.1	0.3			
	new	11.5				6.2						0.7	1.7	3.3	2.4	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.3
36th Highest Daily Mean / 90.4 Percentile of Daily Means																			
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	36 th high.	old	47.4	48.3	44.7	41.9	41.6	42.0	44.9	40.0	38.6								
	90.4 perc.	old								40.8	39.4	37.1	36.9	35.7	36.1	34.5	32.1		
	90.4 perc.	new											37.5	36.1	37.0	35.4	32.8	31.5	31.1
Pop. exposed > DLV (50 µg/m ³) [%]	36 th high.	old	35.9	37.2	27.6	20.3	17.0	20.8	24.8	16.9	16.4								
	90.4 perc.	old								18.1	17.3	13.3	14.7	14.0	15.8	12.0	7.2		
	90.4 perc.	new										16.2	14.6	17.0	13.2	8.1	9.1	8.7	6.1

In 2022 the population exposed to annual mean concentrations of PM₁₀ above the limit value of 40 µg/m³ has been 0.3 % of the total population (calculated using the new methodology), which is (together with the year 2021) the lowest percentage in the eighteen years’ time series. Furthermore, it is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to an annual mean PM₁₀ concentration of 18 µg/m³, being (together with 2020 and 2021) the lowest value in the eighteen years’ time series. The comparison of results for 2015-2018 illustrates well that a clear decrease in the population-weighted concentration does not lead necessarily to a similar decrease in the percentage of population exposed to concentrations above a certain standard.

In the eighteen-year time series, the percentage of people living in areas with concentrations above the annual LV is lower in the latest ten years (2013-2022) than in the first eight years. The overall

picture of the population-weighted annual mean concentration of the whole considered mapping area (i.e. including United Kingdom and without Türkiye) demonstrates a downward trend of about -0.6 µg/m³ per year for the years 2005-2022, based on the old mapping method results for 2005-2019 and the new methodology for 2020-2022 (for trend estimation methodology, see Annex 1, Section A1.2). This trend is statistically significant (at the strongest level ***, i.e. 0.001) and expresses a mean decrease of 0.6 µg/m³ per year.

In 2022 about 6 % of the considered European population have lived in areas where concentrations have been above the PM₁₀ daily limit value (calculated using the 90.4 percentile and the new methodology), being the lowest of the eighteen-year period. The overall population-weighted concentration of the 90.4 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily means (formerly the 36th highest daily mean) is estimated to be about 31 µg/m³ in 2022 for the whole mapping area, which is (together with 2020 and 2021) the lowest of the eighteen years considered. This is the case even though the 36th highest daily means (i.e. possibly underestimated data if applied instead of the 90.4 percentiles, see above) have been used in the 2005-2011 calculations. The population-weighted concentrations of the whole considered mapping area show a statistically significant (at the strongest level ***, i.e. 0.001) downward trend of about -1.0 µg/m³ per year for the years 2005-2022, for the daily LV related indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means (formerly the 36th highest daily mean), as calculated based on the old mapping method results for 2005-2019 and the new methodology for 2020-2022.

7.2 Human health PM_{2.5} indicator

Table 7.2 summarises for human health PM_{2.5} indicator (annual average) the population-weighted concentration and the percentage of the considered European population exposed to PM_{2.5} concentrations above the EU LV for the years 2005 to 2022 (without 2006, for which neither a map nor a population exposure was prepared).

As in the case of PM₁₀, the PM_{2.5} maps for 2022 (as presented in Chapter 3) has been constructed using the updated methodology. The table presents the results for 2005, 2009 and 2015-2019 (all the years for which maps using both methods are available) both based on the updated and the old methodology, for comparability reasons.

Table 7.2 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the PM_{2.5} limit value (LV) for the protection of health for 2005 to 2022

PM _{2.5}	meth.	2005	2006	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###	###
Annual average																			
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	old	18.8	not mapped	16.2	16.4	16.2	16.9	17.8	15.7	15.3	14.1	14.2	13.4	13.6	13.2	11.6			
	new	19.0		16.6									14.3	13.6	13.8	13.5	11.8	11.1	11.2
Population exposed > LV (25 µg/m ³) [%]	old		not mapped	8.2	7.9	7.6	8.3	13.3	9.1	5.8	4.2	6.3	5.4	7.0	4.1	0.9			
	new	16.8		7.6									6.5	5.4	7.2	4.5	1.2	1.1	1.0

The percentage of population exposed in 2022 to annual mean concentrations of PM_{2.5} above the LV of 25 µg/m³ has been 0.6 %, which is the lowest value in the eighteen years’ time series. Furthermore, it is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to an annual mean PM_{2.5} concentration of 11 µg/m³ in 2022, being (together with 2020 and 2021) the lowest values in the time series.

The trend analysis of the population-weighted concentrations across the period 2005-2022 for the total mapping area has been executed, based on the old mapping method results for the period 2005-

2019 and the new method for 2020-2022. At European scale a statistical significant (at the level ***, i.e. 0.001) downward trend can be observed, estimated to be -0.5 µg/m³ per year.

7.3 Human health ozone indicators

Table 7.3 summarises the exposure levels of the considered European inhabitants in terms of population-weighted concentrations for two human health ozone indicators. Furthermore, it presents the percentage of considered European population exposed to concentrations above the target value (TV) threshold and above a level of 6 000 µg/m³·d for the SOMO35 for the years 2005 to 2022.

Table 7.3 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the target value (TV) threshold for the protection of health and a SOMO35 threshold of 6 000 µg/m³·d for 2005 to 2022

Ozone		2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
26th highest daily max. 8-h mean / 93.2 percentile of daily max. 8-h means																			
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	26 th high. 93.2 perc.	111.4	117.6	110.0	109.4	107.7	106.5	108.4	107.3	108.3									
Popul. exp. > TV (120 µg/m ³) [%]	26 th high. 93.2 perc.	29.5	49.8	24.9	13.6	14.9	15.8	15.0	19.0	15.0									
SOMO35																			
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³ ·d]		4622	5045	4291	4164	4233	3850	4318	4174	4089	3500	4312	3619	3890	4962	4478	3945	3563	4485
Pop. exp. > 6000 µg/m ³ ·d		26.8	27.1	26.3	17.0	23.2	15.9	22.0	23.2	18.8	9.4	22.2	11.7	19.1	31.3	20.0	8.6	10.6	15.3

For 2012 and 2013, both the 26th highest value and the 93.2nd percentile of maximum daily 8-hour mean(s) have been calculated. It demonstrates an underestimation of about 0.6 µg/m³ at the 26th maximum daily 8-hour mean, which is caused by the fact that when calculating this indicator there is no correction for the missing values in the incomplete measurement time series.

Using the 93.2 percentile of ozone maximum daily 8-hour means it is estimated that 16 % of the population have lived in 2022 in areas where concentrations were above the ozone target value (TV) threshold of 120 µg/m³, which is a medium value of the eighteen-year period. The overall population-weighted ozone concentration in terms of the 93.2 percentile maximum daily 8-hour means in the background areas is estimated at about 110 µg/m³ for the considered European population, which is slightly above a mean value of the whole eighteen-year period (it should be noted that for 2005-2011 the 26th highest value of the maximum daily eight-hour mean was considered instead).

Examining the time series for 2005-2022, it can be concluded that 2005, 2006, 2015 and 2018 are exceptional years with high ozone concentrations, leading to increased exposure levels compared to the other fourteen years. The years 2014, 2016, 2020 and 2021 show the lowest exposure levels in the eighteen years' time series for the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means.

The trend analysis of the population-weighted concentrations for the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means across the period 2005-2022 for the total considered mapping area does not estimate a statistically significant trend. The reason is the ozone variability, which higher values occurring with warm and dry summers.

A similar tendency is observed for SOMO35. In 2005-2007, a bit more than one-fourth of the population lived in areas where a level of 6 000 µg/m³·d ⁽⁶⁾ was exceeded, with the highest level in 2006. In the period of 2008-2019, it fluctuated from about 16 % to 23 % of the population, except 2014

⁽⁶⁾ Note that the 6 000 µg/m³·d does not represent a health-related legally binding 'threshold'. In this and previous papers it represents a somewhat arbitrarily chosen threshold to facilitate the discussion of the observed distributions of SOMO35 levels in their spatial and temporal context. For motivation of this choice, see Section 4.2.

with about 9 %, 2016 with about 12 %, and 2018 with about one-third of the population. Since 2020, it is below 16%, while 2022 shows the fifth lowest value in eighteen-year period. The population-weighted SOMO35 concentrations show the fourth highest value in 2022. Trend analysis on the population-weighted concentration for the total mapping area shows no trend for the period 2005-2022. The reason is the same as in the case of the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour means.

7.4 Vegetation related ozone indicators

Exposure indicators describing the agricultural and forest areas exposed to accumulated ozone concentrations above defined thresholds are summarised in Table 7.4. Those thresholds are the target value (TV) threshold of 18 000 µg/m³·h and the long-term objective (LTO) of 6 000 µg/m³·h for the AOT40 for vegetation, and the former reporting value (RV) of 20 000 µg/m³·h and the critical level (CL) of 10 000 µg/m³·h for the AOT40 for forests.

Table 7.4 Percentages of the considered European agricultural and forest area (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to ozone concentrations above the target value (TV) threshold and the long-term objective (LTO) for AOT40 for vegetation, and above critical level (CL) and reporting value (RV) for AOT40 for forests and agricultural- and forest-weighted concentrations for 2005 to 2022

Ozone	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
AOT40 for vegetation																		
Agr. area > TV (18 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	48.5	69.1	35.7	37.8	26.0	21.3	19.2	30.0	22.1	17.8	31.4	14.7	23.8	39.7	29.7	3.0	6.7	25.4
Agr. area > LTO (6 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	88.8	97.6	77.5	95.5	81.0	85.4	87.9	86.4	81.0	85.5	79.7	74.1	73.4	95.1	84.0	71.0	73.2	83.9
Agr.-weighted concentr. [µg/m ³ ·h]	17481	22344	14597	15214	13157	13310	13255	14041	12838	12427	14223	10942	11750	16311	13735	8544	10041	13423
AOT40 for forests																		
For. area > RV (20 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	59.1	69.4	48.4	50.2	49.2	49.3	53.0	47.2	44.1	37.7	52.4	41.9	38.9	56.1	51.4	34.4	29.9	46.2
For. area > CL (10 000 µg/m ³ ·h)	76.4	99.8	62.1	79.6	67.4	63.4	68.6	65.0	67.2	68.2	59.8	60.0	55.4	86.7	84.0	58.0	59.5	60.8
For.-weighted concentr. [µg/m ³ ·h]	25900	31154	23744	21951	23532	19625	21892	21580	21753	17124	21150	17573	16798	25397	22343	14584	15070	18386

In 2022, some 25 % of all agricultural land (crops) has been exposed to accumulated ozone concentrations (AOT40 for vegetation) above the target value (TV) threshold, which is in the half of the eighteen-year period. About 84 % of all agricultural land has been exposed to levels in excess of the long-term objective (LTO), which is in the half of the eighteen-year period, as well as the agricultural-weighted AOT40 concentration for 2022.

The trend analysis of the agricultural-weighted concentrations for the AOT40 for vegetation across the period 2005-2022 for the total considered mapping area does not estimate any statistically significant trend. The reason again is the ozone variability correlated with the variability of meteorology.

For the ozone indicator AOT40 for forests, the level of 20 000 µg/m³·h (earlier used reporting value, RV) has been exceeded in about 46 % of the considered European forest area in 2022, which is the seventh lowest value of the whole time series. The forest area exceeding the CL has been in 2022 about 61 %, which is the sixth lowest percentage of the eighteen-year period. The temporal pattern of the concentrations above the AOT40 for forests CL shows some similarity with those of the AOT40 for vegetation, despite their different definitions and receptors and their natural difference in area type characteristics and occurrence. Their annual variability is, however, heavily dependent on meteorological variability.

The trend analysis of the forest-weighted concentrations for the AOT40 for forests across the period 2005-2022 for the total considered mapping area shows no trend.

7.5 Human health NO₂ indicator

Table 7.5 summarises the development in exposure levels of the considered European population for the human health NO₂ indicator (annual average), in terms of population-weighted concentrations and percentage of population exposed to concentrations above the annual LV (40 µg/m³), for the years 2005, 2009, 2010 and 2013 to 2022, for which the maps based on the current methodology are available. The population-weighted concentration is presented additionally also for 2007, although based on different mapping methodology than the other years. This 2007 value is probably slightly underestimated; based on Horálek et al. (2017b), one can suppose the true value would be of about 1 % higher (i.e. it would be about 23.5 µg/m³).

Table 7.5 Population-weighted concentration and percentage of the considered European population (including United Kingdom, without Türkiye) exposed to concentrations above the NO₂ limit value (LV) of 40 µg/m³ for the protection of health for 2005 to 2022

NO ₂	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Annual average																		
Pop.-weighted conc. [µg/m ³]	23.3	not mapped	23.3	not mapped	22.1	22.1	not mapped		19.4	18.6	18.8	18.6	18.4	17.6	16.8	14.0	14.4	14.4
Pop. exp. > LV (40 µg/m ³) [%]	7.9				5.6	4.9			3.2	2.8	3.2	2.8	3.0	1.8	1.3	0.2	0.2	0.2

In 2022 the population exposed to NO₂ annual mean concentrations above the limit value of 40 µg/m³ has been 0.2 % of the total population, which is (together with 2020 and 2021) the lowest in the whole series. Furthermore, it is estimated that the considered European inhabitants have been exposed on average to an annual mean NO₂ concentration of 14 µg/m³, again the lowest in the whole series, together with 2020 and 2021.

Trend analysis on the population-weighted concentration for the total mapping area shows a downward trend of about -0.6 µg/m³ per year, for the period 2005-2022, which is statistically significant (at the highest level ***, i.e. 0.001).

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
ALV	Annual Limit Value	
AOT40	Accumulated Ozone exposure over a Threshold of 40 ppb (i.e. 80 µg/m ³) in a specific period	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF
AQ	Air Quality	
CL	Critical Level	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
CLC	CORINE Land Cover	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (Air Convention)	https://unece.org/environment-policy/air
CORINE	Co-ORDinated INformation on the Environment	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover
CTM	Chemical Transport Model	
CSI	Core Set of Indicators	https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims
Defra	United Kingdom Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs	
DLV	Daily Limit Value	
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	https://www.ecmwf.int/
EBAS	EMEP dataBASE	https://ebas.nilu.no/
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme	https://www.emep.int/
ETC/ACM	European Topic Centre on Air pollution and Climate change Mitigation	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
ETC/ATNI	European Topic Centre on Air pollution, Noise, Transport and Industrial pollution	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
ETC HE	European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs
EU	European Union	https://european-union.europa.eu
GMTED	Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data	
GRIP	Global Roads Inventory Dataset	
HLV	Hourly Limit Value	
ICP	International scientific Cooperative Programme	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/
ILV	Indicative Limit Value	
JRC	Joint Research Centre	https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/joint-research-centre_en

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
LV	Limit Value	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research	https://www.nilu.no/
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide	
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides	
O ₃	Ozone	
ORNL	Oak Ridge National Laboratory	https://www.ornl.gov/
PLA	Projected Leaf Area	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
PM ₁₀	Particulate Matter with a diameter of 10 micrometres or less	
PM _{2.5}	Particulate Matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometres or less	
POD ₆	Phytotoxic Ozone Doze above a threshold of 6 nmol/m ² PLA s ⁻¹	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
POD ₁	Phytotoxic Ozone Doze above a threshold of 1 nmol/m ² PLA s ⁻¹	https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation
R ²	Coefficient of determination	
RIMM	Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping	
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error	
SOMO10	Sum of Ozone Maximum daily 8-hour means Over 10 ppb (i.e. 20 µg/m ³)	
SOMO35	Sum of Ozone Maximum daily 8-hour means Over 35 ppb (i.e. 70 µg/m ³)	
TV	Target Value	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF
UN	United Nations	https://www.un.org
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe	https://unece.org/
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time	
WHO	World Health Organization	https://www.who.int/

References

- Alonso, R., et al., 2014, 'Drought stress does not protect *Quercus ilex* L. from ozone effects: results from a comparative study of two subspecies differing in ozone sensitivity', *Plant Biology* 16, pp. 375-384 (<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/plb.12073>) accessed 21 January 2021.
- Anav, A., et al., 2022, 'Legislative and functional aspects of different metrics used for ozone risk assessment to forests', *Environmental Pollution* 295(118690) (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.118690>) accessed 11 July 2022.
- Ashmore, M., et al., H., 2004, 'New directions: a new generation of ozone critical levels for the protection of vegetation in Europe', *Atmospheric Environment* 38, pp. 2213-2214 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2004.02.029>) accessed 20 November 2020.
- Büker, P., et al., 2015, 'New flux based dose-response relationships for ozone for European forest tree species', *Environmental Pollution* 206, pp. 163-174 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2015.06.033>) accessed 27 April 2022.
- CLRTAP, 2016, *Forest condition in Europe*, 2016 Technical Report of ICP Forests, UNECE Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (<https://www.icp-forests.org/pdf/TR2016.pdf>) accessed 19 November 2020.
- CLRTAP, 2017a, *Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads & levels. Chapter III: "Mapping Critical levels for Vegetation"*, UNECE Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (<https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/chapter-3-mapping-critical-levels-vegetation>) accessed 7 May 2021.
- CLRTAP, 2017b, *Scientific Background Document A of Chapter 3 of "Manual on methodologies and criteria for modelling and mapping critical loads and levels of air pollution effects, risks and trends"* (<https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/ScientificBackgroundDocumentAOct2018.pdf>) accessed 11 December 2020.
- CLRTAP, 2020, *Scientific Background Document B of Chapter 3 of "Manual on methodologies and criteria for modelling and mapping critical loads and levels of air pollution effects, risks and trends"* (<https://icpvegetation.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/Scientific%20Background%20document%20B%20June%202020.pdf>) accessed 11 December 2020.
- Colette, A., et al., 2018, *Long term evolution of the impacts of ozone air pollution on agricultural yields in Europe. A modelling analysis for the 1990-2010 period*, Eionet Report ETC/ACM 2018/15 (https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/eionet_rep_etcacm_2018_15_o3impacttrends) accessed 26 August 2020.
- Cressie, N., 1993, *Statistics for spatial data*, Wiley series, New York.
- Danielson, J. J. and Gesch, D. B., 2011, *Global multi-resolution terrain elevation data 2010 (GMTED2010)*, U.S. Geological Survey Open-File Report, pp. 2011-1073 (<https://pubs.er.usgs.gov/publication/ofr20111073>) accessed 19 November 2020.
- Defra, 2024, *UK Air information resource, Data archive*, UK Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs (<https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/>). Data extracted in April 2024.

De Leeuw, F., 2012, *AirBase: a valuable tool in air quality assessments at a European and local level*, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2012/4 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2012_4_airbase_aassessment) accessed 26 August 2020.

Denby, B., et al., 2008, 'Comparison of two data assimilation methods for assessing PM₁₀ exceedances on the European scale', *Atmospheric Environment* 42, pp. 7122-7134 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2008.05.058>) accessed 26 August 2020.

Denby, B., et al., 2011, *Mapping annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in Europe: application of pseudo PM_{2.5} station data*, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2011/5 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2011_5_spatialpm2-5mapping) accessed 26 August 2020.

De Smet, P., et al., 2011, *European air quality maps of ozone and PM₁₀ for 2008 and their uncertainty analysis*, ETC/ACC Technical Paper 2010/10 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacc_tp_2010_10_spatiaqmaps_2008) accessed 26 August 2020.

Deumier, J. M. and Hannon, C., 2010, 'La période d' initiation de la tubérisation: comment la repérer?' (in French), CNIPT (<http://www.cnipt.fr/wp-content/uploads/2013/10/Irrigation-juin-2010.pdf>) accessed 8 February 2021.

EC, 2002, *Directive 2002/3/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2002 relating to ozone in ambient air*, OJ L 67, 9.3.2002, p. 14–30 (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0003>) accessed 6 November 2024.

EC, 2004, *Directive 2004/107/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2004 relating to arsenic, cadmium, mercury, nickel and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in ambient air*, OJ L 23, 26.1.2005, p. 3-16 (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004L0107&from=EN>) accessed 10 June 2022.

EC, 2008, *Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe*, OJ L 152, 11.06.2008, p. 1-44 (<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:152:0001:0044:EN:PDF>) accessed 26 May 2021.

EC, 2024. *The tomato market in the EU: Vol. 1: Production statistics* (https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/markets/overviews/market-observatories/fruit-and-vegetables/tomatoes-statistics_en) accessed 19 June 2024.

ECMWF, 2023, *CAMS Regional: European air quality analysis and forecast data documentation* (<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/CAMS+Regional%3A+European+air+quality+analysis+and+forecast+data+documentation>) accessed 2 October 2023.

EEA, 2018, *Guide for EEA map layout. EEA operational guidelines*, January 2015, version 5 (https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gis/docs/GISguide_v5_EEA_Layout_for_map_production.pdf) accessed 26 August 2020.

EEA, 2019, *Healthy environment, healthy lives: how the environment influences health and well-being in Europe*, EEA Report 21/2019 (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/healthy-environment-healthy-lives>) accessed 2 June 2021.

EEA, 2021. Concept: P1Y-peakP6M-P8H-dmax in the aggregation process vocabulary (<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabularyconcept/aq/aggregationprocess/P1Y-peakP6M-P8H-dmax>) accessed 17 June 2024.

EEA, 2024a, *Air Quality e-Reporting. Air quality database* (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/aqereporting-8>). Data extracted in March 2024.

EEA, 2024b, *Exposure of Europe's ecosystems to ozone* (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/exposure-of-europes-ecosystems-to-ozone>) accessed 4 September 2024.

Emberson, L. D., et al., 2000, 'Modelling stomatal ozone flux across Europe', *Environmental Pollution* 109, pp. 403-413 ([https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491\(00\)00043-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491(00)00043-9)) accessed 26 May 2021.

EMEP, 2020, *Transboundary particular matter, photo-oxidants, acidifying and eutrophying components*, EMEP Report 1/2020 (https://emep.int/publ/reports/2020/EMEP_Status_Report_1_2020.pdf) accessed 22 January 2021.

EMEP, 2022, *Data of HMs and POPs for the EMEP region*, Meteorological Synthesizing Centre – East (MCS-E) (<https://www.msceast.org/index.php/pollution-assessment/emep-domain-menu/data-hm-pop-menu>) accessed 30 September 2022.

ESA, 2019, *Land cover classification gridded maps from 1992 to present derived from satellite observations* (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-land-cover>) accessed 17 February 2021.

EU, 2020, *Corine land cover 2018 (CLC2018) raster data*, 100x100m² gridded version 2020_20 (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover/clc2018>) accessed 19 November 2020.

Eurostat, 2020, *JRC-GEOSTAT 2018 grid dataset*, Population distribution dataset (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/gisco/geodata/reference-data/population-distribution-demography/geostat>) accessed 12 April 2024.

Eurostat, 2024, *Population on 1 January by age and sex* (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/DEMO_PJAN/default/table) accessed 12 April 2024.

Gilbert, R. O., 1987, *Statistical Methods for Environmental Pollution Monitoring*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York.

Gusev, A., et al., 2005, *Regional Multicompartment Model MSCE-POP*, EMEP/MSC-E Technical Report 5/2005 (http://www.msceast.org/reports/5_2005.pdf) accessed 9 December 2021.

Gusev, A., et al., 2022, *EURODELTA-Carb exercise: Intercomparison of modelled estimates of benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) in Europe*, HARMO 2022 conference proceedings (https://www.harmo.org/Conferences/Proceedings/Aveiro/publishedSections/00488_107_h21-168-alexey-gusev.pdf) accessed 6 September 2023.

Haberle, J. and Svoboda, P., 2015, 'Calculation of available water supply in crop root zone and the water balance of crops', *Contributions to Geophysics and Geodesy* 45, pp. 285-298 (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/293194127_Calculation_of_available_water_supply_in_crop_root_zone_and_the_water_balance_of_crops) accessed 21 January 2021.

Horálek, J., et al., 2007, *Spatial mapping of air quality for European scale assessment*, ETC/ACC Technical paper 2006/6 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacc_techpaper_2006_6_spat_aq) accessed 26 August 2020.

Horálek, J., et al., 2008, *European air quality maps for 2005 including uncertainty analysis*, ETC/ACC Technical paper 2007/7 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacc_tp_2007_7_spatqmaps_ann_interp) accessed 26 August 2020.

Horálek, J., et al., 2010, *Methodological improvements on interpolating European air quality maps*, ETC/ACC Technical Paper 2009/16 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacc_tp_2009_16_improv_spatqmapping) accessed 26 August 2020.

Horálek, J., et al., 2016, *Application of FAIRMODE Delta tool to evaluate interpolated European air quality maps for 2012*, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2015/2 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2015_2_delta_evaluation_aqmaps2012) accessed 26 August 2020.

Horálek, J., et al., 2017a, *European air quality maps for 2014*, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2016/6 (https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2016_6_aqmaps2014) accessed 30 September 2022.

Horálek, J., et al., 2017b, *Inclusion of land cover and traffic data in NO₂ mapping methodology*, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2016/12 (http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2016_12_lc_and_traffic_data_in_no2_mapping) accessed 27 May 2021.

Horálek, J., et al., 2018, *Satellite data inclusion and kernel based potential improvements in NO₂ mapping*, ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2017/14 (www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2017_14_improved_aq_no2mapping) accessed 27 May 2021.

Horálek, J., et al., 2019, *Land cover and traffic data inclusion in PM mapping*, Eionet Report ETC/ACM 2018/18 (<http://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etc-acm-report-18-2018-land-cover-and-traffic-data-inclusion-in-pm-mapping>) accessed 27 May 2021.

Horálek, J., et al., 2021, *Potential use of CAMS modelling results in air quality mapping under ETC/ATNI*, Eionet Report ETC/ATNI 2019/17 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4627762>) accessed 15 June 2021.

Horálek, J., et al., 2022a, *Air quality evolution and trends in Europe in 2005-2019 based on spatial maps*, Eionet Report ETC/ATNI 2021/11 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6586861>) accessed 15 October 2024.

Horálek, J., et al., 2022b, *Benzo(a)pyrene (BaP) annual mapping*, Eionet Report ETC/ATNI 2021/18 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5898376>) accessed 26 August 2022.

Horálek, J., et al., 2024, *Air quality maps of EEA member and cooperating countries for 2021*, Eionet Report ETC HE 2023/3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10589987>) accessed 17 September 2024.

Jarvis, P. G., 1976, 'The interpretation of the variation in leaf water potential and stomatal conductance found in canopies in the field', *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London, Series B: Biological Sciences* 273, pp. 593-610 (<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.1976.0035>) accessed 26 May 2021.

JRC, 2016, *Maps of indicators of soil hydraulic properties for Europe*, dataset/maps downloaded from the European Soil Data Centre (<http://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/maps-indicators-soil-hydraulic-properties-europe>) accessed 8 December 2020.

JRC, 2023, *GHS-POP R2023A - GHS population grid multitemporal (1975-2030)* (<https://doi.org/10.2905/2FF68A52-5B5B-4A22-8F40-C41DA8332CFE>) accessed 12 April 2024.

Krupa, S., et al., 2000, 'Ambient ozone and plant health', *Plant Disease* 85, pp. 4-12 (<https://apsjournals.apsnet.org/doi/pdf/10.1094/pdis.2001.85.1.4>) accessed 8 December 2020.

Kuenen, J., et al., 2021, *Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service regional emissions version 4.2 (CAM5-REG-v4.2)* Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service [publisher] ECCAD [distributor], (<https://doi.org/10.24380/0vzb-a387>) accessed 6 August 2022.

LMD, INERIS, LISA, 2020, *CHIMERE Chemistry-Transport Model (version 2020r1) documentation*, pp. 161–162 (https://www.lmd.polytechnique.fr/chimere/docs/CHIMEREdoc_v2020r1.pdf) accessed 17 September 2024.

MDA, 2015, *World Land Cover at 30m resolution from MDAUS BaseVue 2013* (<https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=1770449f11df418db482a14df4ac26eb>) accessed 17 February 2021.

Meijer, J. R., et al., 2018, 'Global patterns of current and future road infrastructure', *Environmental Research Letters* 13, 0640 (<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabd42>) accessed 10 June 2019.

METEO FRANCE, et al., 2023, *CAMS European air quality forecasts, ENSEMBLE data. Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAM5) Atmosphere Data Store (ADS)* (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts?tab=overview>) accessed on 2 October 2023.

Mills, G., et al., 2011, 'New stomatal flux-based critical levels for ozone effects on vegetation', *Atmospheric Environment* 45, pp. 5064-5068 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2011.06.009>) accessed 19 November 2020.

NILU, 2024, *EBAS, database of atmospheric chemical composition and physical properties* (<http://ebas-data.nilu.no>). Data extracted in April 2024.

Pedersen, S. M., et al., 2005, *Potato production in Europe - a gross margin analysis*, University of Copenhagen, FOI Working Paper Vol. 2005 No. 5, pp. 1-39 (<https://curis.ku.dk/ws/files/135440168/5.pdf>) accessed 26 May 2021.

Pleijel, H., et al., 2007, 'Ozone risk assessment for agricultural crops in Europe: Further development of stomatal flux and flux-response relationships for European wheat and potato', *Atmospheric Environment* 41, pp.3022-3040 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2006.12.002>) accessed 8 December 2020.

Reich, P. B., 1987, 'Quantifying plant response to ozone: a unifying theory', *Tree Physiology* 3, pp. 63-91 (<https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/3.1.63>) accessed 19 November 2020.

Simpson, D., et al., 2012, 'The EMEP MSC-W chemical transport model – technical description', *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 12, pp. 7825-7865 (<https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-12-7825-2012>) accessed 26 August 2020.

Targa, J., et al., 2024, *Status report of air quality in Europe for year 2022, using validated data*, Eionet Report ETC HE 2024/3 (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2024-3-status-report-of-air-quality-in-europe-for-year-2022-using-validated-data>) accessed 28 August 2024.

UN, 2024, *World Population Prospects 2024*, United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (<https://population.un.org/wpp/Download/Standard/MostUsed>) accessed 4 September 2024.

van Geffen, J., et al., 2019, 'TROPOMI ATBD of the total and tropospheric NO₂ data products', KNMI (<https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/247904/2476257/Sentinel-5P-TROPOMI-ATBD-NO2-data-products>) accessed 30 August 2021.

van Geffen, J., et al., 2020, 'S5P TROPOMI NO₂ slant column retrieval: Method, stability, uncertainties and comparisons with OMI', *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques* 13, pp. 1315–1335 (<https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-1315-2020>) accessed 30 August 2021.

Veefkind, J. P., et al., 2012. 'TROPOMI on the ESA Sentinel-5 Precursor: A GMES mission for global observations of the atmospheric composition for climate, air quality and ozone layer applications', *Remote Sensing of Environment* 120, pp. 70–83 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2011.09.027>) accessed 30 August 2021.

Vivanco, M. G., et al., 2024, *Evaluación de la calidad del aire en España mediante modelización combinada con mediciones. Preevaluación año 2023. Protocolo de Actuación MITERD-CIEMAT (2021-2024). Unidad de Modelización Atmosférica. CIEMAT, Ref. 5/2024.*

Vlasáková, L., et al., 2023. *Evaluation of European-wide map creation of flux-based ozone indicator POD for selected tree species*, Eionet Report ETC HE 2022/23 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10688319>) accessed 17 September 2024.

WHO, 2005, *WHO Air quality guidelines for particulate matters, ozone, nitrogen dioxide and sulphur dioxide, Global update 2005*, World Health Organization (<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/107823>) accessed 16 November 2022.

WHO, 2013, *Review of evidence on health aspects of air pollution: REVIHAAP project: technical report*, World Health Organization (<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/341712>) accessed 16 November 2022.

WHO, 2021a, *WHO global air quality guidelines: particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide*, World Health Organization (<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/345329>) accessed 10 December 2021.

WHO, 2021b, *Human health effects of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as ambient air pollutants* (<https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289056533>) accessed 22 September 2022.

Annex 1 Methodology

A1.1 Mapping methodology

Previous mapping reports like Horálek et al. (2007, 2010, 2017b, 2018, 2019, 2022b), De Smet et al. (2011), Denby et al. (2011) discuss methodological developments and details on spatial interpolations and their uncertainties of air quality maps. No changes took place in the mapping methodology with respect to the preceding report (Horálek et al., 2024). This annex summarizes the currently applied method for all the considered indicators. The mapping method has been evaluated with the FAIRMODE Delta tool in Horálek et al. (2016). The method is called the *Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping* (RIMM).

Pseudo PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP station data estimation

To supplement PM_{2.5} measurement data, in the mapping procedure data from so-called pseudo PM_{2.5} stations are also used. These data are the estimates of PM_{2.5} concentrations at the locations of PM₁₀ stations with no PM_{2.5} measurement. These estimates are based on PM₁₀ measurement data and different supplementary data, using linear regression:

$$\hat{Z}_{PM_{2.5}}(s) = c + b \cdot Z_{PM_{10}}(s) + a_1 X_1(s) + a_2 X_2(s) + \dots + a_n X_n(s) \quad (A1.1)$$

where $\hat{Z}_{PM_{2.5}}(s)$ is the estimated value of PM_{2.5} at the station s ,
 $Z_{PM_{10}}(s)$ is the measurement value of PM₁₀ at the station s ,
 c, b, a_1, \dots, a_n are the parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the points of stations with both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measurements,
 $X_1(s), \dots, X_n(s)$ are the values of other supplementary variables at the station s ,
 n is the number of other supplementary variables used in the linear regression.

When applying this estimation method, all background stations (either classified as rural, urban or suburban) are handled together for estimating PM_{2.5} values at background pseudo stations. For details, see Denby et al. (2011). For estimating PM_{2.5} values at urban traffic pseudo stations, Equation A1.1 is applied for the urban traffic stations. For details, see by Horálek et al. (2019).

To supplement NO_x measurement data, NO_x values are estimated at locations of NO₂ stations with no NO_x data. The estimates are calculated similarly as in Horálek et al. (2007), using regression:

$$\hat{Z}_{NO_x}(s) = a_1 Z_{NO_2}(s)^2 + a_2 Z_{NO_2}(s) + c \quad (A1.2)$$

where $\hat{Z}_{NO_x}(s)$ is the estimated value of NO_x at the station s ,
 $Z_{NO_2}(s)$ is the measurement value of NO₂ at the station s ,
 a_1, a_2, c are the parameters of the regression calculated based on the data at the points of measuring stations with both NO_x and NO₂ measurements.

To supplement BaP measurement data, BaP concentrations are estimated at the locations with PM_{2.5} data with no BaP measurements. These estimates are based on PM_{2.5} measurement data (or PM_{2.5} pseudo stations data) and different supplementary data, using exponential regression:

$$\hat{Z}_{BaP}(s) = \exp(c + b \cdot Z_{PM_{2.5}}(s) + a_1 X_1(s) + a_2 X_2(s) + \dots + a_n X_n(s)) \quad (A1.3)$$

where $\hat{Z}_{BaP}(s)$ is the estimated value of BaP at the station s ,
 $Z_{PM_{2.5}}(s)$ is the measurement (or estimated) value of PM_{2.5} at the station s ,

c, b, a_1, \dots, a_n are the parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the locations of stations with both BaP and PM_{2.5} measurements,
 $X_1(s), \dots, X_n(s)$ are the values of other supplementary variables at the station s ,
 n is the number of other supplementary variables used in the linear regression.

When applying this estimation, all background stations (either classified as rural, urban or suburban) are handled together for estimating BaP values at background pseudo stations. The reason for introducing the exponential regression is the exponential relation between BaP and PM_{2.5}. In agreement with Horálek et al. (2022b), the pseudo BaP data are only calculated in areas with a lack of BaP data (see Annex 3, Section A3.5). The estimates are calculated primarily for the locations with PM_{2.5} measured data with no BaP measurements. In the limited areas with a lack of both BaP and PM_{2.5} measurements, pseudo PM_{2.5} data (see Eq. A1.1) calculated for locations with PM₁₀ measurements are used.

Interpolation

The mapping method used is a linear regression model followed by kriging of the residuals produced from that model (residual kriging). Interpolation is therefore carried out according to the relation:

$$\hat{Z}(s_0) = c + a_1X_1(s_0) + a_2X_2(s_0) + \dots + a_nX_n(s_0) + \hat{R}(s_i) \quad (\text{A1.4})$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_0)$ is the estimated value of the air pollution indicator at the point s_0 ,
 $X_1(s_0), X_2(s_0), \dots, X_n(s_0)$ are the n individual supplementary variables at the point s_0 ,
 c, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are the $n+1$ parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the measurement points,
 $\hat{R}(s_i)$ is the spatial interpolation of the residuals of the linear regression model at the point s_0 calculated based on the residuals at the measurement points.

For different pollutants and area types (rural, urban background, and in the case of PM and NO₂, also urban traffic), different supplementary data are used, depending on their improvement to the fit of the regression. Ordinary kriging is used to interpolate the residuals:

$$\hat{R}(s_i) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i R(s_i), \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i = 1 \quad (\text{A1.4a})$$

where $R(s_i)$ are the residuals in the points of the measuring stations s_i ,
 $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N$ are the weights estimated based on the variogram,
 N is the number of the stations used in the interpolation.

The variogram (as a measure of a spatial correlation) is estimated using a spherical function (with parameters nugget, sill, range). For details, see Horálek et al. (2007), Section 2.3.5 and Cressie (1993).

For PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP, both measurement data and the estimated data from the pseudo stations are used. For the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} indicators, prior to linear regression and interpolation, a logarithmic transformation is applied to measurement and modelling concentrations. After interpolation, a back-transformation is applied. For details, see De Smet et al. (2011) and Denby et al. (2008).

For the vegetation-related indicators (AOT40 for vegetation and forests, POD, and NO_x) only rural maps are constructed based on rural background stations, based on the assumption that no vegetation is located in urban areas. For the health-related indicators, the rural and urban background map layers (and for PM and NO₂ also urban traffic map layer) are constructed separately and then merged.

Merging of rural and urban background (and urban traffic) map layers

Health related indicator map layers are created for rural and urban background areas on a grid at resolution of 1 km (for PM, NO₂ and BaP) and 10 km (for ozone), and for urban traffic areas at 1 km (for PM and NO₂). The rural background map layer is based on rural background stations, the urban background map layer on urban and suburban background stations and the potential urban traffic map layer is based on urban and suburban traffic stations. The separate treatment of the map layers is based on the assumption that the estimated rural values are lower (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and BaP) or higher (ozone) than the estimated urban background map values. In the limited areas where this criterion does not hold, a joint urban/rural map layer (created using all background stations regardless of their type) is used, as long as its value lies in between the rural and urban background map value. Thus, the adjusted rural and urban background map layers are calculated and further used. For details, see De Smet et al. (2011).

Subsequently, the separate map layers are merged into one combined final map at 1 km resolution, according to

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{Z}_F(s_0) &= (1 - w_U(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_R(s_0) + w_U(s_0) \cdot \left((1 - w_T(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) + w_T(s_0) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) \right) \\ &\quad \text{for PM}_{10}, \text{PM}_{2.5}, \text{ and NO}_2 \\ &= (1 - w_U(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_R(s_0) + w_U(s_0) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \text{ for ozone and BaP} \quad (\text{A1.5})\end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{Z}_F(s_0)$ is the resulting estimated concentration value in a grid cell s_0 for the final map,
 $\hat{Z}_R(s_0)$ is the estimated value in a grid cell s_0 for the rural background map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0)$ is the estimated value in a grid cell s_0 for the urban background map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0)$ is the estimated value in a grid cell s_0 for the urban traffic map layer,
 $w_U(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of the urban character of the a grid cell s_0 ,
 $w_T(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of areas exposed to traffic air quality in a grid cell s_0 .

The weight $w_U(s_0)$ is based on the population density grid, while $w_T(s_0)$ is based on the buffers around the roads. For further details, see Horálek et al. (2017b).

In all calculations and map presentations the EEA standard projection ETRS89-LAEA5210 (also known as ETRS89 / LAEA Europe, see www.epsg-registry.org) is used. The interpolation and mapping domain consists of the areas of all EEA member and cooperating countries, and other microstates, as far as they fall within the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018). Due to the interpolation methodology, the interpolation and mapping domain also includes the area of the United Kingdom. However, although they have been calculated, the results for the United Kingdom are not presented in this report, after this country left the EU.

A1.2 Calculation of population and vegetation exposure

Population and vegetation exposure estimates are based on the interpolated concentration maps, population density data and land cover data.

Population exposure

Population exposure is calculated for individual countries (apart from BaP), for large regions, for EU-27 and for the whole mapping area. For ozone and BaP, it is calculated from the air quality maps and population density data, both at 1 km resolution. For each concentration class, the total population per country as well as the European-wide total is determined. For PM and NO₂, the population exposure is calculated separately for areas where the air quality is considered to be directly influenced

by traffic and for the background (both rural and urban) areas. For each concentration class ‘j’, the percentage population per country as well as the European-wide total is determined according to:

$$P_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{Bij} (1-w_U(i)w_T(i))p_i + \sum_{i=1}^N I_{Tij}w_U(i)w_T(i)p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{A1.6})$$

where

- P_j is the percentage population living in areas of the j -th concentration class in either the country or in Europe as a whole,
- p_i is the population in the i -th grid cell,
- I_{Bij} is the Boolean 0-1 indicator showing whether the background air quality concentration (estimated by the combined rural/urban background map layer) in the i -th grid cell is within the j -th concentration class ($I_{Bij} = 1$), or not ($I_{Bij} = 0$),
- I_{Tij} is the Boolean 0-1 indicator showing whether the traffic air quality concentration in the i -th grid cell is within the j -th concentration class ($I_{Tij} = 1$), or not ($I_{Tij} = 0$), $w_U(s_0)$ is the weight representing ratio of the urban character of the a grid cell s_0 ,
- $w_U(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of the urban character of the a grid cell s_0 ,
- $w_T(s_0)$ is the weight representing ratio of areas exposed to traffic air quality in a grid cell s_0 .
- N is the number of grid cells in the country, in the region or in the whole mapped area.

In addition, the exposure for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and the whole area is expressed also as the population-weighted concentration, i.e. the average concentration weighted according to the population in a 1 km x 1 km grid cell:

$$\hat{c} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N c_i p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i} \quad (\text{A1.7})$$

where

- \hat{c} is the population-weighted average concentration in the country, large region, EU-27 or in the whole mapping area,
- p_i is the population in the i^{th} grid cell,
- c_i is the concentration in the i^{th} grid cell (based on the final merged map),
- N is the number of grid cells in the country or in Europe as a whole.

Vegetation exposure

Vegetation exposure for individual countries, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapping area is calculated based on the air quality maps and land cover data, both in the 2 km resolution grid. For each concentration class, the total agricultural and forest area per country as well as European-wide is determined.

Next to this, per-country and European-wide exposure are expressed as the agricultural- and forest-weighted concentration, i.e. the average concentration weighted according to the agricultural and forest area in a 1 km x 1 km grid cell, similarly like in Eq. A1.7.

Estimation of trends

For detecting and estimating the trends in time series of annual values of population exposure, the non-parametric Mann-Kendall’s test for testing the presence of the monotonic increasing or decreasing trend is used. Next to that, the non-parametric Sen’s method for estimating the slope of a linear trend is executed. For details, see Gilbert (1987). The significance of the Mann-Kendal test is shown by the usual way, i.e. + for 0.1, * for 0.05, ** for 0.01, and *** for 0.001.

Geographical distribution of considered countries to large regions for use in the assessment

The population and vegetation exposure and population-, agricultural- and forest-weighted concentration is presented, apart from the individual countries, the EU-27 and the whole mapped area, also in five large European regions. For this purpose, the countries have been grouped into five large European regions as follows. See also Map A1.1. Note that the designation of the large regions is intended primarily for the assessments of the mapping reports and does not necessarily follow common geographic or geopolitical terms.

- 1) Northern Europe (N): Denmark (including Faroes), Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden;
- 2) Western Europe (W): Belgium, France north of 45°, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands;
- 3) Central Europe (C): Austria, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Liechtenstein, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland;
- 4) Southern Europe (S): Andorra, Cyprus, France south of 45°, Greece, Italy, Malta, Monaco, Portugal, San Marino, Spain;
- 5) South-eastern Europe (SE): Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia including Kosovo under the UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Türkiye.

Map A1.1 Five large European regions

A1.3 Phytotoxic Ozone Dose above a threshold flux Y (POD_Y) calculation

The calculation of the phytotoxic ozone dose above a threshold Y (POD_Y) as described below follows the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads & levels of the Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution Convention (CLRTAP) in its most recent available revision (CLRTAP, 2017a), including some specifications presented in the Scientific background documents of this manual (CLRTAP, 2017b, 2020), as prepared by the International scientific Cooperative Programme

on effects of air pollution on natural vegetation and crops of the Working Group on Effects of the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation). The steps to be taken are presented in Table A1.1.

Table A1.1 Steps to calculate POD_Y of flux-based critical levels

1	Decide on the species and biogeographical region(s) to be included.
2	Obtain the ozone concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period.
3	Calculate the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto}).
4	Model the hourly stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto}).
5	Calculation of POD_Y from F_{sto} .

Source: CLRTAP, 2017a.

The cumulative stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) are calculated over the course of the growing season based on ambient ozone concentration and stomatal conductance (g_{sto}) to ozone. g_{sto} is calculated using a multiplicative stomatal conductance model proposed by Jarvis (1976) and modified by Emberson et al. (2000) as a function of species-specific maximum g_{sto} (expressed on a single leaf-area basis), phenology, and prevailing environmental conditions (photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD)), air temperature, vapour pressure deficit (VPD), and soil moisture.

Hourly averaged stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a threshold Y (expressed in $mmol/m^2$ PLA h^{-1}) are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period during daylight hours, in order to get the phytotoxic ozone dose above the threshold Y (POD_Y).

Crops

For the wheat as for other crop species, the Y value is taken equal to $6 \text{ nmol}/m^2 \text{ PLA } s^{-1}$. Although several POD indicators are proposed in CLRTAP (2017a), POD_6 is recommended for wheat, as the hourly averaged stomatal ozone fluxes above a value of 6 are more relevant for that crop. For potato and tomato, POD_6 is also recommended. Two POD_6 versions are available in CLRTAP (2017a): POD_6IAM (which is a simplified version recommended for Integrated Assessment Modelling) and POD_6SPEC (which is specific to a given specie). Here, POD_6SPEC was preferred and used, in agreement with Colette et al. (2018).

Obtaining the ozone concentrations at the top of the canopy for the species or vegetation-specific accumulation period

The ozone concentration at the top of the canopy ($nmol/m^3$) in the given hour H is calculated according to

$$c(z_1) = c(z_m, O_3) * \left[1 - \frac{R_a(z_{tgt}, z_m, O_3)}{R_a(d+z_0, z_m, O_3) + R_b + R_{surf}} \right] \quad (A1.8)$$

where $c(z_1)$ is ozone concentration at the top of the canopy,
 $c(z_m, O_3)$ is the ozone concentration measured at the height z_m ,
 $R_a(x, y)$ is the aerodynamic resistance between the height of y and the height of x ,
 R_b is the resistance to ozone diffusion in the laminar sub-layer,
 R_{surf} is the overall resistance to ozone deposition to the underlying surfaces,

⁽⁷⁾ PLA, or the projected leaf area, is the total area of the sides of the leaves that are projected towards the sun. PLA is different to the total leaf area, which accounts for both sides of the leaves.

while $R_a(z_{tgt}, z_{m,O3}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot u^*} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{z_{tgt}-d} \right) - \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{L} \right) + \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{tgt}-d}{L} \right) \right]$ (A1.8a)

$R_a(d + z_0, z_{m,O3}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot u^*} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{z_0} \right) - \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_{m,O3}-d}{L} \right) + \Psi_H \left(\frac{z_0}{L} \right) \right]$ (A1.8b)

$R_b = \frac{2}{k \cdot u^*} \left(\frac{Sc}{Pr} \right)^{2/3}$ (A1.8c)

$R_{surf} = \frac{1}{\frac{LAI}{R_{sto}} + \frac{SAI}{R_{ext}} + \frac{1}{R_{inc} + R_{soil}}}$ (A1.8d)

while $L = - \frac{u^{*3}}{k \cdot g \cdot \frac{H \cdot R}{P \cdot c_p}}$ (A1.8e)

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41),
 z_{tgt} is the top canopy height (the target height),
 $z_{m,O3}$ is the height of the available ozone measurement above the canopy,
 z_0 is the roughness length, usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height,
 L is the Obukhov length,
 H is the sensible heat flux in [Wm²],
 d is the displacement height, usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
 u^* is the friction velocity in [m/s],
 Sc is the Schmidt number for ozone (equal to 0.41),
 Pr is the Prandtl number of air (equal to 0.71),
 P is the atmospheric pressure in [Pa],
 g is the gravity acceleration (equal to 9.8 m/s²),
 c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure (equal to 1048 J/kg/K),
 R is the specific gas constant for dry air (equal to 287.05 J/kg/K),
 LAI is the projected leaf area in [m²/m²] ⁽⁸⁾,
 SAI is the surface area of the canopy in [m²/m²],
 $\Psi_H(\dots) = \Psi_H(\zeta)$ is the similarity function for heat with ζ as the argument ⁽⁹⁾,

according to

$\begin{aligned} (\zeta) &= 2 && \text{when } \zeta < 0 \\ &= -5\zeta && \text{when } \zeta \geq 0 \end{aligned}$ (A1.8f)

with $x = (1 - 16 * \zeta)^{1/4}$ (A1.8g)

and R_{ext} is the resistance to cuticular deposition of ozone (equal to 2 500 s/m);

R_{soil} is the soil resistance (equal to 200 s/m¹),

while $R_{sto} = 1/g_{sto}$ (A1.8h)

$R_{inc} = b \cdot SAI \cdot h / u^*$ (A1.8i)

where g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance,
 b is the empirical constant (equal to 14 m⁻¹),
 h is the height of the canopy.

Calculation of the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto})

The basis of the approach used for calculating phytotoxic ozone doses is the calculation of an instantaneous stomatal conductance g_{sto} in the given hour H , according to the equation

⁽⁸⁾ For more details see LMD et al. (2020).

⁽⁹⁾ For more details see CLRTAP (2017b).

$$g_{sto} = g_{max} * [\min(f_{phen}, f_{O3})] * f_{light} * \max[f_{min}, (f_{temp} * f_{VPD} * f_{sw})] \quad (A1.9)$$

where g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in [mmol O₃ /m² PLA per second],
 g_{max} is the species-specific maximum stomatal conductance in [mmol O₃ /m² PLA per second], see Table A1.2,
 f_{phen} is the relative proportion function for the phenology for the different stage of growing,
 f_{O3} is the relative proportion function for the influence of ozone on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence,
 f_{min} is the species-specific relative minimum stomatal conductance that occurs during daylight hours, see Table A1.2,
 $f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{sw}, f_{light}$ are relative proportion functions for leaf stomata respond to temperature, air humidity, soil moisture and light.

Parameters $f_{phen}, f_{O3}, f_{light}, f_{temp}, f_{VPD}, f_{sw}$ and f_{min} are expressed as relative proportion functions, taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} . These functions allow taking into account irradiance (f_{light}), temperature (f_{temp}), water vapour deficit at leaves level (f_{vpd}), soil moisture (f_{sw}), phenology for the different stage of growing (f_{phen}) and the influence of ozone on stomatal flux by promoting premature senescence (f_{O3}). f_{min} is the minimum relative value of stomatal conductance during the daylight.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated based on the accumulation of thermal time over the growing season of the crop being considered (Colette et al., 2018), according to CLRTAP (2017a). For wheat and potato, the accumulation period is defined for each year using the effective temperature sum (ETS) in °C for days in excess of 0 °C, while for tomato for days in excess of 10 °C.

For wheat, the total accumulation period during which wheat is sensitive to ozone exposure is 200 °C days and 300 °C days before mid-anthesis (mid-point in flowering) to 700 °C days to 550 °C days after mid-anthesis for Atlantic, Boreal and Continental regions and Mediterranean region, respectively. The timing of mid-anthesis is estimated by starting at the first date after 1 January (or just 1 January) when the temperature exceeds 0 °C. The mean daily temperature is then accumulated (temperature sum), and mid-anthesis is estimated to be a temperature sum of 1075 °C days for Atlantic, Boreal and Continental regions and 1250 °C days for Mediterranean region, which in general corresponds to bread wheat.

For potato, the accumulation period stands between 330 °C days before the tuber initiation date and 800 °C days after this date. The tuber initiation date is considered to be homogeneous throughout Europe. The reasons for its simplification are a) heterogeneous climatic conditions in the European countries naturally lead to different time of potato planting (Pedersen et al., 2005) followed by different time of the tuber initiation and b) lack of detailed local data availability for modelling and mapping.

As discussed ⁽¹⁰⁾ with the French national Chamber of agriculture (APCA, <http://chambres-agriculture.fr>), the tuber initiation starts 15 days after the transplantation in the field, which occurs in May. Therefore, the fixed date for the tuber initiation was set to June 1st.

⁽¹⁰⁾ There is a lack of information on a date of potato tuber initiation in Europe. It should ideally rely on existing models based on agricultural practices, local climatology, ground properties, and location. INERIS, while developing the POD script, relied on contents of discussions with the French National Chamber of Agriculture (consultation with APCA, March 2018; Deumier and Hannon, 2010). Based on the information given that the tuber initiation starts 15 days after the transplantation in the field, which occurs in May in France, a fixed date of June 1st has been chosen for France and applied also for the rest of Europe. This date should be revised according to the availability of more accurate information on potato plantations in Europe.

For tomato, the accumulation period is from 250 °C days to 1500 °C days after transplantation in the field over a base temperature of 10 °C. The timing of the transplantation is set on the date June 1st.

The parameter f_{phen} is calculated according to following equations:

in the case of wheat:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{phen} &= 1 && \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_1_ETS}) \leq ETS \leq (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_3_ETS}) \\
 &= 1 - \left(\frac{f_{phen_a}}{f_{phen_4_ETS} - f_{phen_3_ETS}} \right) * (ETS - f_{phen_3_ETS}) \\
 &&& \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_3_ETS}) < ETS \leq (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_4_ETS}) \\
 &= f_{phen_e} - \left(\frac{f_{phen_e}}{f_{phen_5_ETS} - f_{phen_4_ETS}} \right) * (ETS - f_{phen_4_ETS}) \\
 &&& \text{when } (f_{phen_2_ETS} + f_{phen_4_ETS}) < ETS \leq f_{phen_5_ETS}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A1.9a}$$

in the case of potato (formulated based on CLRTAP, 2017b):

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{phen} &= 1 - \left(\frac{1 - f_{phen_a}}{f_{phen_1_ETS}} \right) * ETS && \text{when } f_{phen_1_ETS} \leq ETS < 0 \\
 &= 1 - \left(\frac{1 - f_{phen_e}}{f_{phen_2_ETS}} \right) * ETS && \text{when } 0 < ETS \leq f_{phen_2_ETS}
 \end{aligned} \tag{A1.9b}$$

in the case of tomato (formulated based on CLRTAP, 2017b):

$$f_{phen} = \frac{ETS - f_{phen_2_ETS}}{A_{start_ETS} - f_{phen_2_ETS}} \quad \text{when } A_{start_ETS} \leq ETS < A_{end_ETS} \tag{A1.9c}$$

where ETS is the effective temperature sum in °C days using a base temperature of 0 °C for wheat and potato and a base temperature of 10 °C for tomato (see Table A1.2); for wheat, ETS is set to 0 °C days at mid-anthesis day. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 200 °C days before mid-anthesis, and A_{end_ETS} will be at 700 °C days after mid-anthesis over a base temperature of 0 °C; for potato, ETS is set to 0 °C days at tuber initiation day. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 330 °C days before tuber initiation and A_{end_ETS} at 800 °C days after tuber initiation over a base temperature of 0 °C; for tomato, ETS is set to 0 °C days at transplantation day in the field. Then A_{start_ETS} will be at 250 °C days after transplantation in the field and A_{end_ETS} at 1500 °C days after transplantation in the field over a base temperature of 10 °C, f_{phen_a} , f_{phen_e} is the phenology function, which consists of terms describing rate changes of g_{max} expressed as fractions (see Table A1.2), $f_{phen_1_ETS}$, $f_{phen_2_ETS}$, $f_{phen_3_ETS}$, $f_{phen_4_ETS}$, $f_{phen_5_ETS}$ are °C days (see Table A1.2; $f_{phen_1_ETS}$ and $f_{phen_5_ETS}$ define period crops to be sensitive to ozone exposure), A_{start_ETS} and A_{end_ETS} are the effective temperature sums (counted from the day of the mid-anthesis for wheat, from the day of the tuber initiation for potato and from the day of the transplantation in the field for tomato) above a base temperature of 0 °C for wheat and potato and 10 °C for tomato at the start and end of the O_3 accumulation period respectively; see Table A1.2.

The parameter f_{O_3} in the case of wheat is calculated according to equation

$$f_{O_3} = [(1 + (POD_0/14))^8]^{-1} \tag{A1.9d}$$

$$\text{while } POD_0 = \sum_{n=A_{start}}^{H-1} F_{sto}(n) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6} \tag{A1.9e}$$

where POD_0 is the ozone flux already accumulated since the beginning of the vegetation

$F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly ozone flux in the hour n , calculated in the previous steps based on Equation A1.10, while $F_{sto}(A_{start})$ is equal to 0.

The parameter (ozone function) f_{O_3} in the case of potato is calculated according to equation

$$f_{O_3} = [(1+(AOTO/40)^5)^{-1}] \quad (A1.9f)$$

where $AOTO$ is accumulated ozone concentration from the start of the vegetation period A_{start} up to the last hour $H-1$.

The parameter (ozone function) f_{O_3} in the case of tomato is not determined.

The parameter f_{light} is calculated according to

$$f_{light} = 1 - \text{EXP}[-\text{light_a} * \text{PPFD}] \quad (A1.9g)$$

while $\text{PPFD} = \text{SSRD} * 0.5 * 4.5 \quad (A1.9h)$

where PPFD represents the photosynthetic photon flux density [$\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$ per second],
 light_a is a light parameter (see Table A1.2),
 SSRD represents the surface net solar radiation in [W/m^2].

The parameter f_{temp} is calculated according to:

$$f_{temp} = \begin{cases} f_{min}, & [(T - T_{min}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min})] * [(T_{max} - T) / (T_{max} - T_{opt})]^{bt} \text{ when } T_{min} < T < T_{max} \\ f_{min} & \text{when } T_{min} > T > T_{max} \end{cases} \quad (A1.9i)$$

while $bt = (T_{max} - T_{opt}) / (T_{opt} - T_{min}) \quad (A1.9j)$

where T_{min} , T_{max} and T_{opt} are minimum, maximum and optimum temperatures determining leaf stomata opening (see Table A1.2)

The parameter f_{VPD} is calculated according to:

$$f_{VPD} = \min\{1, \max\{f_{min}, [(1-f_{min}) * (\text{VPD}_{min} - \text{VPD}) / (\text{VPD}_{min} - \text{VPD}_{max})] + f_{min}\}\} \quad (A1.9k)$$

while $\text{VPD} = e_s(T_a) * (1-h_r) \quad (A1.9l)$

$$e_s(T_a) = a \exp[bT_a / (T_a + c)] \quad (A1.9m)$$

where VPD_{min} is the minimum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening,
 VPD_{max} is the maximum vapour pressure deficit determining leaf stomata opening,
 T_a is the air temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$],
 h_r is the relative humidity [%]/100,
 $e_s(T_a)$ is the potential (saturation) water vapour pressure,
 a, b, c are the empirical constants ($a = 0.611$ kPa, $b = 17.502$, $c = 240.97$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The ΣVPD (i.e. the function describing stomatal re-opening in the afternoon) is taken into account for maps POD_{SPEC} for wheat and potato. ΣVPD (kPa) should be calculated for daylight hours until dawn of the next day. If $\Sigma\text{VPD} \geq \Sigma\text{VPD}_{\text{crit}}$, g_{sto} calculated using Equation A1.9 is valid if smaller or equal to

g_{sto} of the preceding hour. If g_{sto} is larger than g_{sto} of the preceding hour, given that ΣVPD is larger than or equal to ΣVPD_{crit} , it is replaced by the g_{sto} of the preceding hour.

Table A1.2 Parametrisation for POD_6SPEC for wheat flag leaves and the upper-canopy sunlit leaves of potato and tomato, for different biogeographical regions

Parameter	Units	(Bread) Wheat		Potato	Tomato
		Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (Pannonia, Steppic)	Mediterranean	Atlantic, Boreal, Continental (Mediterranean Pannonia, Steppic)	Mediterranean
g_{max}	mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	500	430	750	330
f_{min}	fraction	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06
light_a	-	0.0105	0.0105	0.005	0.0125
T_{min}	°C	12	12	13	18
T_{opt}	°C	26	28	28	28
T_{max}	°C	40	39	39	37
VPD_{max}	kPa	1.2	3.2	2.1	1
VPD_{min}	kPa	3.2	4.6	3.5	4
ΣVPD_{crit}	kPa	8	16	10	-
f_{O_3}	POD0 mmol O ₃ /m ² PLA per second	14	-	-	-
f_{O_3}	AOTO, ppmh	-	-	40	-
f_{O_3}	exponent	8	-	5	-
Astart_ETS	°C day	-	-	-	250
Aend_ETS	°C day	-	-	-	1500
Leaf dimension	cm	2	2	4	3
Canopy height	m	1	0.75	1	2
f_{phen_a}	fraction	0.3	0.5	0.4	1
f_{phen_b}	fraction	-	-	-	-
f_{phen_c}	fraction	-	-	-	-
f_{phen_d}	fraction	-	-	-	-
f_{phen_e}	fraction	0.7	0.5	0.2	0.0
$f_{phen_1_ETS}$	°C day	-200	-300	-330	0
$f_{phen_2_ETS}$	°C day	0	0	800	2770
$f_{phen_3_ETS}$	°C day	100	70	-	-
$f_{phen_4_ETS}$	°C day	525	312	-	-
$f_{phen_5_ETS}$	°C day	700	550	-	-
mid-anthesis	°C day	1075	1250	-	-

Source: CLRTAP, 2017a; González-Fernández et al., 2013; González-Fernández (personal communication, May 2021).

The parameter f_{SW} is replaced by f_{SMI} (where SMI represents Soil Moisture Index with maximum at field capacity), taking values between 0 and 1 as a proportion of g_{max} (with 0 for soil moisture at and below wilting point), following the parameterization given in Simpson et al. (2012), similar to the plant available water (PAW) parameterization f_{PAW} as defined for wheat in CLRTAP (2017a). The basic equation used for f_{SW} resp. f_{SMI} is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_{SMI} &= 0 && \text{for } SMI \leq 0 \\
 &= \frac{SMI}{PAW_t} && \text{for } 0 < SMI \leq PAW_t \\
 &= 1 && \text{for } SMI > PAW_t
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{A1.9n}$$

while $SMI = \frac{SWLL - PWP}{FC - PWP}$ (A1.9o)

where PAW_t is the threshold amount of water in the soil available to the plants, above which stomatal conductance is at a maximum, set to 0.5,
 $SWLL$ is the soil moisture in [m^3/m^3],
 PWP is the permanent wilting point in [cm^3/cm^3],
 FC is the field capacity in [cm^3/cm^3].

The Soil Moisture Index using the EMEP methodology as described in Simpson et al. (2012) and CLRTAP (2020) is used. It is computed using the soil moisture variable available from a meteorological model, which represents the water content in m^3 of water per m^3 of ground [m^3/m^3] in a specific ground level, in dependence on the available dataset. For soil moisture, the ECWMF's ERA5-Land variable Volume of water in soil layer 3 (i.e. 28-100 cm) has been used, see Section 3.3. The level of soil layer was chosen based on recommendation of Haberle and Svoboda (2015). The soil moisture is quite a sensitive parameter in the calculation of the POD. Next to the soil moisture, the soil moisture index also takes into account the permanent wilting point and the field capacity; they are taken from JRC soil database (JRC, 2016), see Annex 2, Section A2.3.

No limitation of stomatal conductance due to soil moisture can be assumed for tomato, since it is an irrigated horticultural crop. Thus, f_{SMI} for this crop could be established to $f_{SMI} = 1$ over the whole range of SMI values to remove limitation due to soil moisture deficit.

Modelling the hourly stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto})

Once the hourly stomatal conductance of ozone (g_{sto}) and all relevant variables are computed, the stomatal flux of ozone (F_{sto}) can be calculated, based on the assumption that the concentration of ozone at the top of the canopy represents a reasonable estimate of the concentration at the upper surface of the laminar layer for a sunlit upper canopy leaf. F_{sto} is calculated according to the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation) methodology, thus the fraction of the ozone taken up by the stomata is given using a combination of the stomatal conductance, the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance and the leaf surface resistance. The hourly stomatal flux in the given hour H is calculated according to

$$F_{sto} = c(z_1) * g_{sto} * \frac{r_c}{r_b + r_c} \quad (A1.10)$$

where F_{sto} is the hourly stomatal flux of ozone in [$nmol/m^2$ PLA per second]
 $c(z_1)$ is the concentration of ozone at canopy top in [$nmol/m^3$]
 r_b is the quasi-laminar resistance in [s/m]
 r_c is the leaf surface resistance in [s/m]
 g_{sto} is the actual stomatal conductance in [m/s],

while $r_c = 1/(g_{sto} + g_{ext})$ (A1.10a)

$$r_b = 1.3 * 150 * \sqrt{\frac{L}{u(z_1)}} \quad (A1.10b)$$

where g_{ext} is the external leaf, or cuticular, resistance in [m/s], equal to 1/2500 m/s
 $u(z_1)$ is the wind speed at height z_1 (z_1 is the canopy top)
 L is the cross-wind leaf dimension (2 cm, see Table A1.2)

while $u_{(z1)} = \frac{u^*}{k} * \ln\left(\frac{z_1 - d}{z_0}\right)$ (A1.10c)

where k is the von Kármán constant (equal to 0.41)

d	is the displacement height usually assumed as 2/3 of the canopy height,
z_1	is the top of the canopy
z_0	is the roughness length usually assumed as 1/10 of the canopy height
u^*	is the friction velocity.

Box A1.1 shows the conversion of stomatal conductance and ozone concentration to units demanded for POD_Y calculation.

Box A1.1 Conversion of stomatal conductance g_{sto} and ozone concentration to units demanded for POD_Y calculation

Stomatal conductance g_{sto} has to be converted from units $mmol/m^2$ per second to units m/s (since all the resistances are expressed in the unit of s/m). At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure ($1.013 \times 10^5\text{ Pa}$), the conversion is made by dividing the conductance in $mmol/m^2$ per second by 41 000 to give conductance in m/s .

To convert the **ozone concentration (C)** at canopy height from $\mu g/m^3$ resp. ppb to $nmol/m^3$, the following equation should be used:

$$C [nmol \cdot m^{-3}] = C [ppb] \cdot P / (R \cdot T) = C [\mu g / m^3] / 2 \cdot P / (R \cdot T) \quad (A1.11)$$

where P is the atmospheric pressure in Pa,
 R is the universal gas constant of $8.31447\text{ J/mol per Kelvin}$
 T is the air temperature in Kelvin.

At standard temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and air pressure ($1.013 \times 10^5\text{ Pa}$), the concentration in ppb should be multiplied by 41.56 to calculate the concentration in $nmol/m^3$.

Source: CLRTAP, 2017a.

Calculation of POD_Y from F_{sto}

Hourly averaged stomatal ozone fluxes (F_{sto}) in excess of a Y threshold are accumulated over a species or vegetation-specific accumulation period using the following equation:

$$POD_Y = \sum_n (F_{sto}(n) - Y) \cdot \frac{3600}{10^6} \quad (A1.12)$$

while Y (for wheat, potato or tomato) = $6\text{ nmol}/m^2\text{ PLA per second}$

where POD_Y is the phytotoxic ozone dose related to the threshold Y , in $[mmol/m^2\text{ PLA}]$,
 $F_{sto}(n)$ is the hourly ozone flux in the hour n of the accumulation period.

The value Y (in $[nmol/m^2\text{ PLA s}^{-1}]$) is subtracted from each hourly averaged F_{sto} (in $[nmol/m^2\text{ PLA s}^{-1}]$) value and the F_{sto} (after the subtracting of Y) is accumulated only when $F_{sto} > Y$, during daylight hours (when global radiation is more than $50\text{ W}/m^2$). The value is then converted to hourly fluxes by multiplying by 3 600 and to $mmol$ by dividing by 10^6 to get the stomatal ozone flux in $mmol/m^2\text{ PLA}$.

Trees

The POD maps for selected trees, i.e. beech (*F. sylvatica*) and spruce (*P. abies*), are created with calculated hourly POD values which are based on hourly O_3 concentrations, hourly meteorological parameters such as temperature, vapour pressure deficit, solar radiation and soil hydraulic property

data. The hourly O₃ concentrations are calculated by combining the monitoring data from rural background stations, chemical transport modelling data and other supplementary data (Horálek et al., 2023).

The calculation of the phytotoxic O₃ dose above a threshold Y (POD₁) as described in Vlasáková et al. (2023) follows precisely the methodology described in the Manual for modelling and mapping critical loads & levels of the CLRTAP in its most recent available revision (CLRTAP, 2017a), including some specifications presented in the Scientific Background Documents of this manual (CLRTAP, 2017b, 2020), as prepared by the International scientific Cooperative Programme on effects of air pollution on natural vegetation and crops of the Working Group on Effects of the CLRTAP (ICP Vegetation).

A1.4 Methods for uncertainty analysis

The uncertainty estimation of the European map is based on leave-one-out cross-validation. This cross-validation method computes the quality of the spatial interpolation for each point of measurement (i.e. monitoring station) from all available information except from the point in question, i.e. it withholds one data point and then makes a prediction at the spatial location of that point. This procedure is repeated for all measurement points in the available set. The predicted and measurement values at these points are plotted in the form of a scatter plot. With help of statistical indicators (see below), the quality of the predictions is demonstrated objectively. The advantage of the nature of this cross-validation technique is that it enables evaluation of the quality of the predicted values at locations without measurements, as long as they are within the area covered by the measurements.

In addition, a simple comparison is made between the point measurement data and the estimated values of the 1 km x 1 km grid cells (for PM and NO₂) or the 10 km x10 km grid cells (for ozone) for the separate rural and urban background (and urban traffic, where relevant) map layers and the 1 km x 1 km grid cells for the final combined maps, for the health-related indicators, and the 2 x 2 km grid cells in the case of AOT40 and NO_x. Note that the grid cell value is the mean estimated value of this grid cell area. The estimated value within a grid cell will only approximate the predicted value(s) at the station(s) lying within that cell. This additional analysis has not been performed for BaP.

Cross-validation

The results of cross-validation are described by the statistical indicators and scatter plots. The main indicator used is root mean squared error (RMSE) and the additional ones are relative RMSE (RRMSE), which is expressed in relative terms (by relating the RMSE to the mean of the air pollution indicator value for all stations), and bias (mean prediction error, MPE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Z}(s_i) - Z(s_i))^2} \quad (A1.13)$$

$$RRMSE = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{Z}} \cdot 100 \quad (A1.14)$$

$$bias(MPE) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Z}(s_i) - Z(s_i)) \quad (A1.15)$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_i)$ is the air quality indicator value derived from the measured concentration at the i^{th} point, $i = 1, \dots, N$,
 $Z(s_i)$ is the air quality estimated indicator value at the i^{th} point using other information, without the indicator value derived from the measured concentration at the i^{th} point,
 $RRMSE$ is the relative RMSE, expressed in percent,
 \bar{Z} is the arithmetic average of the indicator values $Z(s_1), \dots, Z(s_N)$, as derived from measurement concentrations at the stations $i = 1, \dots, N$,
 N is the number of the measuring points.

Other indicators are R^2 and the regression equation ($y = a.x + c$) parameters slope (a) and intercept (c), following from the scatter plot between the predicted (using cross-validation) and the observed concentrations. RMSE should be as small as possible, bias (MPE) should be as close to zero as possible, R^2 should be as close to 1 as possible, slope a should be as close to 1 as possible, and intercept c should be as close to zero as possible (in the regression equation $y = a.x + c$).

In the cross-validation of PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP, only stations with PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP measurement data, respectively, are used (not the pseudo PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP stations, see Annex 1 Section A1.1).

Comparison of the point measurement and interpolated grid values

The comparison of point measurement and predicted grid values is described by the linear regression equation and its parameters and statistical values. The comparison is executed separately for rural and urban background (and urban traffic, where relevant) map layers and for the final combined map. In the case of PM_{2.5} and NO_x, only the stations with actual PM_{2.5} and NO_x measurement data are used (not the pseudo PM_{2.5} and NO_x stations). This analysis is done for PM, ozone, NO₂ and NO_x, not for BaP.

The point observation – point cross-validation prediction analysis (Annex 3, sections “Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation”) describes interpolation performance at point locations when there is no observation (as it follows the leave-one-out approach). In this case, the smoothing effect of the interpolation is most prevalent.

The point observation – grid prediction approach indicates performance of the value for the grid cell (either in 1 km, 2 km or 10 km resolution) with respect to the observations that are located within that cell. As such, some variability is due to smoothing but it also includes smoothing due to spatial averaging into the grid cells. As such, the point-grid validation approach tells us how well our interpolated and aggregated grid values approximate the measurements at the actual station (point) locations. Whereas the point-point approach tells us how well our interpolated values estimate the indicator at a point where there is no actual measurement at that location, under the constraint that the point lies within the area covered by measurements.

Annex 2

Input data

The types of input data in this paper are similar as in Horálek et al. (2023), apart from the modelling data: instead of the EMEP model results, the CHIMERE model output has been used for BaP mapping, see Section A2.2. The air quality, modelling, satellite and meteorological data as used in Horálek et al. (2024) has been updated for 2022. For readability of this paper, the list of the input data is reproduced here. The key data is the air quality measurements at the monitoring stations extracted from the Air Quality e-Reporting database EEA (2024a), including geographical coordinates (*latitude, longitude*).

The supplementary data cover the whole mapping domain and are converted into the EEA reference projection ETRS89-LAEA5210 on a 1 km grid resolution (for health-related indicators apart from ozone) and a 10 km grid resolution (ozone). The data for the maps of vegetation related indicators (particularly AOT40) were converted – like in the previous reports (Horálek et al., 2024, and references cited therein) – into a 2 km resolution to allow accurate land cover exposure estimates to be prepared for use in the EEA indicator on ecosystem exposure to ozone (EEA, 2024b).

A2.1 Air quality monitoring data

Air quality station monitoring data for the relevant year as extracted from the official EEA Air Quality e-Reporting database, EEA (2024a) in March 2024 has been used. This data set has been supplemented with British stations from the Defra (2024) database ⁽¹¹⁾ and with several EMEP rural stations from the EBAS (NILU, 2024) database not reported to the Air Quality e-Reporting database. Specifically, additional 7 stations for PM₁₀, 5 for PM_{2.5}, 12 for NO₂ and 6 NO_x from the EBAS database and additional 82 British stations for PM₁₀, 72 for PM_{2.5}, 64 for ozone, 140 for NO₂, 13 for NO_x and 27 for BaP from the data archive Defra have been added, for mapping purposes.

The following pollutants and aggregations are considered:

PM ₁₀	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
	– 90.4 percentile of the daily average values [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
PM _{2.5}	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
Ozone	– 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour average values [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
	– peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
	– SOMO35 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2022
	– SOMO10 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2022
	– AOT40 for vegetation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2022
	– AOT40 for forests [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2022
	– hourly values [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], all hours of the year 2022 (for the purpose of POD _y mapping)
NO ₂	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
NO _x	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
NO	– annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022 (for the purposes of NO _x mapping only)
BaP	– annual average [ng/m^3], year 2022

The exact values of percentiles are actually 90.41 in the case of PM₁₀ daily means and 93.15 in the case of ozone maximum daily 8-hour means.

⁽¹¹⁾ The United Kingdom exited the European Union in January 2020 and does not report air quality data to the AQ e-reporting database. Nevertheless, in order to enable the interpolation across the whole mapping domain, the publicly available British data from the Defra database have also been used in the analysis.

For a considerable number of stations NO_x is measured, but it is not reported as such but separately as NO and NO₂. For these stations reporting NO and NO₂ separately, the NO_x concentrations were derived according to the equation

$$NO_x = NO_2 + \frac{46}{30} \cdot NO \quad (A2.1)$$

In this equation, all components are expressed in µg/m³, with a molecular mass for NO of 30 g/mol and for NO₂ of 46 g/mol.

For the purpose of this report, the peak season is calculated for each station as the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration during the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running-average O₃ concentration. This means that for each station, twelve 6-month running averages of the daily 8-hour maximum are calculated. The first 6-month running average starts with calculations from August 1 of the previous year to January 31 of the current year, while the last 6-month running average ends with calculations from July 1 to December 31 of the current year. The maximum of these 12 values is selected as the peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means (EEA, 2021).

SOMO35 is the annual sum of the differences between maximum daily 8-hour concentrations above 70 µg/m³ (i.e. 35 ppb) and 70 µg/m³. SOMO10 is the annual sum of the differences between maximum daily 8-hour means above 20 µg/m³ (i.e. 10 ppb) and 20 µg/m³. AOT40 is the sum of the differences between hourly concentrations greater than 80 µg/m³ (i.e. 40 ppb) and 80 µg/m³, using only observations between 08:00 and 20:00 CET, calculated over the three months from May to July for AOT40 for vegetation and over the six months from April to September for AOT40 for forests.

Only the stations with annual data coverage of at least 75 percent are used. In the case of SOMO35, SOMO10 and AOT40 indicators, a correction for the missing data is applied according to the equation

$$I_{corr} = I \cdot \frac{N_{max}}{N} \quad (A2.2)$$

where I_{corr} is the corrected indicator (SOMO35, SOMO10 or AOT40 for vegetation or for forests),
 I is the value of the given indicator without any correction,
 N is the number of the available daily resp. hourly data in a year for the given station,
 N_{max} is the maximum possible number of the days or hours applicable for the indicator.

For the indicators relevant to human health (i.e. for all PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} indicators, ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means SOMO35 and SOMO10, and NO₂ and BaP annual averages), data from stations classified as *background* (for all the three types of area, *rural*, *urban* and *suburban*) are considered; for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} and NO₂, also *urban* and *suburban traffic* stations are considered. (Throughout the paper, the urban and suburban stations are handled together). *Industrial* stations are not considered, as they represent local concentration levels that cannot be easily generalized for the whole map. For the indicators relevant to vegetation damage (i.e. for ozone AOT40 and POD₆ parameters and NO_x annual average), only *rural background* stations are considered; the relevant maps are constructed (and applicable) for rural areas only. In the case of existing data (with sufficient annual time coverage) from two or more different measurement devices in the same station location, the average of these data is used.

The stations from French overseas areas (departments), Svalbard, Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands were excluded. These areas outside the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018) were excluded from the interpolation and mapping domain, as the interpolation should be performed across a generally compact territory.

Table A2.1 shows the number of the measurement stations (not pseudo stations) selected for the individual pollutants and their respective indicators.

Table A2.1 Number of stations selected for each pollutant indicator and area type, 2022

Station type	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	Ozone				NO ₂	NO _x	BaP	
			Health rel. (3)	Peak seas.	AOT40 veg.	AOT40 for.				POD _y
Rural background	415	278	567	547	566	570	569	506	417	105
Urban/suburb. backgr.	1654	1065	1258	1198	-	-	-	1485	-	491
Urban/suburb. traffic	814	488	-	-	-	-	-	1292	-	-

For the PM_{2.5} mapping, in addition to the PM_{2.5} stations, 156 rural background, 164 urban/suburban background and 356 urban/suburban traffic PM₁₀ stations (at locations without PM_{2.5} measurement) have been also used for the purpose of calculating the pseudo PM_{2.5} station data.

In the case of NO_x, 374 stations with NO_x reported data have been used, while for 43 stations NO_x values are calculated from reported NO₂ and NO data using Eq. A2.1. Next to this, for the NO_x mapping 90 additional rural background NO₂ stations (at locations without NO_x measurement) were also used for the purpose of calculating the pseudo NO_x station data.

For the BaP mapping, in addition to the BaP stations, 60 rural and 73 urban background pseudo BaP station data calculated based on the PM_{2.5} measurements have also been used.

A2.2 Chemical transport modelling outputs

Up to the maps for 2019, EMEP MSC-W model was used, specifically its model results for year Y based on meteorology for year Y and emissions for year Y-1. Then, the maps for 2020 and 2021 were prepared using the CAMS Ensemble Forecast (CAMS-ENS FC) model output, as the EMEP model results based on the emissions for year Y-1 were not available in these years (as 2020 was a special year due to the COVID-19 situation). In these years, the CAMS-ENS FC model output was used, in agreement with Horálek et al. (2021), which recommended this modelling product as an alternative to the EMEP model. For the year 2022, both modelling products were again available, giving quite similar results in the mapping. It was decided further to use the CAMS-ENS FC model output, due to the consistency both with the last two years and with the interim maps (for which the CAMS-ENS FC model output is used).

The CAMS Ensemble Forecast model output, as provided by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) at a regional scale over Europe, consists of an ensemble of eleven involved air quality models run operationally (MINNI and MONARCH models have been added to existing ones in June 2022.) All models use the same CAMS-REG anthropogenic emissions and current meteorology from the operational ECMWF IFS forecast. The models provide (together with other products) a 96-hour forecast made available at 08:00 UTC on the day of the forecast. The forecast data product is available on an hourly time resolution and at a spatial resolution of 0.1° x 0.1°, which corresponds roughly to 5-10 km x 10 km. Each model forecast is combined into the Ensemble Forecast by taking the median of all modelling results. For further details see ECMWF (2023).

In this report, the CAMS Ensemble Forecast data (for the lead hour 0-23) for 2022 have been used (METEO FRANCE et al., 2023). All the models used in the ensemble were run using the CAMS-REG-v5.1 REF2 v2.0.1 emissions representative of 2018 for most of the year 2022 (implemented in March), while before March 2022 CAMS-REG-AP_v4.2_REF2.1 representative of 2017 were used ECMWF (2023). For more information on emissions, see Kuenen et al., 2021. All modelling data have been aggregated from the hourly means to the same set of parameters as for the air quality observations:

PM₁₀ – annual average [µg/m³], year 2022

- 90.4 percentile of the daily means [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
- PM_{2.5} – annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
- Ozone – 93.2 percentile of the highest maximum daily 8-hour average value [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
 - peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
 - SOMO35 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2022
 - SOMO10 [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{day}$], year 2022
 - AOT40 for vegetation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2022
 - AOT40 for forests [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{hour}$], year 2022
- NO₂ – annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022
- NO_x – annual average [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$], year 2022

Due to the complete temporal data coverage available at the modelled data, the PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means is identical with the 36th highest daily mean and the O₃ indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means is identical with the 26th highest maximum daily 8-hour mean.

The data were re-gridded into the reference EEA 10 km x 10 km grid (for ozone health related indicators), 1 km x 1 km grid (for PM and NO₂) and 2 km x 2 km grid (for vegetation related indicators).

For BaP, the model used is the three-dimensional Eulerian chemistry transport model CHIMERE (version: chimere 2013), as run by CIEMAT (Vivanco et al., 2024). Meteorological data used as input to the model were obtained from simulations of the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which were obtained from the MARS archive at the ECMWF through the access provided for research projects by the Spanish State Meteorological Agency (AEMET). The model was run at a spatial resolution of 0.15° x 0.15° (circa 15 km x 15 km) for a domain covering the whole mapping domain, apart from Iceland. A simulation with a similar treatment for BaP (implemented in a more recent version of CHIMERE) was included in a multi-model comparison, which concluded that CHIMERE and the EMEP MSC-E POP model (used in previous mapping reports) were the two best-performing models (Gusev et al., 2022). The parameter used is

- Benzo(a)pyrene – annual average [ng/m^3], year 2022.

The CHIMERE model output has been used for the second time instead of the previously used EMEP model run by MSC-E, due to the lack of the EMEP modelling data for 2022 in the time of the analysis (as a consequence of relocation of the MSC-E from Moscow to Ljubljana, due to the aggression of Russia against Ukraine). The domain of the CHIMERE model output does not cover Iceland. Thus, an alternative BaP map using the *EMEP MSC-E POP* model output for 2020 (EMEP, 2022) has been constructed and applied for the area of Iceland (see Annex 3 Section A3.5). The EMEP MSC-E POP model is a three-dimensional Eulerian multi-compartment chemistry transport model (Gusev et al., 2005). Its resolution is 0.1° x 0.1°, i.e. circa 10 km x 10 km.

A2.3 Other supplementary data

Meteorological parameters

The meteorological data used are the ECMWF data extracted from the CDS (Climate Data Store, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/home>). Hourly data for 2022 are used. Most of the data come from the reanalysed data set ERA5-Land at a 0.1°x0.1° resolution (of CDS), namely the indicators:

- Surface solar radiation [MW/m^2] – variable “Surface solar radiation downwards”
- Temperature [K] – variable “2m temperature”

Wind speed [m/s] – calculated based on variables “10m u-component of wind” and “10m v-component of wind”

Relative humidity [%] – calculated based on variables “2m temperature” and “2m dewpoint temperature”

Soil water – variable “Volumetric soil water layer 3”, i.e. layer of 28-100 cm (used for POD only)

Wind speed (WV) is derived from the “10m u-component of wind” (10U) and “10m v-component of wind” (10V) according to relation

$$WV = \sqrt{(10U)^2 + (10V)^2} \quad (A2.3)$$

Relative humidity (RH) is derived by means of the saturated water vapour pressure (e_t) as a function of “2m temperature” (2T) and “2m dew point temperature” (2D) according to relation

$$RH = \frac{e_{2D}}{e_{2T}} \cdot 100, \text{ with } e_t = 6.1365^{\frac{17.502 \cdot t}{24097+t}} \quad (A2.4)$$

where t is 2T and 2D, respectively.

In the coastal areas (where the data from ERA5-Land are not available), the same parameters from the reanalysed data set ERA5 in 0.25°x0.25° resolution are applied. Next to this, the following data (not available in the ERA5-Land data set) from the ERA5 data set is also used:

Friction velocity [m/s] – variable “Friction velocity”. The friction velocity (also known as the shear-stress velocity) has the dimensions of velocity.

Surface sensible heat flux [W/m²] – variable “surface_sensible_heat_flux”.

Most of the meteorological parameters are used for POD_y maps only. For other maps than POD_y, annual aggregations based on hourly data are used, namely for the parameters:

Wind speed – annual average [m/s¹], year 2022

Relative humidity – annual average [%], year 2022

Surface solar radiation – annual average of daily sum [MWs/m²], year 2022

All meteorological data were re-gridded and converted into the reference EEA 1 km resolution grid, 10 km resolution grid and 2 km resolution grid, in the ETRS89-LAEA5210 projection.

Altitude

The altitude data field (in meters) of Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) is used, with an original grid resolution of 15 arcseconds (some 463 m at 60N). Source: U.S. Geological Survey Earth Resources Observation and Science, see Danielson and Gesch (2011). The field is converted into the ETRS 1989 LAEA projection. (The resolution after projection was 449.2 m). In the following step, the raster dataset was resampled to 100 m resolution and shifted to the extent of EEA reference grid. Finally, the dataset was spatially aggregated into 1 km, 2 km and 10 km resolutions. Next to this, another aggregation has been executed based on the 1 km grid cells, i.e. the floating average of the circle with a radius of 5 km around all relevant grid cells.

Population density and population totals

Population density (in inhbs/km², number of residents for the year 2018) is based on JRC-Geostat 2018 grid dataset, Eurostat (2020). The dataset is in 1 km resolution, in the EEA reference grid.

For regions not included in the JRC-Geostat 2018, an alternative source was used. Namely, it was GHS population grid for 2020 in the 1 km resolution as prepared by the JRC (JRC, 2023). As the GHS population data were available for 2020 only, not for 2018 (like JRC-Geostat 2018), we have scaled them to 2018 based on the country bases, based on 2018 and 2020 Eurostat data for countries (Eurostat, 2024). The areas lacking JRC-Geostat 2018 data, and supplemented with the scaled GHS data were: Andorra, Türkiye, Faroe Islands, Jan Mayen, Crown dependencies, Gibraltar and northern Cyprus. As such, the JRC-Geostat 2018 data and these supplements cover the entire mapping area.

To verify the consistency of merging the JRC-Geostat 2018 with the GHS (JRC) data, these two datasets were compared based on the national population totals of the individual countries. Additionally, the national population totals for the JRC-Geostat 2018 gridded data (supplemented by the scaled GHS data) were verified with the Eurostat national population data for 2022 (Eurostat, 2024). Figure A2.1 presents both comparisons. From these verifications, one can conclude a high correlation of the national population totals of each data source. Based on this, in the further calculations on national population totals the actual Eurostat data for 2022 (Eurostat, 2024) were used, as described further.

Figure A2.1 Correlation of national population totals for GHS with JRC-GHS 2018 (left) and Eurostat 2022 with supplemented JRC-Geostat 2018 (right)

Population density data can be used to classify the spatial distribution of each type of area (rural, urban or mixed population density) in Europe. This information is used to select and weight the air quality values, grid cell by grid cell and merge them into a final combined map (Annex 1). Furthermore, it is used to estimate population health exposure and percentages above standards per country, large regions, EU-27 and for the total mapping area, including involved uncertainties. These activities take place on the 1 km resolution grid in accordance with the recommendations of Horálek et al. (2010). The supplemented JRC-Geostat 2018 data (as described above) are used in all the calculations.

National population totals presented in the exposure tables of this paper are based on Eurostat national population data for 2022 (Eurostat, 2024). For France, Portugal and Spain, the population totals of areas outside the mapping area (i.e. French overseas departments Azores, Madeira and Canarias) are subtracted. For Andorra, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Monaco, San Marino and Faroe Islands with no data for 2022 in the Eurostat database, the population totals are based on UN (2024), as well as for Cyprus (as Eurostat does not include the population of the northern part of Cyprus).

Land cover

CORINE Land Cover 2018 (CLC2018) – 100 m resolution, Version 2020_20 is used (EU, 2020). For Andorra that is missing in this database, World Land Cover at 30m resolution from MDAUS BaseVue 2013 (MDA, 2015) resampled to 100m resolution is used. For area that are neither included in the CLC2018 nor in the World Land Cover database (i.e. Jan Mayen and some border areas), ESA Climate Change Initiative Global Land Cover for 2018 (ESA, 2019) is used, resampled to 100m resolution.

In agreement with Horálek et al. (2017b), the 44 CLC classes have been re-grouped into the 8 more general classes. In this paper four of these general classes are used, see Table A2.2.

Table A2.2 General land cover classes, based on CLC2018 classes, used in mapping

Label	General class description	CLC classes grid codes	CLC classes codes	CLC classes description
HDR	High density residential areas	1	111	Continuous urban fabric
LDR	Low density residential areas	2	112	Discontinuous urban fabric
AGR	Agricultural areas	12-22	211-244	Agricultural areas
NAT	Natural areas	23-34	311-335	Forest and semi natural areas

Two aggregations are used, i.e. into 1 km resolution grid and into the circle with radius of 5 km. For each general CLC class, the high land use resolution is spatially aggregated into the 1 km EEA standard grid resolution. The aggregated grid square value represents for each general class the total area of this class as percentage of the total 1 km x 1 km area. For details, see Horálek et al. (2017b).

Road type vector data

GRIP (Meijer et al., 2018) vector road type data provided by the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL) are used for the weighting procedure of the urban background and the urban traffic map layers (Annex 1, Section A1.1). The road types are distributed into 5 classes, from highways to local roads and streets. In agreement with Horálek et al. (2017b), road classes No. 1 “Highways”, No. 2 “Primary roads” and No. 3 “Secondary roads” are used.

Percentage of the area influenced by traffic is represented by buffers around the roads: for the individual classes 1-3 and for classes 1-3 together, at all 1 km x 1 km grid cells; a buffer of 75 metres distance at each side from each road vector is taken for the roads of classes 1 and 2, while a buffer of 50 metres is taken for the roads of class 3. For details, see Horálek et al. (2017b).

Satellite data

The annual average NO₂ dataset was constructed based on data from the Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) onboard of the Sentinel-5 Precursor satellite (Veefkind et al., 2012). All available swath-based Level-2 data with an irregular pixel geometry was acquired for the year 2022. The spatial resolution of the product is cc. 5.5 km by 3.5 km. The product used is the S5P_OFFL_L2_NO2 product (van Geffen et al., 2019, 2020) and it provides the tropospheric vertical column density of NO₂, i.e. a vertically integrated value over the entire troposphere. All overpasses for a specific day were then mosaicked using HARP (<https://stcorp.github.io/harp/doc/html/index.html>) and retrievals with a quality assurance values greater than 0.75 (indicating high quality and cloud-free conditions) were gridded to a regular projected grid for all area with a 1 km spatial resolution in a ETRS89 / ETRS-LAEA (EPSG 3035) projection. The daily gridded files were subsequently averaged to an annual mean. I.e. the parameter used is

NO₂ – annual average tropospheric vertical column density (VCD) [number of NO₂ molecules per cm² of earth surface], year 2022 (aggregated from cloud-free high-quality daily data).

Soil hydraulic properties data

JRC data called "Maps of indicators of soil hydraulic properties for Europe" in 1 km resolution are used for POD calculations, JRC (2016). Namely the following indicators are used:

Wilting Point – water content at wilting point [cm³/cm³],
Field Capacity – water content at field capacity [cm³/cm³].

Annex 3

Technical details and mapping uncertainties

This annex contains technical details on the linear regression models and the residual kriging as used in the mapping. Furthermore, uncertainty estimates for the maps of the indicators are given.

A3.1 PM₁₀

Technical details on the mapping and uncertainty estimates for both PM₁₀ indicators maps annual average (Map 2.1) and 90.4 percentile of daily means (Map 2.3) are presented in this section.

Technical details on the mapping

Table A3.1 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models (c , a_1 , a_2 , ...) and of the residual kriging (nugget, sill, range) and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging, for both PM₁₀ indicators. The linear regression and ordinary kriging of its residuals are applied on the logarithmically transformed data of both measurement and modelled PM₁₀ values. In Table A3.1 the standard error and variogram parameters (nugget, sill and range) refer to these transformed data, whereas RMSE and bias refer to the interpolation after a back-transformation. Since 2017 maps, an updated methodology as developed and tested under Horálek et al. (2019) has been used, i.e. including land cover among the supplementary data and using the traffic urban map layer.

The adjusted R^2 and standard error are indicators for the fit of the regression relationship, where the adjusted R^2 should be as close to 1 as possible and the standard error should be as small as possible. The adjusted R^2 for the rural areas was 0.64 at both the annual average and the 90.4 percentile of daily means (P90.4); for the urban background areas 0.31 at both the annual average and the P90.4; for the urban traffic areas 0.42 at the annual average and 0.31 at the P90.4.

Table A3.1 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of PM₁₀ indicators annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means for 2022 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for the final combined map

		Annual average			90.4 percentile of daily means		
		Rural areas	Urb. b. ar.	Urb. tr. ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb. b. ar.	Urb. tr. ar.
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	1.34	1.05	1.75	0.96	1.22	2.46
	a_1 (log. CAMS model)	0.811	0.752	0.55	0.801	0.736	0.42
	a_2 (altitude GMTED)	-0.00010			-0.00012		
	a_3 (wind speed)	<i>non signif.</i>		-0.046	-0.03687		-0.073
	a_4 (relative humidity)	-0.010			<i>non signif.</i>		
	a_5 (land cover NAT)	-0.0013			-0.0014		
	Adjusted R^2	0.64	0.31	0.42	0.64	0.31	0.31
	Stand. Error [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	0.24	0.32	0.26	0.23	0.33	0.29
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	Nugget	0.020	0.020	0.018	0.018	0.021	0.022
	Sill	0.048	0.047	0.036	0.040	0.056	0.044
	Range [km]	1000	130	330	1000	130	330
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	4.0	6.2	5.0	7.8	11.6	9.5
	Relative RMSE [%]	26.1	27.4	22.6	29.5	29.8	25.0
	Bias (MPE) [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.2	0.0	-0.2

RMSE (the smaller the better) and bias (the closer to zero the better), highlighted by orange, are the cross-validation indicators, showing the quality of the resulting map. The bias indicates to what extent the predictions are under- or overestimated on average. Further in this section, more detailed uncertainty analysis is presented.

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Using RMSE as the most common indicator, the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map at areas 'in between' the station measurements (i.e. at locations without measurements, as long as they are within the area covered by the measurements) can be expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Table A3.1 shows that the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of PM_{10} annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means expressed by RMSE is $4.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $7.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the rural areas, $6.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $11.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the urban background areas, and $5.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $9.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the urban traffic areas, respectively. Alternatively, one can express this uncertainty in relative terms by relating the absolute RMSE uncertainty to the mean air pollution indicator value for all stations. This relative mean uncertainty (Relative RMSE) of the final combined map of PM_{10} annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means is 26.1 % and 29.5 % for rural areas, 27.4 % and 29.8 % for urban background areas, and 22.6 % and 25.0 % for urban traffic areas, respectively. These quite high numbers in urban background areas compared to previous years up to 2015 are caused by inclusion of Türkiye since 2016 mapping. For the mapping results without Türkiye, the relative mean uncertainty is 19.6 % and 20.1 % for rural areas, 19.5 % and 22.3 % for urban background areas and 18.4 % and 19.7 % for urban traffic areas, respectively. Nevertheless, the relative uncertainty values including Türkiye fulfil the data quality objectives for models as set in Annex I of the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

Figure A3.1 shows the cross-validation scatter plots, obtained according to Annex 1, Section A1.4 for rural, urban background and urban traffic areas, for both PM_{10} indicators. The R^2 indicates that the variability is attributable to the interpolation for about 65 % and 57 % at the rural areas, for 66 % and 65 % at the urban background areas, and for about 70 % and 67 % at the urban traffic areas, for the annual average and the 90.4 percentile of daily means, respectively.

Figure A3.1 Correlation between cross-validated predicted (y-axis) and measurement values for PM_{10} indicators annual average (top) and 90.4 percentile of daily means (bottom) for 2022 for rural (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) areas

The trend line in the scatter-plots deviates at the lowest values somewhat above, and at higher values below the symmetry axis, indicating that the interpolation methods tend to underestimate the high concentrations and overestimate the low concentrations. For example, in urban background areas for annual average an observed value of 40 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolations to be about 35 µg/m³, about 12 % lower. This underestimation at high values is common to all spatial interpolation methods. It could be reduced by either using a higher number of stations with an improved spatial distribution, or by introducing an improved regression that uses either other supplementary data or more advanced chemical transport model (resp. model in finer resolution).

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

In addition to the above point observation – point prediction cross-validation, a simple comparison has been made between the point observation values and interpolated prediction values spatially averaged at grid cells. This point observation – grid averaged prediction comparison indicates to what extent the predicted value of a grid cell represents the corresponding measurement values at stations located in that cell. The comparison has been made primarily for the separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers at 1 km resolution. (One can directly relate this comparison result to the cross-validation results of Figure A3.1). Apart from this, the comparison has been done also for the final combined maps at the same 1 km resolution. Figure A3.2 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons, for PM₁₀ annual average only as an illustration. The results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.1 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation for separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers, and for the final combined maps are summarised in Table A3.2 for both PM₁₀ indicators.

Figure A3.2 Correlation between predicted grid values from rural (upper left), urban background (upper middle) and urban traffic (upper right) map layer and final combined map (all bottom) (y-axis) versus measurements from rural (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) for PM₁₀ annual average 2022

Table A3.2 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from separate (rural, urban background or urban traffic) map layers and final combined map versus the measurement point values for rural (upper left), urban background (upper right) and urban traffic (bottom left) stations for PM₁₀ indicators annual average (top) and 90.4 percentile of daily means (bottom) for 2022

PM ₁₀	Rural backgr. stations				Urban/suburban backgr. stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Annual average								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	4.0	-0.1	0.654	y = 0.626x + 5.6	6.2	0.0	0.664	y = 0.729x + 6.1
grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	2.7	-0.3	0.854	y = 0.742x + 3.7	3.7	-0.1	0.861	y = 0.789x + 4.5
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	3.4	0.2	0.760	y = 0.818x + 3.0	3.9	0.0	0.867	y = 0.831x + 3.8
90.4 percentile of daily means								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	7.8	-0.2	0.572	y = 0.573x + 11.1	11.6	0.0	0.650	y = 0.709x + 11.3
grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	5.4	-0.5	0.816	y = 0.698x + 7.5	6.6	-0.1	0.891	y = 0.825x + 6.7
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	6.1	0.3	0.742	y = 0.770x + 6.5	6.8	0.0	0.879	y = 0.826x + 6.75
PM ₁₀	Urban/suburban traffic stations							
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation				
Annual average								
cross-valid. prediction, urban traffic map layer	5.0	0.1	0.697	y = 0.810x + 4.4				
grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	3.7	-0.1	0.825	y = 0.791x + 4.6				
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	5.2	-2.5	0.727	y = 0.729x + 3.6				
90.4 percentile of daily means								
cross-valid. prediction, urban traffic map layer	9.5	-0.2	0.673	y = 0.681x + 11.9				
grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	7.6	-0.1	0.791	y = 0.746x + 9.5				
grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	10.6	-4.2	0.656	y = 0.668x + 8.4				

By comparing the scatterplots and the statistical indicators for the separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers with the final combined map, one can evaluate the level of representation of the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas in the final combined map. Both the rural and the urban air quality are fairly well represented in the 1 km final combined map, while the traffic air quality is underestimated in this spatial resolution. One can conclude that the final combined map in 1 km resolution is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas.

The Table A3.2 shows a better relation (i.e. lower RMSE, higher R², smaller intercept and slope closer to 1) between station measurements and the interpolated values of the corresponding grid cells at either rural, urban background or urban traffic areas than it does at the point cross-validation predictions. That is because the simple comparison between point measurements and the gridded interpolated values shows the uncertainty at the actual station locations (points), while the point cross-validation prediction simulates the behaviour of the interpolation at point positions assuming no actual measurement would exist at that point. The uncertainty at measurement locations is introduced partly by the smoothing effect of the interpolation and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 1 km grid cells. The level of the smoothing effect leading to underestimation at areas with high values is there smaller than in situations where no measurement is represented in such areas. For example, in urban background areas the predicted interpolation gridded annual average value in the separate urban background map will be about 36 µg/m³ at the corresponding station with the measurement value of 40 µg/m³. This means an underestimation of about 10 %. It is a slightly less than the prediction underestimation of 12 % at the same point location, when leaving out this one actual measurement point and the interpolation is done without this station (see the previous subsection).

A3.2 PM_{2.5}

Technical details and uncertainty estimates for Map 2.5 with the PM_{2.5} annual average are presented in this section.

Technical details on the mapping

Like for PM₁₀, an updated methodology as developed and tested under Horálek et al. (2019) has been used, i.e. including the land cover among supplementary data and using the traffic urban map layer.

Table A3.3 presents the regression coefficients determined for pseudo PM_{2.5} stations data estimation, based on the 1145 rural and urban/suburban background and 430 urban/suburban traffic stations that have both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measurements available (see Section 2.1.1).

Table A3.3 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model for generating pseudo PM_{2.5} annual average data for 2022 in rural and urban background (left) and urban traffic (right) areas

PM _{2.5} , Annual average		Rural and urban background areas	Urban traffic areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.1)	c (constant)	35.7	58.7
	b (PM ₁₀ measurement data)	0.654	0.487
	a1 (surface solar radiation)	-0.004	-0.006
	a2 (latitude)	-0.421	-0.755
	a3 (longitude)	0.094	0.124
	Adjusted R²	0.83	0.76
Standard Error [µg.m⁻³]	1.9	2.2	

Due to sufficient data coverage of PM_{2.5} measurements in urban background areas in some countries, the pseudo PM_{2.5} stations have not been used in urban background areas of these countries. This refers to Austria, Czechia, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Slovenia and Slovakia. Table A3.4 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models (c, a₁, a₂,...) and of the residual kriging (nugget, sill, range) and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging of its residuals.

Table A3.4 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of PM_{2.5} annual average 2022 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for final combined map

PM _{2.5}		Annual average		
		Rural areas	Urban b. areas	Urban tr. areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	0.79	0.72	0.73
	a1 (log. CAMS model)	0.765	0.751	0.739
	a2 (altitude GMTED)	-0.00030		
	a3 (wind speed)	-0.058		
	a4 (land cover NAT1)	-0.0010		
	Adjusted R²	0.65	0.43	0.62
Standard Error [µg.m⁻³]	0.26	0.30	0.24	
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	nugget	0.025	0.027	0.008
	sill	0.065	0.062	0.052
	range [km]	1000	230	1000
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [µg.m⁻³]	2.6	3.2	2.2
	Relative RMSE [%]	27.9	25.1	19.5
	Bias (MPE) [µg.m⁻³]	0.0	0.1	-0.1

The same supplementary data as in Horálek et al. (2019) has been used. Like in the case of PM₁₀, the linear regression is applied on the logarithmically transformed data of both measurement and

modelled PM_{2.5} values. Thus, the standard error and variogram parameters refer to these transformed data, whereas RMSE and bias refer to the interpolation after the back-transformation.

The adjusted R² and standard error are indicators for the quality of the fit of the regression relation. The adjusted R² is 0.65 for the rural areas, 0.43 for urban background areas and 0.62 for urban traffic areas. Quite weaker regression relation in the urban background areas causes a higher impact of the interpolation part of the interpolation-regression-merging mapping methodology in these areas.

RMSE and bias – highlighted in orange – are the cross-validation indicators, showing the quality of the resulting map; the bias indicates to what extent the predictions are under- or overestimated on average. Only stations with PM_{2.5} measurement data are used for calculating the RMSE and the bias (i.e. the pseudo PM_{2.5} stations are not used). These statistical indicators are calculated excluding the pseudo stations because they are estimated values only, not actual measurement values. According to Denby et al (2011), the pseudo PM_{2.5} data does not satisfy the quality objectives for fixed monitoring alone. The pseudo stations are used as they improve the mapping estimate, whereas the actual measurements can be used for evaluating the quality of the map. For the future, it will be considered to quit the application of the PM_{2.5} pseudo stations as the current number of the actual PM_{2.5} measurement stations has increased over time such that the use of pseudo PM_{2.5} stations may not contribute enough any longer to improve the mapping estimates.

Due to the lack of rural stations in Türkiye for PM_{2.5}, no proper interpolation results could be presented for this country in a rural map, so the estimated PM_{2.5} values for Türkiye are not presented in the final map. Thus, the stations located in Türkiye have not been used in the uncertainty estimates (although used in the mapping process), as they lie outside the mapping area.

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Table A3.4 shows that the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of PM_{2.5} annual average expressed as RMSE is 2.6 µg/m³ for the rural areas, 3.2 µg/m³ for the urban background areas and 2.2 µg/m³ for the urban traffic areas. On the other hand, the relative mean uncertainty (Relative RMSE) of the final combined map of PM_{2.5} annual average is 28 % for rural areas, 25 % for urban background areas and 20 % for urban traffic areas. These relative uncertainty values fulfil the data quality objectives for models as set in Annex I of the Air Quality Directive (EC, 2008).

Figure A3.3 shows the cross-validation scatter plots, obtained according to Section A1.3, for different area types. The R² indicates that about 69 % of the variability is attributable to the interpolation for both the rural and the urban background areas and 77 % for the urban traffic areas.

The scatter plots indicate that in areas with high concentrations the interpolation methods tend to underestimate the levels. E.g., in urban background areas an observed value of 25 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolations to be about 22 µg/m³, which is an underestimated prediction of about 11 %. This underestimation at high values is an inherent feature of all spatial interpolations. It could be reduced by either using a higher number of the stations at improved spatial distribution, or by introducing a closer regression that uses either other supplementary data or more improved CTM output.

Figure A3.3 Correlation between cross-validated predicted and measurement values for PM_{2.5} annual average 2022 for rural (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) areas

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

Like for PM₁₀, a simple comparison has been made between the point observation values and interpolated prediction values spatially averaged in grid cells, in addition to the cross-validation. The comparison has been made primarily for the separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers at 1 km resolution. Next to this, the comparison has been done also for the final combined maps at the same 1 km resolution. Figure A3.4 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure A3.4 Correlation between predicted grid values from rural (upper left), urban background (upper middle) and urban traffic (upper right) map layer and final combined map (all bottom) (y-axis) versus measurements from rural (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) for PM_{2.5} annual average 2022

The results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.3 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation Figure A3.4 for separate map layers and for the final combined map are summarised in Table A3.5.

By comparing the scatterplots and the statistical indicators for separate rural, urban background and urban traffic map layers with the final combined maps, one can evaluate the level of representation of the rural, urban background and urban traffic areas in the final combined map. Similar results as for PM₁₀ can be observed: the final combined map in 1 km resolution is fairly well representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas.

Like in the case of PM₁₀, Table A3.5 shows a better correlated relation with the station measurements for the simply interpolated gridded values than for the point cross-validation predictions, at all area types. That is because the simple comparison shows the uncertainty at the actual station locations, while the cross-validation prediction simulates the behaviour in the areas with no measurements (within the area covered by measurements).

The uncertainty at measurement locations is introduced partly by the smoothing effect of the interpolation and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 1 km x 1 km grid cells. For example, in urban background areas the predicted interpolation gridded value in the final map will be about 23 µg/m³ at the corresponding station with the measurement value of 25 µg/m³ (calculated based on the linear regression equation), which coincides with an underestimation of about 9 %.

Table A3.5 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from separate (rural, urban background or urban traffic) map layers and final combined map versus the measurement point values for rural (upper left), urban background (upper right) and urban traffic (bottom left) stations for PM_{2.5} annual average 2022

PM _{2.5} , Annual average	Rural backgr. stations				Urban/suburban backgr. stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	2.6	0.0	0.689	y = 0.703x + 2.7	3.2	0.1	0.685	y = 0.762x + 3.1
Grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	1.8	-0.2	0.838	y = 0.767x + 1.9	2.1	0.0	0.845	y = 0.826x + 2.2
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final merged map	1.9	0.0	0.825	y = 0.785x + 1.9	2.2	0.0	0.831	y = 0.820x + 2.2

PM _{2.5} , Annual average	Urban/suburban traffic stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-val. prediction, urban traffic map layer	2.2	-0.1	0.767	y = 0.744x + 2.8
Grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	1.7	0.1	0.859	y = 0.856x + 1.8
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final merged map	2.1	-0.5	0.803	y = 0.830x + 1.5

A3.3 Ozone

In this section, the technical details and the uncertainty estimates are presented for the maps of ozone health-related indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, SOMO35 and SOMO10 (Maps 3.1, 3.3-3.5), as well as for the maps of ozone vegetation-related indicators AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests (Maps 3.7 and 3.8). Next to this, the details of POD_v (i.e. POD₆ and POD₁) maps are presented.

Technical details on the mapping

Table A3.6 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models and of the residual kriging, including the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging.

The adjusted R² and standard error show the quality of the fit of the regression relation. For the rural areas, all indicators show the value of the adjusted R² between 0.48 and 0.65. For the urban areas, the adjusted R² is in between 0.35 and 0.44 for all indicators apart from SOMO10, for which it is 0.16. For the vegetation-related indicators the urban maps are not constructed. RMSE and bias – highlighted by orange – are the cross-validation indicators, showing the quality of the resulting map.

Table A3.6 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hourly means, peak season average of maximum daily 8-hourly means, SOMO35 and SOMO10 in rural and urban areas and for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation and for forests in rural areas for 2022

		93.2 perc.		Peak seas. avg		SOMO35		SOMO10		AOT40v	AOT40f
		Rur. ar.	Urb. ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb.ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb.ar.	Rur. ar.	Urb.ar.	Rur. ar.	Rur. ar.
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	-22.1	11.3	-7.2	20.5	430	3261	1685	5810	-2164	-1215
	a1 (CAM5 model)	1.31	1.08	1.12	0.88	1.04	0.73	0.91	0.68	1.28	1.14
	a2 (altit. GMTED)	0.0150		0.0117		2.92		3.48		8.38	14.16
	a3 (wind speed)		-4.32		-3.12		-622.0		-211.1		
	a4 (s. solar rad.)	<i>n.sign.</i>	1.1	1.4							
	Adjusted R²	0.55	0.44	0.56	0.35	0.58	0.39	0.48	0.16	0.65	0.62
	St. Err. [µg/m³·x]*	9.7	13.2	7.5	11.4	1566	1847	2471	3458	5680	9232
Ord. krig. (OK) of LRM	Nugget	21	40	13	30	9.0E+05	1.4E+06	2.7E+06	2.4E+06	9.0E+06	2.4E+07
	Sill	60	94	35	63	2.1E+06	2.2E+06	5.0E+06	5.4E+06	2.6E+07	6.7E+07
	Range [km]	180	110	160	380	280	110	280	110	280	280
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [µg/m³·x]*	8.8	10.9	7.0	9.2	1461	1579	2346	2740	5102	8258
	Rel. RMSE [%]	7.7	9.8	7.3	10.1	25.3	32.8	10.8	14.2	31.3	30.2
	Bias [µg/m³·x]*	0.2	0.0	0.1	-0.1	12	-3	7	-4	82	104

* Units: 93.2 percentile of daily 8-h maximums and peak season average of daily 8-h maximums: [µg/m³], SOMO35 and SOMO10: [µg/m³·d], AOT40v and AOT40f: [µg/m³·h].

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

The basic uncertainty analysis is provided by cross-validation. Table A3.6 shows both absolute and relative mean uncertainty, expressed by RMSE and Relative RMSE. The relative mean uncertainty of the 2022 ozone map is around 7-11 % for the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-h means and the peak season average of maximum daily 8-h means, around 25-33 % for SOMO35, around 11-15 % for SOMO10 and around 30-31 % at AOT40 indicators. The small levels of the relative uncertainty for the 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-h means, the peak season indicator and SOMO10 are highly influenced by the low ratio between the relevant standard error and mean calculated based on all annual station concentration data: for these three indicators the ratio is at the level of about 0.11-0.20, while for SOMO35 and for both AOT40 indicators it is at the level of about 0.42-0.58.

Figure A3.5 shows the cross-validation scatter plots for both the rural and urban areas of the 2022 map for the health-related ozone indicators. Based on the R², one can see that for the health-related ozone indicators, about 48-63 % of the variability is attributable to the interpolation. The scatter plots indicate that the higher values are underestimated and the lower values somewhat overestimated by the interpolation method; a typical smoothing effect inherent to the interpolation method with the linear regression and its residuals kriging. For example, in the case of the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-h maximums, in urban areas (Figure A3.5, upper right panel) an observed value of 150 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolation as 136 µg/m³, which is 9 % lower. Or, in the case of SOMO35, in rural areas (Figure A3.5, lower middle left panel) an observed value of 9 000 µg/m³·d is estimated in the interpolation as about 7 900 µg/m³·d, which is 13 % lower. In addition, an overestimation at the lower end of predicted values occurred. One could reduce this under- and overestimation by extending the number of measurement stations and by optimising the spatial distribution of those stations, specifically in areas with elevated values over years.

Figure A3.5 Correlation between cross-validated predicted (y-axis) and measurement values for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hourly means (top), peak season average of maximum daily 8-hourly means (higher middle), SOMO35 (lower middle) and SOMO10 (bottom) for 2022 for rural (left) and urban (right) areas

Figure A3.6 shows the cross-validation scatter plots of the AOT40 for both vegetation and forests. R^2 indicates that about 72 % of the variability is attributable to the interpolation in the case of AOT40 for vegetation, while for AOT40 for forests it is about 70 %. The cross-validation scatter plots show again that in areas with higher accumulated ozone concentrations the interpolation methods tend to deliver underestimated predicted values. For example, in agricultural areas (Figure A3.6, left panel) an observed value of 25 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$ is estimated in the interpolation as about 23 000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{h}$, i.e. an underestimation of about 8 %.

Figure A3. Correlation between cross-validated predicted (y-axis) and measurement values for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation (left) and AOT40 for forests (right) for 2022 for rural areas

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

In addition to the above point observation – point prediction cross-validation, a simple comparison has been made between the point observation values and interpolated predicted grid values.

For health-related indicators, the comparison has been made primarily for the separate rural and separate urban background maps at 10 km resolution. (One can directly relate this comparison result to the cross-validation of the previous section.) Next to this, the comparison has been done also for the final combined maps at 1 km resolution.

Figure A3.7 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons, for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means only, as an illustration. The results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.5 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation for the separate rural and the separate urban background map, and for the final combined maps are summarised in Table A3.7. By comparing the scatterplots and the statistical indicators for the separate rural and separate urban background map with the final combined maps, one can again evaluate the level of representation of the rural resp. urban background areas in the final combined maps. Both the rural and the urban air quality are fairly well represented in the 1 km x1 km final combined map.

The uncertainty of the map layers at measurement locations is caused partly by the smoothing effect of interpolation and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 10 km x 10 km grid cells. The level of smoothing, which leads to underestimation in areas with high values, is weaker in areas where measurements exist than in areas where a measurement point is not available. For example, in the case of the 93.2 percentile of daily 8-h maximums, in urban areas an observed value of 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is estimated in the interpolation as about 142 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, which is about 5 % lower. It is less than the cross-validation underestimation of 9 % at the same point location, when leaving out this one actual measurement point and the interpolation without this station is done (see the previous subsection).

Figure A3.6 Correlation between predicted grid values from rural (upper left) and urban (bottom left) 10 km resolution and final combined 1 km resolution (both right) map (y-axis) versus measurements from rural (top) or urban/suburban (bottom) background stations (x-axis) for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of daily maximum 8-hourly means for 2022

Table A3.7 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted point values based on cross-validation and the predicted grid values from separate (rural resp. urban) 10 km resolution and final merged 1 km resolution map versus the measurement point values for rural (left) and urban (right) background stations for ozone indicators 93.2 percentile of daily max 8h means (top), peak season average of daily max 8h means (higher middle), SOMO35 (lower middle) and SOMO10 (bottom) for 2022

Ozone	rural backgr. stations				urban/suburban backgr. stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
93.2 percentile of daily max. 8-hour means								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	8.8	0.2	0.625	y = 0.659x + 39.52	10.9	0.0	0.616	y = 0.640x + 40.02
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	4.5	0.3	0.910	y = 0.827x + 20.24	6.5	-0.2	0.869	y = 0.794x + 22.75
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	5.7	-0.6	0.849	y = 0.788x + 23.83	7.5	0.2	0.820	y = 0.789x + 23.67
Peak season average of daily max. 8-hour means								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	7.0	0.1	0.618	y = 0.635x + 35.24	9.2	-0.1	0.570	y = 0.593x + 37.36
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	3.9	0.2	0.889	y = 0.796x + 19.80	7.0	-0.2	0.757	y = 0.691x + 28.22
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	4.5	-0.8	0.849	y = 0.778x + 20.58	7.6	0.2	0.712	y = 0.693x + 28.41
SOMO35								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	1461	12	0.630	y = 0.646x + 2059	1579	-3	0.556	y = 0.574x + 2049
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	947	34	0.852	y = 0.771x + 1353	1174	-38	0.762	y = 0.684x + 1481
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	1091	-153	0.805	y = 0.730x + 1406	1233	40	0.732	y = 0.683x + 1566
SOMO10								
cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	2346	7	0.531	y = 0.530x + 10221	2740	-4	0.476	y = 0.496x + 9730
grid prediction, 10 km resol.separ. (r or ub) map layer	1651	14	0.783	y = 0.673x + 7130	1717	-53	0.811	y = 0.694x + 5856
grid prediction, 1 km resolution final merged map	1838	-331	0.731	y = 0.647x + 7341	1929	73	0.744	y = 0.688x + 6098

Table A3.8 presents the results of the point observation – point prediction cross-validation of Figure A3.6 and those of the point-grid validation for the rural map, for vegetation related indicators AOT40 for vegetation and AOT40 for forests. Again, one can see for both indicators a better correlation between the station measurements and the averaged interpolated predicted values of the corresponding grid cells, than at the point cross-validation predictions, of Figure A3.6.

Table A3.8 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for predicted point values based on cross-validation and predicted grid values from rural 2 km resolution map versus measurement point values for rural background stations for ozone indicators AOT40 for vegetation (top) and forests (bottom) for 2022

Ozone	rural backgr. stations			
	RMSE	bias	R ²	linear regression equation
AOT40 for vegetation				
cross-valid. prediction, rural map	5102	82	0.716	y = 0.756x + 4064
grid prediction, 2 km resolution rural map	2808	20	0.915	y = 0.873x + 2082
AOT40 for forests				
cross-valid. prediction, rural map	8258	104	0.699	y = 0.731x + 7440
grid prediction, 2 km resolution rural map	4654	32	0.907	y = 0.856x + 3969

Details of POD_γ maps

POD₆ maps have been calculated using the ozone based on the hourly ozone rural maps, hourly meteorological data and soil hydraulic properties data, according to the methodology described in Annex 1, Section A1.3.

The hourly ozone maps needed for POD_γ (i.e. POD₆ and POD₁) calculation have been calculated at the 2 km resolution, based on rural background measurements. The maps for each hour of the year 2022 have been constructed using the same methodology as for the annual maps, i.e. the multiple linear regression followed by the kriging of its residuals (see Annex 1, Section A1.1) based on the measurement data, CAMS-ENS Forecast model output, altitude and the surface solar radiation. Table A3.9 presents the summary results of the RMSE, RRMSE and bias for the whole year, based on the annual average and percentiles of these three statistics. For bias, annual sum is also shown in addition.

Table A3.9 Annual statistics average, 2nd percentile, 25th percentile, 50th percentile (median), 75th percentile, 98th percentile and sum (where relevant) for average ozone concentration, number of stations considered, and cross-validation parameters RMSE, RRMSE and Bias of hourly ozone maps, 1.1.2022-31.12.2022. Units: µg/m³ apart from N and RRMSE.

	Rural background areas						Sum
	avg	p2	p25	p50	p75	p98	
N	517	489	513	519	524	531	
avg	63.3	33.7	48.5	61.5	75.5	103.2	
RMSE	16.0	10.4	13.7	15.5	18.0	23.7	
RRMSE	27.5%	13.3%	19.1%	27.0%	34.6%	48.6%	
Bias	-0.01	-0.48	-0.12	-0.02	0.09	0.49	-97

Figure A3.8 and A3.9 presents the averages of the cross-validation indicators Bias and RMSE in the individual hours of the year 2022.

Figure A3.8 Cross-validation statistical indicator Bias of hourly ozone maps, average at rural background stations, 1.1.2022-31.12.2022

Figure A3.9 Cross-validation statistical indicator RMSE of hourly ozone maps, average at rural background stations, 1.1.2022-31.12.2022

In the POD_Y calculations, the module to estimate phytotoxic ozone doses from a given atmospheric ozone exposure developed by INERIS and adapted by CHMI has been used.

During the POD_Y maps calculation, different biogeographical regions were considered. Plant stomatal functioning varies per plant species and can vary by biogeographical region, reflecting different adaptations of plants to climate and soil water in these regions. Parametrization for POD_6 (i.e. for wheat, potato and tomato) is currently available for all different biogeographic regions of Europe apart from Alpine region, i.e. for Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Steppic, and Mediterranean regions (CLRTAP, 2017a). In the case of wheat, the parametrization is the same for most of these regions (namely Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, and Steppic), while for Mediterranean regions is different. For Alpine region, the parametrization of the Continental and several other regions are used. For potato and tomato, only one parametrization exists – in the case of potato, the

parametrisation is set for all regions apart from the Alpine one, while for tomato for the Mediterranean region only (see Table 1.2). In the calculations, the existing parametrisation has been applied for the entire mapping area. Parametrization for POD_1 for spruce is available for all biogeographical regions apart from the Mediterranean, Anatolian and Black Sea ones.

The values calculated in $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ resolution were converted into the standard ETRS89-LAEA5210 projection and transferred into the EEA 2 km resolution grid.

A3.4 NO_2 and NO_x

In this section, the technical details and the uncertainty estimates for the maps of NO_2 annual average and NO_x annual average, for Maps 4.1 and 4.3, are presented.

Technical details on the mapping

In agreement with Horálek et al. (2007) and Annex 1, the NO_x measurements are supplemented by the so-called pseudo NO_x stations. The pseudo NO_x data are calculated based on the NO_2 data, using quadratic regression Eq. A1.2a. The regression coefficients were estimated based on 381 rural background stations with both NO_x and NO_2 measurements (see Annex 1, Section A1.1). The estimated coefficients of Eq. A1.2 are: $a = 0.0198$, $b = 1.076$, $c = 0.46$. Adjusted R^2 is 0.95, the standard error is $1.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Table A3.10 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models and of the residual kriging and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging. Only stations with actual measurement data of the relevant pollutant (i.e. not the pseudo stations) have been used for calculating the cross-validation parameters RMSE and bias.

Table A3.10 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of NO_2 annual average for 2022 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for the final combined map (left) and NO_x annual average for 2022 in rural areas (right)

		NO_2 Annual average			NO_x Annual average
		Rural areas	Urb. b. areas	Urb. tr. areas	Rural areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	5.3	13.9	22.21	-3.2
	a1 (CAMS model)	0.339	<i>non signif.</i>	<i>non signif.</i>	0.839
	a2 (altitude)	<i>non signif.</i>		<i>non signif.</i>	-0.0034
	a3 (altitude_5km_radius)	<i>non signif.</i>		<i>non signif.</i>	
	a4 (wind speed)	-0.75	-2.18	-2.63	-1.09
	a5 (solar radiation)				0.003
	a6 (satellite TROPOMI)	1.02	1.94	1.88	
	a7 (population*1000)	0.00166	0.00033		
	a8 (NAT_1km)		-0.0427		
	a9 (AGR_1km)		-0.0195		
	a10 (TRAF_1km)		0.0695		
	a11 (LDR_5km_radius)	<i>non signif.</i>	<i>non signif.</i>	0.0009	
	a12 (HDR_5km_radius)		0.0010	0.0033	
	a13 (NAT_5km_radius)	-0.00044			
	Adjusted R^2	0.63	0.46	0.34	0.48
	Standard Error [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	2.7	5.5	8.1	5.3
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	nugget	4	12	10	12
	sill	6	17	38	16
	range [km]	590	53	130	700
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	2.4	4.4	6.1	4.6
	Relative RMSE [%]	37.5	27.4	24.1	50.2
	Bias (MPE) [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Table A3.10 shows both absolute and relative mean uncertainty, expressed by RMSE and Relative RMSE. The absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of NO₂ annual average expressed as RMSE is 2.4 µg/m³ for the rural areas, 4.4 µg/m³ for the urban background areas and 6.1 µg/m³ for the urban traffic areas. For the NO_x rural map it is 4.6 µg/m³. The relative mean uncertainty of the NO₂ annual average map is 37.5 % for rural areas, 27 % for urban background areas and 24 % for urban traffic areas. The NO_x annual average rural map has a relative mean uncertainty of 50 %.

Figure A3.10 shows the point observation – point prediction cross-validation scatter plots for NO₂ annual average. The R² indicates that about 71 % of the variability is attributable to the interpolation for the rural areas, while for the urban background areas it is 65 % and for the urban traffic 63 %.

Figure A3.10 Correlation between cross-validated predicted and measurement values for NO₂ annual average 2022 for rural (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) areas

Like in the case of other pollutants, the cross-validation scatter plots show the underestimation of predictions at high concentrations at locations with no measurements. For example, in urban background areas an observed value of 40 µg/m³ is estimated in the interpolations to be about 33 µg/m³, which is an underestimated prediction of about 18 %.

Figure A3.11 shows the cross-validation scatter plot for NO_x annual average rural map. The R² indicates that about 59 % of the variability is attributable to the interpolation.

Figure A3.11 Correlation between cross-validated predicted and measurement values for NO_x annual average 2022 for rural areas

Comparison of point measurement values with the predicted grid value

Next to the above presented cross-validation, a simple comparison was made between the point observation values and interpolated predicted 1 km and 2 km grid values, respectively.

For NO₂ annual average, the comparison has been made primarily for the separate map layers at 1 km resolution. Besides, the comparison has been done also for the final combined map. Table A3.11 presents the results of this comparison, together with the results of cross-validation prediction of Figure A3.10. One can conclude that the final combined map in 1 km resolution is representative for rural and urban background areas, but not for urban traffic areas.

Table A3.11 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from separate (rural, urban background or urban traffic) map layers and final combined map versus the measurement point values for rural (upper left), urban background (upper right) and urban traffic (bottom left) stations for NO₂ annual average 2022

NO ₂ , Annual average	Rural backgr. stations				Urban/suburban backgr. stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-val. prediction, separate (r or ub) map layer	2.4	0.0	0.710	y = 0.723x + 1.7	4.4	0.0	0.653	y = 0.695x + 4.9
Grid prediction, 1 km res., separ. (r or ub) map layer	2.0	-0.2	0.796	y = 0.770x + 1.3	3.4	0.3	0.798	y = 0.777x + 3.9
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	2.5	0.4	0.722	y = 0.870x + 1.3	3.7	0.8	0.770	y = 0.825x + 3.6

NO ₂ , Annual average	Urban/suburban traffic stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Lin. r. equation
Cross-valid. prediction, urban traffic map layer	6.1	0.0	0.627	y = 0.668x + 8.5
Grid prediction, 1 km res., urban traffic map layer	3.8	0.1	0.861	y = 0.801x + 5.1
Grid prediction, 1 km res., final combined map	9.7	-7.1	0.575	y = 0.496x + 5.8

Table A3.12 presents the cross-validation results of Figure A3.11 and those of the point observation – grid averaged prediction validation for the rural map of NO_x annual average.

Table A3.12 Statistical indicators from the scatter plots for predicted point values based on cross-validation and predicted grid values from rural 2 km resolution map versus measurement point values for rural background stations for NO_x annual average 2022

NO _x	Rural background stations			
	RMSE	Bias	R ²	Linear regression equation
Cross-valid. prediction, rural map	4.6	0.1	0.588	y = 0.598x + 3.76
Grid prediction, 2 km resolution, rural map	4.0	0.1	0.686	y = 0.646x + 3.31

A3.5 BaP

In this section, the technical details and the uncertainty estimates for Map 5.1 of BaP annual average are presented.

Technical details on the mapping

The methodology as developed and tested in Horálek et al. (2022b) has been used. Table A3.13 presents the regression coefficients determined for pseudo BaP stations data estimates, based on the 344 rural and urban/suburban background that have both BaP and PM_{2.5} measurements available (see Annex 1 Section A1.1). Looking at the parameters of the regression, one can note that the adjusted R² of 0.76 is a relatively poor correlation. Based on this and in agreement with Horálek et al. (2022b), the pseudo stations have only been used in areas with a significant lack of the BaP measurements. The pseudo stations have been applied for countries and areas, as follows. For the rural areas: All the mapping area, apart from Austria, Benelux, Czechia, Germany, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, and Italy north of 44 degrees latitude. For the urban background areas: Iceland, Portugal, Scandinavia (including

Denmark), Greece and west Balkan countries (namely, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Northern Macedonia, and Serbia including Kosovo).

Table A3.13 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model for generating pseudo BaP annual average data for 2022 in rural and urban background areas

		Rural and urban background areas
Nonlinear regression model (NLRM, Eq. A1.2b)	c (constant)	-8.18
	a1 (PM _{2.5} annual average)	0.156
	a2 (latitude)	0.053
	a3 (longitude)	0.099
	a4 (land cover NAT_1km)	<i>n. sign.</i>
	a5 (land cover NAT_5km_r)	<i>n. sign.</i>
Adjusted R²		0.76
Standard Error [ng/m³]		

Table A3.14 presents the estimated parameters of the linear regression models (c, a₁, a₂,...) and of the residual kriging (nugget, sill, range) and includes the statistical indicators of both the regression and the kriging of its residuals. Almost the same supplementary data as in Horálek et al. (2022b) has been used. The only change was the use of the CHIMERE model results instead of the EMEP model output (see Section A2.2). Note that the domain of the CHIMERE model output does not cover Iceland. However, the EMEP model results for 2020 show a high correlation with the CHIMERE model results for 2022 in the points of stations (R²=0.85). Thus, an alternative BaP map using the EMEP model output for 2020 has been constructed for the whole domain and applied for the area of Iceland.

Table A3.14 Parameters and statistics of linear regression model and ordinary kriging of BaP annual average 2022 in rural, urban background and urban traffic areas for the final combined map

BaP		Annual average	
		Rural areas	Urban b. areas
Linear regression model (LRM, Eq. A1.3)	c (constant)	1.79	1.77
	a1 (log. CHIMERE model)	0.607	0.664
	a2 (altitude GMTED)	-0.00105	
	a3 (wind speed)	-0.200	
	a4 (temperature)	-0.132	-0.16
	a5 (land cover NAT_1km)	-0.0055	
Adjusted R²		0.46	0.56
Standard Error [ng/m³]		0.96	0.86
Ordinary kriging (OK) of LRM residuals	nugget	0.410	0.160
	sill	0.609	0.604
	range [km]	250	470
LRM + OK of its residuals	RMSE [ng/m³]	0.48	0.88
	Relative RMSE [%]	145.9	79.8
	Bias (MPE) [ng/m³]	0.04	0.03

The adjusted R² is 0.46 for the rural areas and 0.56 for urban background areas.

Uncertainty estimated by cross-validation

Table A3.14 shows that the absolute mean uncertainty of the final combined map of BaP annual average expressed as RMSE is 0.48 ng/m³ for the rural areas and 0.88 ng/m³ for the urban background areas. The RRMSE of this map is 145.9 % for rural areas and 79.8 % for urban background areas. The cross-validation relative uncertainty RRMSE is still at the considerably higher level (especially in the rural areas) compared to the 60%, being the data quality objective for the modelling uncertainty in the European directive (EC, 2004).

Annex 4

Concentration maps including stations

Throughout the report, the concentration maps presented do not include the concentration values measured at the stations. The reason is to better visualise the health-related indicators with their distinct concentration levels at the more fragmented and smaller urban areas.

As presented in Annex 3, the kriging interpolation methodology somewhat smooths the concentration field. Therefore, it is valuable to present in this Annex 4 the indicator maps including the concentration values resulting from the measurement data at the stations. These points provide important additional visual information on the smoothing effect caused by the interpolation. For instance, maps A4.1 and A4.2 present PM₁₀ indicators annual average and 90.4 percentile of daily means and include the stations points used in the interpolation. They correspond to Maps 2.1 and 2.3 of the main report, which do not have stations. Table A4.1 provides an overview of the maps in the main report and the corresponding maps including stations point values as presented in this annex.

Both the rural and the urban/suburban background stations and also urban/ traffic stations for PM and NO₂ are included in the maps of the health-related indicators, while the rural stations only are shown in the maps of vegetation related indicators. For PM_{2.5}, NO_x and BaP, only the stations with relevant measured data (i.e. not the pseudo stations) are presented.

Table A4.1 Overview of maps presented in this Annex 4 and their relationship with the maps presented in the main report

Air pollutant	Indicator	Map including stations	Map without stations
PM ₁₀	Annual average	A4.1	2.1
	90.4 percentile of daily means	A4.2	2.3
PM _{2.5}	Annual average	A4.3	2.5
Ozone	93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means	A4.4	3.1
	Peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means	A4.5	3.3
	SOMO35	A4.6	3.4
	SOMO10	A4.7	3.5
	AOT40 for vegetation ^(a)	A4.8	3.7
	AOT40 for forests ^(a)	A4.9	3.8
NO ₂	Annual average	A4.10	4.1
NO _x	Annual average ^(a)	A4.11	4.3
BaP	Annual average	A4.12	5.1

^(a) Rural map, applicable for rural areas only.

Map A4.1 Concentration map of PM₁₀ annual average including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.2 Concentration map of PM₁₀ indicator 90.4 percentile of daily means including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.3 Concentration map of PM_{2.5} annual average including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.4 Concentration map of ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.5 Concentration map of ozone peak season average of maximum daily 8-hour means, 2022

Map A4.6 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO35 including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.7 Concentration map of ozone indicator SOMO10 including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.8 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for vegetation including station measurement values, rural air quality, 2022

Map A4.9 Concentration map of ozone indicator AOT40 for forests including station measurement values, rural air quality, 2022

Map A4.10 Concentration map of NO₂ annual average including station measurement values, 2022

Map A4.11 Concentration map of NO_x annual average including station measurement values, rural air quality, 2022

Map A4.12 Concentration map of benzo(a)pyrene annual average including station measurement values, 2022, experimental map

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